

T-Factor MID-TERM EVALUATION REPORT

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| T-FACTOR

PARTICIPATORY FUTURES. REGENERATING CITIES WITH TEMPORARY USES

T-Factor is a Horizon 2020 Innovation project that seeks to unlock the transformative potential of temporary uses in urban regeneration.

Our mission is to build a full portfolio of tested innovations embracing design, organisation, management, governance, funding and regulatory aspects of temporary uses, so as to contribute to unlocking their transformative potential towards inclusive, sustainable and thriving cities.

We work across early stage and advanced regeneration projects in different European cities, leveraging international collaboration, co-creation and knowledge exchange to support the spread of temporary uses as viable tools for impactful urban regeneration.

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TERMINOLOGY NOTE

At European level, the topic of temporary uses in urban regeneration is a field of practice, policy making and research that still lacks consolidated concepts and terminology. The terms used to describe the reuse and reactivation of vacant, leftover and unused spaces in cities are many, such as 'temporary use', 'interim use', 'pop up use', 'transient use' and the more recent term 'meanwhile use'.

In this report, we mainly use terms such as 'temporary use', 'meanwhile use', 'meanwhile intervention' interchangeably to refer to temporary uses and activities developed within the context of regeneration plans and processes, focussing in particular on the period of time that stands in-between the approval of masterplans or pre-masterplans on the one hand, and the actual delivery of regenerated spaces and areas on the other hand.

GLOSSARY

/Temporary Use

Temporary use is a practice in urbanism aiming to revitalise empty spaces in urban areas, especially abandoned and decaying buildings. Many spaces are left empty by owners because they do not have plans for the space, no capital for its renovation, or cannot sell or rent the space at the price they want. Instead of waiting with an empty space, which can often mean being additionally taxed by the municipality, they can offer a temporary use. This allows various community members to obtain the space for their social, cultural, or other needs, often under more favourable terms. The property owner often has less requirements than in the case of a normal lease: they do not have to maintain the space and can cancel the use at a much shorter notice. On the other hand, temporary users can use the space at no or symbolic cost, and often maintain the spaces themselves. (source: Wikipedia).

/Meanwhile Use

A “meanwhile use” describes a situation where a site is utilised for a duration of time before it is turned into a more permanent end state, taking advantage of a short window of opportunity. Meanwhile interventions are tactical and slot into wider strategies of planned change. They can help in shaping positive urban transformation. We evidence the transitional nature of meanwhile uses within urban development, where its primary purpose is to deliver benefits to the community through predominantly social outcomes as well as

economic and environmental. It is not exclusive to its users but inclusive of social need; it delivers social value, informs longer-term development and drives a new vision of city making (ARUP, 2020). Not all temporary uses are meanwhile: meanwhile uses take advantage of a window of opportunity on a site, before and after another use. And not all meanwhile uses are short term. Some meanwhile uses are offered long leases, for instance in regeneration projects spanning decades. (Source: Centre for London, 2018).

/Mission-oriented Innovation

Mission-oriented innovation is the new paradigm informing the way in which research and innovation shall drive Europe towards climate-neutral, just and thriving societies and economies. In the words of the European Commission, ‘EU Missions are a new way to bring concrete solutions to some of our greatest challenges. They will deliver impact by putting research and innovation into a new role, combined with new forms of governance and collaboration, as well as by engaging citizens. EU Missions [...] aim to mobilise public and private actors, such as EU Member States, regional and local authorities, research institutes, farmers and land managers, entrepreneurs and investors to create real and lasting impact. EU Missions will support Europe’s transformation into a greener, healthier, more inclusive and resilient continent.’ In a nutshell, missions essentially embrace a new way of defining innovation

objectives, making them more concrete, time-bound, achievable and capable of mobilising different actors and assets in a joint and collaborative effort of discovery and learning. In T-Factor, we leverage the ‘meanwhile’ in urban regeneration as a collective, laboratorial space to address place-based missions of innovation that are relevant to broader regeneration challenges and to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). These missions are designed so as to respond to pressing local problems, and to convene local actors in the pursuit of solutions, pooling material and immaterial resources that are distributed in our cities yet often disconnected. Core to this approach is the understanding of temporary uses as the opportunity to define shared goals of urban regeneration, aligning public and private interests around the creation of shared public value.

/Pilots

Urban regeneration initiatives where T-Factor develops strategies of temporary uses in response to local missions of innovation that are relevant to broader regeneration challenges. T-Factor’s pilots are: Aleksotas Kaunas, Amsterdam Science Park, Euston London, MIND Milan, Trafaria Lisbon, Zorrotzaurre Bilbao. See: <https://www.t-factor.eu/pilots/>

/Local Coalitions

In T-Factor, Local Coalitions are place-based alliances involving stakeholders across different

sectors. These alliances collaborate in the 'meanwhile' of urban regeneration in address to shared missions of innovation that are relevant to broader regeneration challenges and opportunities.

/Theory of Change

A Theory of Change (ToC) can be conceived as a tool that serves as the articulation of intended objectives, how you think the objectives will be achieved, and why you believe it to be so (Robert Penna, 2011). The ToC is typically constructed by first identifying the desired long-term goals and then working backward from these to identify all the intermediary effects, or outcomes, that are intended to occur to demonstrate progress. The ToC includes the influence of the context you are working in, as well as the assumptions and evidence you are relying on. A ToC carries several benefits (Brest, 2010; Brown, 2020; Jackson, 2013). First, it can help describe and interpret for all involved stakeholders what you are seeking to achieve and why. In this way, the ToC can serve as a tool to align and manage expectations. Adopting a high-level portfolio view of Theory of Change, it can also inform scoping decisions in terms of themes, instruments, and partnerships. Furthermore, it can identify gaps and issues that require further validation, as you prioritise how you seek additional research and evidence. A ToC should also inform the selection of methods, indicators, and standards that you can use to measure and evaluate success, while aligning short- and long-term measurement efforts.

/Transformation Labs (T-Labs)

Thematic Labs involving different partners in T-Factor, that support the pilots in designing and delivering temporary uses according to their missions. In the project, there are seven T-Labs: 1. Arts, Culture & Creativity; 2. T-Lab2: Urban production & Digitalisation; 3. Citizen-led Smartness; 4. Urban Design for Health and Well-being; 5. Circular & Collaborative Economy; 6. Social Innovation and Social Inclusion; 7. Climate Change and Regenerative Cities. See: <https://www.t-factor.eu/how-we-work/>

/Transformation Agency

A design-driven task force that, within T-Factor, supports the Pilots with tools and methods to design, plan, deliver, monitor and evaluate strategies of missions-oriented temporary uses in urban regeneration.

/Prompt, Regular, Stable Uses

In T-Factor, meanwhile strategies are designed and delivered according to three main types of uses:

- **Prompt uses** - i.e. one off events such as workshops, fairs, seminars, primarily aimed at **attracting people to spaces**;
- **Regular uses** - i.e. more regular activities such as training, incubation and acceleration programmes, volunteering schemes, etc. meant to start **retaining people in places**;
- **Stable uses** - i.e. stable temporary uses such as pop up kitchens, community gardens, artistic residencies, etc., meant to start **anchoring and weaving people in places**).

/Outcome Mapping

Outcome Mapping (OM) is a methodology for planning and assessing projects aiming to bring about sustainable social change. The main idea underpinning OM is that societal structures are created and maintained by people and, thus, long-term changes are essentially changes in relationships, behaviours and actions of people, groups, and organisations that are directly involved in a project (Earl et al., 2001). At the planning stage, outcome mapping helps a project team or program be specific about the actors it intends to target, the changes it hopes to see and the strategies appropriate to achieve these. For ongoing monitoring, OM provides a set of tools to design and gather information on the results of the change process, measured in terms of the changes in behaviour, actions or relationships that can be influenced by the team or program. As an evaluation approach, OM unpacks an initiative's theory of change, provides a framework to collect data on immediate, basic changes that lead to longer, more transformative change, and allows for the plausible assessment of the initiative's contribution to results (Source, Better Evaluation).

| INTRODUCTION

This document describes the mid-term results achieved by the H2020 T-Factor project during the period between February 2022 - October 2022.

Although the project officially started in June 2020, the evaluation time frame considered in this report mainly relates to the later period of concrete implementation of meanwhile strategies by the T-Factor's pilots - **Aleksotas in Kaunas, Amsterdam Science Park, Euston in London, MIND in Milan, Trafaria in Lisbon, Zorrotzaurre in Bilbao.**

Given the *meanwhile methodology* of T-Factor which unveils through four main steps that are largely **practice and action research-led**, it is indeed hard to set a precise moment in time in which all the pilots started to implement such interventions[1]. As of July 2021, after almost one year of research[2], all pilots began their meanwhile journeys on the ground, developing a rich variety of engagement activities meant to explore **challenges and opportunities** attached to the broader

[1] More in detail, the four steps or 'stations' (i.e., 'Exploring & Inquiring', 'Scoping & Ideating', 'Prototyping', 'Iterating') are understood as intermediate milestones that punctuate the main stages of T-Factor's place-making method in the 'meanwhile of urban regeneration'. In brief, the steps are:

- 'Exploring & Inquiring' – i.e., exploring and inquiring into challenges and opportunities for meanwhile interventions attached to broader regeneration projects and plans.
- 'Scoping & Ideating' – i.e., scoping out specific innovation missions that have the potential to transform regeneration projects and processes towards meaningful impact, and ideating portfolios of temporary uses in address to the set missions.
- 'Prototyping & Testing' – i.e., developing and testing temporary uses and activities as planned in the portfolio.
- 'Iterating' – i.e., iterating and evolving temporary uses and activities considering insights and learning harvested over time.

For more information, the reader can explore the T-Factor Toolbox, available at: <https://hub.t-factor.eu/>

[2] In its first year of work, T-Factor delivered two main streams of research. The first stream was dedicated to the so-called 'Advanced Cases' of T-Factor and aimed at harvesting approaches, tools and lessons learnt for temporary use strategies across eight advanced cases of urban regeneration. The results were documented within **D2.1 Advanced Cases Portfolio** delivered in May 2021. The second stream was instead dedicated to the **T-Factor's Pilots**, with the overall purpose of investigating the regeneration projects and plans within which the pilots operate. The results were documented within **D2.2 T-Factor Pilots: Regeneration Projects, Masterplans, Temporary Uses**, delivered in June 2021.

regeneration plans; scope out specific **innovation missions** that could enhance such plans towards meaningful impact; and ideate **portfolios of temporary uses** in address to the set missions. For the sake of simplicity, we consider 'implementation period' (or prototyping and testing) the one commenced at completion of portfolios' design, a milestone achieved for all the pilots by January 2022. At that date, the **Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E) framework and tools** were also completed, thus allowing the pilots to rely on a set of common yet adaptable tools for monitoring and evaluating temporary activities and uses over time[3].

Therefore, most of the insights and learning captured in this report build upon data collection and analysis applied to the activities run during the period considered. However, the evaluation also attempted to consider past activities and preceding periods, particularly by reflecting on the overall journey of the pilots toward the ultimate ambition of T-Factor - i.e., **demonstrating the role and potential of meanwhile uses in influencing broader plans of regeneration and redevelopment towards more inclusive, sustainable, and thriving urban environments.**

The structure and content of the report is organised around the **three main levels** at which T-Factor operates and aims to achieve impact, as explained in the **T-Factor's Theory of Change (ToC)** [4]:

Mission level – the 'micro' level of meanwhile activities. At mission level, impact is considered in regard to **specific temporary uses and activities undertaken**. The context and scale of reference is **local and 'small'**, revolving around the site and its immediately affected stakeholders and communities. The variety of missions addressed via temporary uses are defined within the scope of six impact themes, identified through previous research on temporary uses across Europe, and analysis of the targeted redevelopments at pilot sites: **Improving quality of life; Making places, Attaining sustainability; Growing prosperity; Cultivating innovation; Building communities.**

[3] Deliverable 7.1 T-Factor's Theory of Change and 7.2 Monitoring and Evaluation Framework and Tools were delivered in June 2021 and December 2021 respectively, outlining the impact framework and M&E tools and processes to be applied in the project.

[4] See: <https://www.t-factor.eu/d7-1-theory-of-change/>

Within these six themes, local missions are expressed as evocative statements that give meaning and direction to temporary uses, and are geared towards creating or accelerating positive impact and/or preventing or mitigating negative impact. 'Safe and convivial streets', 'Wild and cultivated spaces', 'Growing and greening' are examples of concrete missions defined across the T-Factor's pilots.

Pilot level - the 'meso' level of the masterplan and regeneration project. A synergistic design and coordination of temporary uses can go beyond results at single use, unlocking spillover benefits throughout the different dimensions and aspects of **urban regeneration plans and processes**. The spatial and timing scope is thus broader, as it considers the regeneration area and the wider urban context while going beyond the (short) timeframe of temporary uses. In particular, the pilot level considers the whole choreography of temporary uses, inquiring into its effects (negative and positive) and contributions to three forms of value creation:

- **Strategic value**, understood as the contribution of temporary uses to higher quality regeneration. Here, we mainly consider aspects such as positioning and reputation of the redevelopment, attractiveness, change in perceptions, enhanced alignment between different agendas, etc.
- **Operational value**, understood as the contribution of temporary uses to a more resilient, multidisciplinary and holistic regeneration process. Here we mainly consider aspects such as decision-making, design and management skills and tools, funding and capital deployment, etc.
- **Relational value**, understood as the contribution of temporary uses to accelerating and adding on positive impact and legacy towards the long run. Here we consider aspects such as trust and relational capital creation, multi-stakeholder collaboration, participation, etc.

Transnational level - the 'macro' level of T-Factor. At transnational level, impact is understood in terms of contribution of the project to sustainable urban development challenges. The scope is no longer expressed spatially, but rather conceived as **best practice** that may

Figure 1: Impact levels of the T-Factor's Theory of Change.

inspire others to take similar action, by means of awareness raising, co-creation and dissemination of new knowledge, practice and policies on temporary uses in urban regeneration. The transnational level is anchored to the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**. Specifically, for T-Factor SDG 11 and 17 are placed central as they embrace the core goals of the project, that are to contribute to sustainable cities and communities, and to strengthen international partnerships for this purpose.

According to the three levels mentioned above, the report is organised as follows:

- Section '**Methodology**' provides an overview of the main methods and tools for monitoring & evaluation (M&E) applied across the three levels, as well as an explanation of how the evaluation process has been organised and managed.
- Part 1 '**T-Factor's Pilots**' captures evaluation results for each pilot. More in detail, each pilot chapter: i) provides a brief introduction to the context addressed by regeneration interventions as well as an overview of the regeneration project; ii) describes the overarching challenge and specific missions addressed through meanwhile interventions in T-Factor, including an overview of the portfolio of temporary uses and activities; iii) describes the activities delivered in the period of reference and the main results and outcomes achieved at mission level; iv) reflects on the overall meanwhile journey of the pilot so far through the lens of strengths and weaknesses (pilot level).
- Part 2 '**Transnational level**' describes broader project's activities and results relevant to the creation and dissemination of knowledge, practice and policies on temporary uses that can help sustain the spread of these practices across urban redevelopments in Europe, so as to contribute to address and prioritise broad challenges of sustainable urban development.
- Lastly, section '**Conclusions**' summarises the main findings and learning from the mid-term evaluation, including a reflection on challenges and issues encountered over time in terms of impact measurement, as well as key takeaways for the next evaluation period.

METHODOLOGY

According to the general structure of the T-Factor's Theory Change briefly outlined in the Introduction, this section briefly explains the monitoring and evaluation methodology applied during the period of reference across the 'mission', 'pilot', and 'transnational' levels.

At **missions level**, results and contribution to impact were assessed for **each implemented activity** against a number of pre-identified targets, the latter defined through **outcome mapping methodologies** [5] applied during the scoping and ideation phase developed by each pilot, as part of the broader process of definition and design of meanwhile strategies.

At the **pilot level**, results and contribution to impact were assessed considering the **overall, combined effects of the pilot's activities** against three key dimensions - strategic, operational, relational - describing the improvements of the pilots during the observed period.

At the **transnational level**, results and contribution to impact were assessed by understanding the project's contribution to the creation of awareness, new and better knowledge, practices and policies on temporary uses that can help spread them across European cities, leveraging international collaboration, collaborative research and innovation, and co-creation to this end.

For each level, output and outcome indicators/proxies are used to describe, assess, and monitor the desired change.

[5] Outcome Mapping (OM) is a methodology for planning and assessing projects aiming to bring about sustainable social change. The main idea underpinning OM is that societal structures are created and maintained by people and, thus, long-term changes are essentially changes in relationships, behaviours and actions of people, groups, and organisations that are directly involved in a project (Earl et al., 2001). At the planning stage, outcome mapping helps a project team or program be specific about the actors it intends to target, the changes it hopes to see and the strategies appropriate to achieve these. For ongoing monitoring, OM provides a set of tools to design and gather information on the results of the change process, measured in terms of the changes in behaviour, actions or relationships that can be influenced by the team or program. As an evaluation approach, OM unpacks an initiative's theory of change, provides a framework to collect data on immediate, basic changes that lead to longer, more transformative change, and allows for the plausible assessment of the initiative's contribution to results (Source, Better Evaluation).

Mission level

The methodology at mission level followed the same process for each activity organised over time. Before the activity was executed, a comprehensive activity planning was required to define the monitor and evaluation (M&E) characteristics of the activity. Therefore, as a first step, an in-depth conversation between the M&E reference person (i.e. person within the Local Coalition appointed for the M&E activities) and I-Propeller was organised. During this conversation, activity type, content, objective, scope and beneficiaries were disclosed by the M&E local reference person. After that, I-Propeller and the M&E reference person selected the most relevant output and outcome proxies from the overall pilot's framework [6], depending on the specific characteristics and objective of the meanwhile activity considered.

Figure 2: M&E process applied for each activity (mission level)

In a second step, I-Propeller made a proposal for the most appropriate tools for data harvesting and collection, based on a general list of tools and methods previously defined within Deliverable 7.2. M&E Framework and Tools. Lastly, based on the agreements made during the initial conversation, I-Propeller developed, adjusted and validated the necessary M&E tool(s) for the activity.

[6] Deliverable 7.2 Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E) Framework and Tools contains a detailed description of each pilot's evaluation framework, including outputs and outcomes proxies and indicators.

At completion of the activity, data was gathered and analysed to assess its performance and results:

- Typically, when the Local Coalition opted for a **survey tool**, both qualitative and quantitative data could be generally gathered as the survey had multiple choice questions and open questions. Multiple-choice questions often entailed the use of scales to assess the extent to which an activity contributed to the outcome proxy; i.e., respondents could indicate if and to what extent the activity had contributed to a certain outcome proxy, ranging from no contribution to high/significant contribution. Based on the answers, a weighted average score was calculated, as shown in **Figure 3**. Furthermore, for the open questions, the respondents had the chance to qualitatively describe what were the key contributors and bottlenecks of the activity vis-à-vis the outcome proxy(ies) considered.
- When the Local Coalition opted for an **interview or observation**, the focus was more on qualitative information harvested through a semi-structured template. For an observation template, the observer described the environment and local context, taking into account the relevant and applicable outcome proxies. For the interview template, general semi-structured interview questions were provided to give an indication of the targeted outcome proxies. However, the interviewer had the flexibility to ask additional questions from time to time.

Figure 3: illustrative example multiple choice question – weighted average score of respondents

Pilot level

For the assessment of the pilots along the three improvement dimensions (Strategic, Operational, Relational), a **Critical Friend interview** [7] (Annex 1) was carried out by the Agency with the Local Coalition (LC). The aim of the interview was to gather qualitative insights on the implemented activities and overall functioning of the pilot, and their combined impact on the three above mentioned dimensions. As part of the interview, a **strategy self-assessment scoreboard** (Annex 2) was also used where the Local Coalitions rated their perceived progress on the set dimensions. An additional **self-reporting template** was used to allow the T-Labs and Agency to report on their specific pilots' support activities delivered over time, in order to understand and assess their contribution to the impact dimensions observed at the pilot level.

[7] A transversal interview tool used by the Agency to operate as a critical friend throughout the pilot execution and hence is referred to as Critical Friend Interview. The interview draws upon the data harvested throughout the monitoring process at mission level, to provide additional informed and qualitative insights about the pilot's progress towards the envisaged KTIs. Refer to Annex 3.

Lastly, at pilot level, **qualitative synthesis** was carried out for the data collected through the Critical Friend interview and the self reporting template. The Local Coalition's rankings on the strategy self-assessment scoreboard further contributed to understanding the overall impact contribution towards the set indicators.

Figure 4: Example of questions related to the operational dimension of the CF Interview

OPERATIONAL (the contribution of the Portfolio to the effectiveness, efficiency and quality of the regeneration process)	
PLANNING & DELIVERY CAPACITIES	<p>Do you have the right resources (financial, human, technical) to run the mission smoothly?</p> <p>Are there activities generating or attracting additional resources? Which ones? How? Is there a pooling of immaterial and material resources activated by the portfolio? Is the pilot working appropriately to gather resources also for future sustainability?</p> <p>Which combination of innovative skills & knowledge is harnessed at the moment in the meanwhile portfolio? Which other expertise and inputs might be needed to increase future impact?</p> <p>Has the portfolio experimented with new ways of planning, designing and delivering urban regeneration? Has it contributed to a new urban regeneration culture amongst developers and key regeneration stakeholders?</p>
RESILIENCE, FLEXIBILITY & ADAPTABILITY	<p>Has the portfolio allowed you to take more informed and evidence-based decisions? Has it transformed masterplans' assumptions over time in response to emerging needs and opportunities?</p> <p>Has the portfolio improved risk and conflict management and mitigation? How?</p>
INTEROPERABILITY & CONNECTIVITY	<p>Is the activity aligned and coherent with the other initiatives in the area? Do you feel that the mission is in synergy with wider city plans and initiatives?</p> <p>Are there newly identified or developed policies, programmes, schemes, initiatives or financial incentives contributing to the meanwhile strategy or that the strategy can contribute to? How? To which field these policies target to and for whom, for example: creative and cultural industries and favours access to spaces by young creatives, students or start-uppers?</p> <p>What might be needed to increase the synergy and dialogue between these initiatives?</p> <p>What might be needed to improve the synergy between temporary uses?</p>

Transnational level

For assessing the transnational level of the project, the following tools were applied for data collection:

- **Online surveys** were designed and applied to knowledge co-creation and capacity building activities (mainly, workshops and training activities) of T-Factor.
- An **interview** was carried out with **CENTRINNO's** Project Coordinator to dig deeper into the ongoing collaborations across the sister projects [9].
- A **Focus Group** was carried out with all the members of the Transformation Labs to understand the contribution of the project to novel placemaking practices and policies in urban regeneration.

At transnational level, quantitative and qualitative approaches were used for the analysis of the data collected through the tools applied. The emerging results are presented across two areas: (1) Contribution to practices of meanwhile uses; (2) Contribution to 'politics' of urban regeneration and 'policies' for meanwhile uses.

As introduced earlier, a full and in-depth description of the M&E framework and methodology is provided within **Deliverable 7.2 'Monitoring and Evaluation Framework and Tools'**.

Level	What is assessed?	Tools Applied	How is it assessed?
Mission	Impact of each activity on the identified targets of the site	Online Surveys, interviews and observations	Single activity-based evaluation
Pilot	Overall strategic, operational, and relational improvements of the site	- Critical Friend Interview - Self reporting templates for T Labs and Agency	Overall assessment of combined effects of all activities of the site
Transnational	Project's contribution in co-creating new knowledge at policy level and in raising awareness on meanwhile approach	-Online Surveys -Interview with sister project -Focus Group Discussion	Overall assessment of the transversal activities and efforts of the project

Table 1: M&E Framework

[9] For more information about the collaboration activities developed by the sister projects (T-Factor, CENTRINNO, Hub-IN), the reader can refer to: <https://www.t-factor.eu/towards-innovative-inclusive-and-creative-hubs-in-european-cities/>

| PART 1

CONTRIBUTION TO IMPACT AT **MISSION AND PILOT LEVELS**

Pilots chapters

ALEKSOTAS KAUNAS

Photo credits: Marta Arniani

ALEKSOTAS, KAUNAS

| About Aleksotas and the development of the AIIP (Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park)

The Aleksotas district is located in the Southern part of Kaunas, on the upper terrace of the Nemunas river. The area used to be quite separated from the rest of the city, and is mainly characterised by mono-functional buildings, mostly residential. The situation changed in 2002, when the second bridge (M.K.Ciurlionis bridge) crossing the Nemunas River was completed. This new connection brought Aleksotas closer to the city. Since 2015 the city of Kaunas has been investing efforts and resources in order to upgrade the site and prepare it for renewal and regeneration. As a result, Aleksotas is increasingly attracting interest and attention for urban redevelopment and transformation. Many new housing projects are taking place along the river Nemunas in Freda district as well as in the outskirts of Aleksotas district.

In order to attract investments, Kaunas needs to create appealing conditions. The establishment of the **Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park (AIIP)** is an important project for the whole of Lithuania, as it can contribute to the implementation of national strategic goals and objectives. The AIIP location is known as a former testing site for helicopters. Moreover, its surroundings preserve the history of **Kaunas Fortress**, a fortress complex built between 1882 and 1915 to protect the Russian Empire's western borders. Later, during the period of the First Republic of Lithuania, the military warehouses became garages, where tanks were parked. Nowadays, the main warehouse has been transformed into a space to host events and workshops, as well as the headquarters offices of the Kaunas Fortress Park.

The AIIP is an urban regeneration project in Kaunas aimed to become a recreational area both for AIIP workers and inhabitants of the city. The main objective of the AIIP is to convert the military base into an **industrial innovation area for low carbon companies focusing on bio-med, bio-pharma and bio-food**. Through the AIIP, Lithuania and Kaunas want to reinforce the relationship between local businesses and research institutions which will contribute to economic and social value and improve national competitiveness.

| Overarching Challenge and Innovation Missions in T-Factor

The overall challenge of the AIIP is to develop the AIIP as a 'new bit' of Kaunas. At present, the site has shortages in basic services and facilities and after years of abandonment, a new identity for the area needs to be developed. The AIIP aspires to establish a dynamic and creative ecosystem for new businesses and research in highly specialised fields (bio-med, bio-pharma and bio-food). The engagement of the local communities is a crucial component of the AIIP project, which might create new spaces for dialogue and collaboration between the professional community that will inhabit the area and local communities nearby. In this regard, the implementation of temporary uses aims to serve as a "demonstrator" that may potentially be expanded across other regeneration projects in Kaunas and beyond.

At the moment, the identity of the area is mainly centred around military and aircraft purposes. Therefore, as part of the regeneration project, the site will need to get a new identity. There are existing communities such as arts and cultural groups nearby the site, that could be engaged in developing its cultural heritage. This is an opportunity to engage with local communities and exchange visions on the site for both the short and long term. Furthermore, the current legal system does not envisage temporary uses, and this is quite a new practice in the city and across the whole of Lithuania.

There is currently a lack of diversity in functions and initiatives in the park. Cultural offers and basic public services are not broadly available as most of the area is used for industrial and residential purposes. However, there is rich cultural heritage in and around the site, for example the Kaunas Fortress complex.

Regarding the development of the AIIP, there is a risk for it to become a free economic zone focusing primarily on production rather than on R&D. The aim of the AIIP is to become a frontrunner in Lithuania for innovation, research and development. In this respect, there might be the possibility to develop the area as a temporary experimental zone, a sandbox for R&D.

Within this context, the pilot focuses on the following three missions:

Mission 1: Collaborative, Creative & Community-led Meanwhile: The main focus of this mission is to create collaborative and creative communities around the AIIP, who can co-develop a variety of meanwhile uses, giving the chance to local stakeholders to create a community of practice on innovative city making methods.

Mission 2: People and Planet-centred Innovation Ecosystem: With an emphasis on technology, health, and sustainability, this mission strives to create a favourable environment for the growth of a vibrant network of research communities, start-ups, and businesses in industries including biotech, biofood, and medtech. The area can become perceived as a place where cultural, business and tech-related actors start engaging with each other, disseminating, and promoting knowledge exchange on life sciences and green tech.

Mission 3: Short Distance and Multi-Function Place: This mission intends to foster the development of new services and amenities on the site that can enhance the liveability while beginning to change perceptions of isolation and remoteness. The aim of this mission is to set the basis to increase, on a longer run, the liveability and attractiveness of the area.

Photo credits: Marta Arniani

ALEKSOTAS KAUNAS THEORY OF CHANGE

How can we develop the Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park as a 'new bit' of Kaunas?

- #PROMPT USES:** one off events that attract people in places
- #REGULAR USES:** regular activities that retain people in places
- #STABLE USES:** temporary uses that anchor people to places
- #COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE**
- #INVESTMENT & FUNDING**
- #SMART PLANNING, POLICY & REGULATION**

Missions (if we)

Mission 1: Collaborative, Creative & Community-led meanwhile

Mission 2: People & Planet-centered innovation ecosystems

Mission 3: Short- distance Multi- function place

By (Portfolio of temporary activities)

Figure 5: Theory of Change of the Aleksotas Pilot

| Meanwhile Portfolio

The activity portfolio is designed to tackle the overall objective of Kaunas, making Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park as a new 'bit' of the city. The starting point is to involve the local communities and other stakeholders through a set of cultural events organised by the local coalition, composed by Kaunas Technical University (KTU), Kaunas Municipality, and Kaunas Fortress Park. These events aim at creating awareness and steering co-creative visioning processes for the future of the AIIP.

To support the thematic R&D positioning of AIIP, the portfolio also include a cluster of activities that focus on the **development of the area as a regulatory sandbox**, understood as a testbed for innovative technologies and R&D solutions. Furthermore, the portfolio foresees the development of **digital placemaking tools**, including through the development of the **Space Syntax**, a model that contains a set of methods for analysing spatial layouts and human activity patterns in urban sites.

The stable use **Kaunas Fortress Community Space** is planned to be the focal location for the local community to participate in prompt and regular activities, since it perfectly fits as a space to organise and prototype meanwhile uses on site. Furthermore, **an urban garden and several prompt initiatives** are considered with the aim to test new facilities and services on the site. Regular uses like educational and capacity building activities on topics such as biodiversity and circular design are contributing to mission 2 'People and Planet-centred Innovation Ecosystem'. The activities are contributing to the mission by attracting visitors to the site and presenting innovative and inspiring ideas on the future uses of the area.

Lastly, as the current regulatory framework slows down possibilities for temporary uses, a dialogue with the government strategic analysis centre has been started, with the aim of developing a policy lab. This policy lab will try to improve policies for temporary urbanism in the country, which in turn could enable conditions for the delivery of the sandbox areas, another stable use, to boost R&D, innovation, community-led and multi-stakeholder engagement.

Figure 6: Meanwhile Portfolio of the Aleksotas Pilot
(Double clic on the text to access the digital version of the Portfolio on Miro)

| Portfolio delivery: overview

In the time frame considered for the mid-term evaluation^[10], the Aleksotas pilot has designed and organised four different activities of the portfolio, namely (1) **Public Participation and Engagement in Multi-Stakeholder Collaborations**, (2) **International Congress "CoHappiness. Rewilding & Rethinking"**, (3) **Architectural-urban en plein-air "Innovative Fortification workshop - the Conversion of Kaunas Fortress buildings and territory in Aleksotas,"** that are related to Mission 1 'Collaborative, Creative & Community-led Meanwhile', and (4) **'LT 5G SANDBOX Info Day & ideas pitch and business contacts fair'**, related to Mission 2 'People and Planet-centred Innovation Ecosystem'.

'**Public Participation and Engagement in Multi-Stakeholder Collaborations**' included several meetings and discussions in the period October 2021 - July 2022 to assess the possibilities of participation during the development of the AIIP. As a result of the activity, the report 'Public participation and engagement in multi-stakeholder collaborations' was conducted by the Aleksotas pilot within T-Lab 6 - Social Innovation and Social Inclusion collaboration, together with partners from the City of Lodz, University of Lodz, and the University of Dortmund. The report investigates needs, challenges and opportunities for the AIIP, introducing new insights and recommendations to increase its feasibility through a participatory lens.

The International Congress '**CoHappiness. Rewilding & Rethinking**' in June 2022 was an activity part of an international congress called 'CoHappiness', organised by Vytautas Magnus University and Kaunas 2022. The congress combined science, culture and art in order to explore the topic of 'happiness'. The activity hosted presentations, discussions, and workshops. The congress lasted three days, however only the last day was related to T-Factor activities. The activities organised by T-Factor have been:

- Children painting workshop & live graffiti drawing "No-Fly Zone": the activity was a painting workshop, inviting **Ukrainian kids** to make drawings together with artists. A selected number of paintings were placed on the Open Gallery Wall, which is one of the permanent meanwhile uses of the activity portfolio.
- Lectures & round table discussions: the activity took place in the Kaunas fortress. First, there was an online presentation called "The Science of Happiness" by professor Ruut Veenhoven, a sociologist and psychologist, researcher and founder of the World Database of Happiness (World Happiness Report). The presentation was followed by the talk: "*Otherness: a precondition for happiness or an obstacle to it?*" which aimed at attracting citizens and promoting the AIIP as well as temporary uses.

[10] Generally, the period considered in this report is February 2022 - October 2022, which is the overall time frame in which the T-Factor Pilots started to implement and run their temporary use strategies. However, it should be noted that the insights and results (especially more qualitative results) captured in this report also refer to the preceding period (the whole 2021), particularly when it comes to preliminary activities of engagement, initial scoping and co-design that started to set the ground for implementing and iterating temporary uses and activities.

The **Architectural-urban plein-air 'Innovative Fortification - the Conversion of Kaunas Fortress buildings and territory in Aleksotas'** workshop invited professionals from various fields, such as architects, urban planners, specialised companies and project participants to create an interdisciplinary dialogue on the existing practices of urban regeneration and proposed new solutions for sustainable and innovative practices to be applied in regeneration projects related to the Kaunas Fortresses system. The main topic was how to activate Kaunas Fortress and premises located in Lakunu. The activity aimed to explore and find ways to implement uses or spaces that can have a positive contribution on the site. This cycle of workshops lasted for three months, started in June 2022 and has been divided into several iterations. The activity entailed lectures, excursions and presentations. The final result of the activity will be a proposal of a strategy and the development of design solutions to be experimented on the short and long term, that would activate the surroundings of Kaunas Fortress headquarters, which is located on the North side of the AIIP.

The **'Co-happiness' event and 'Architectural-urban workshop'** contributed to the 'Open Gallery' activity and the 'Kaunas Fortress Community Space' activities that are both stable uses in the activity portfolio, more specifically:

- Assets of the 'Kaunas Fortress Community Space' were used to host the events. The aim of the events was to present research and new findings on the history of the Kaunas Fortress and how it influenced urban planning and social life in Lithuania, revealing perspectives on the transformation and functions of former military cultural heritage buildings in contemporary Kaunas. During the workshop, ideas and uses that could improve the area of Kaunas Fortress territory were discussed and investigated. The Fortress community space also hosted the presentations and discussions at the 'Co-happiness' event.
- The 'Open Gallery' consists of a number of paintings that decorate the wall surrounding the AIIP territory, which has a symbolic meaning for the area. The wall represents the transition between the old and new identity of the territory, because since the start of the regeneration project, the wall got partly demolished. The abandoned and forgotten wall has been transformed and raised to a new life, becoming a place

recognizable as a cultural manifesto for the city, providing new opportunities for community participation, arts and culture. During the painting workshop at the 'Co-happiness' congress, some selected paintings and other art objects were used to decorate the wall of the Open Gallery permanent space.

Photo credits: Marta Arniani

The **'Sandbox Info Day & ideas pitch and business contacts fair'** was organised by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Communication of the Republic of Lithuania in June 2022. The T-Factor team could pitch their idea to make the AIIP area a Sandbox area, which is foreseen to become a permanent activity. The Local Coalition presented the project, and it was a good opportunity to get the attention of the Ministry.

Currently the T-Factor team agreed that they will combine the initiative of the sandbox with the next initiatives the government might promote and organise in AIIP. The event was aimed at presenting “New Generation Lithuania”, the national Recovery and Resilience Plan, which will invest around 700 million euros to foster the digital transition. The plan includes the facilitation of 5G roll-out and the promotion of mobility innovations, among other measures. One of the actions is the 5G Sandbox initiative planned by the Ministry of Transport and Communications - a legal, regulatory and financial environment for testing and putting into practice under real conditions the 5G connection-based innovations in mobility and other sectors. A financial support mechanism is being developed and 24.5 million euros have been allocated for this initiative.

Besides the activities mentioned in the paragraphs above, the Aleksotas pilot focused on several preparatory and planning actions related to digital placemaking. The T-Cycle on digital placemaking ‘**Inclusive Urban Metaverse**’ looked into how digital territories can support placemaking that takes place at a site characterised by a digitally savvy population and a reduced possibility for manoeuvre inside the area. The actions, designed by KTU and Futuribile (the latter within T-Lab 3 ‘Citizen-led Smartness’) explore the challenge of how the digital territory could not only be a digital twin for top-down modelling but also be a space for community building.

It tackles the topic of ‘what activities that are hard to perform in real life could take place in the digital territory more easily’ and ‘how could it augment existing practices and feed back into the built city and body and flesh communities’. As cities worldwide prepare for the next step of the ‘smart city’ and look into Extended Reality (XR) as a means to provide services to citizens and optimise the city, the question of planning immersive territories will be increasingly present in the agenda of city makers. The T-Cycle is built around the question of how to design inclusive urban metaverse, starting a conversation about social justice and participatory design in envisioning the extended city. A Manifesto was launched in September 2022 to articulate the need for a social justice approach to digital territories, and stating some guiding values. The manifesto is a curatorial statement that will be declined in different upcoming activities. Firstly, an online interdisciplinary meeting with international experts to determine the social values and the functionalities that could take place in an urban metaverse. The discussion is aimed to identify inclusive design principles for digital territories. Secondly, a public talk taking place in the city of Kaunas to describe the cycle and gather participants for the final activity, which is a workshop dedicated to co-design a digital district with citizens. The latter will provide the first ever use case of a digital district imagined by citizens and answering their needs.

| Stakeholders and beneficiaries

Several stakeholders and partners with the right expertise and resources needed to be engaged to make the different activities happen. The Local Coalition, formed by Kaunas Fortress Park, Kaunas Municipality and Kaunas Technology University (KTU), co-organised multiple activities. For instance, the 'Architectural-urban' workshop was co-executed by Kaunas Fortress and KTU, and the report of 'Public Participation and Engagement in Multi-Stakeholder Collaborations' was discussed and reviewed by these entities several times. The other entities that the Aleksotas pilot consists of are the Vytautas Magnus University and Kaunas European Capital of Culture 2022, especially for the 'Co-Happiness Congress'. For the painting workshop, several artists and cultural organisations, providing their professional expertise, were involved together with children. The persons involved for the lecture and discussion at the same congress were sociologists, psychologists, philosophers, photographers and journalists. Lastly, for the 5G sandbox event, policy makers were involved as the event was organised by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Communication of the Republic of Lithuania.

Through their activities, the Aleksotas pilot managed to engage many different beneficiaries. The exact numbers of the beneficiaries are hard to define for the activity 'Public Participation and Engagement in Multi-Stakeholder Collaborations' since the end-result of the activity will be a report which has not been published yet. However, local residents, and other individuals could benefit from the different participation possibilities in the regeneration of the Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park. Regarding the painting workshop at the 'Co-happiness' congress, the involvement of children was a great contributor to the success of the activity. Regarding the lecture and discussion at the same event, there were a total of 22 listeners registered online and on site. Lastly, since the main objective of the architectural-urban workshop was to evaluate and propose new solutions and ideas for further regeneration projects of Kaunas Fortress, the activity was mainly targeting **architects, urbanists & landscape designers**. Indirectly, the Kaunas Fortress system can be seen as a beneficiary as well. Lastly, the participants of the 5G sandbox event were mainly businesses and policymakers.

Activity 1: Public Participation and Engagement in Multi-Stakeholder Collaborations

Target groups: Local community, local residents, and other groups involved in the redevelopment.

Collaborators: Kaunas Fortress, KTU, and T-Lab 6

Keywords:
#Local enterprises
#Learning, Skilling, Making

Prompt use
October 2021 - July 2022

Main beneficiaries:

- 16** No exact figures available, but local community, local residents and other groups affected in the redevelopment.
- 10** different sessions: Reviewing the report required several meetings & discussions between the T-Lab 6, Kaunas City and KTU.

Activity 2: International Congress "CoHappiness. Rewilding & Rethinking"

Target groups: Academic community, K22, local community, artists & creatives and the Ukrainian community (artists & children). Anyone interested in the topic locally and internationally.

Collaborators: Vytautas Magnus University and Kaunas European Capital of Culture 2022

Keywords:
#Creativity & talent
#Learning, Skilling, Making

Prompt use
1/06/2022 - 3/06/2022

Painting workshop:
Main beneficiaries:

- 30** children and teenagers directly involved and 20 beneficiaries indirectly involved, mainly parents, grandparents and relatives.
- 30** products delivered: Graffiti on the walls and paintings on paper.

Painting workshop:
Main beneficiaries:

- 22** online viewers of the lecture and congress, in which 15 of the community and 7 from academia.

Activity 3: Architectural-urban workshop

Target groups: Multidisciplinary professionals, especially architects, urbanists, landscape architects, historic and environmentalists.

Collaborators: Kaunas Fortress and KTU

Keywords:
#Creativity & talent
#Learning, Skilling, Making

Prompt use
October 2021 - July 2022

Main beneficiaries:

- 16** professionals such as architects, urbanists & landscape architects and 7 related to academia - 1 professor teaching at an architecture school and his students were involved.
- 4** tangible products: (1) Presentations, description & visuals material of the results, (2) Booklet of all the design proposals, (3) Photos, and (4) Press release.

- 10** different sessions: 6 lectures, 2 excursions and 2 workshops about restoration.

Activity 1: : LT 5G SANDBOX Info Day & ideas pitch and business contacts fair

Target groups: Government, Businesses and Start-ups.

Collaborators: Ministry of Infrastructure and Communication of the Republic of Lithuania

Keywords:
#Local enterprises
#Learning, skilling, making

Prompt use
15/06/2022

Main beneficiaries:

- 1** session: presentation /pitch of the Aleksotas pilot.

- 72** participants
- 38** companies
- 19** entities related to the government
- 11** from Academia
- 4** from the consultancy sector

| Contribution to impact at mission level - Main activities' results

In the paragraphs that follow, an overview of the main results achieved through the activities described earlier is provided. Results are mainly extracted from online surveys addressed to the beneficiaries involved as well as from the self-reporting templates compiled by the local coalition coordinator.

Knowledge on how temporary uses could enhance the creativity & talent of people

Overall, the 'Co-happiness congress' lecture and discussion, and the 'Architectural-urban workshop' were good examples of how temporary uses can add value to people and places, stimulating participation and collective visioning. Taking into account the results of the survey, the participants stated that the topics were interesting and helped generate new thoughts and ideas, while encouraging participants to think further on the topics discussed. For the 'Architectural-urban' workshop, the respondents gave a weighted score of 3,8 out of 5 on this same dimension. Temporary practices in Lithuania are generally under-explored, thus organising a programme of temporary uses related to AIP can be considered as a stimulating factor to creativity, as acknowledged by many of the participants.

Figure 7: outcome proxy for the lecture and discussions at Co-Happiness Festival

Overall, the two activities were good ways to show the added value of temporary uses to stimulate creativity. However, the sense of effective increased creativity was relatively small, with respective weighted scores of 2,8 and 3,4 out of 5. On the one hand, as already indicated, the lecture of the 'Co-happiness' event created new thoughts but there was not a moment foreseen to discuss and go deeper on the theme. At the 'Architectural-urban workshop' some of the respondents stated that the activity created an occasion to apply their creativity, but didn't really provide new creative skills.

The painting workshop at the 'Co-happiness congress' had a positive influence on the creativity of the participants. The children, under supervision of artists, painted with brushes, pencils and with their own hands. The educators helped the children when they raised questions or wanted to explore some new ideas, which strengthened the development of children's creativity and freedom of expression. Some of the children's paintings ended up as graffiti on a concrete wall of AIP.

As already indicated, the painting workshop is also connected to the 'Open Gallery', which in turn contributes to mission 3 'Short Distance and Multi-Function Place'. The paintings and graffiti drawn on the wall of AIP boosted the liveability and attractiveness of the place, and generated a greater sense of belonging to the place for the families who participated in the activity. The main struggle for the territory is that it has been uncanny for a long period, with a shared perception of the area as being disconnected from the city. The graffiti action surely contributed to make the area more attractive to citizens, who may be willing to visit it and, by doing so, rediscover the area.

Skills and capacities in collaborative and participatory placemaking

In general, the feedback of the surveys of the 'Co-happiness congress: lecture and discussion' and the 'Architectural-urban' workshop is twofold, indicating both positive and negative feedback:

- The lecture and discussion: on the one hand, feedback from the event was 'it was nice to see, and be in the place', but it did not influence participants' skills in collaborative and participatory placemaking. However, even if the lecture and following discussion have been perceived as an interesting sharing and learning moment, the follow-up of the activity was perceived as being unclear, since most of the respondents indicated that they don't know how to apply or implement these skills in the future.
- Architectural-urban workshop: the invited persons were mainly professional architects and urbanists. Therefore, with the discussions, no specific improvement of their professional skills have been measured, indicating that participants already had a consolidated background on the theme of urban regeneration applied to heritage buildings. . Nonetheless, the activity was an occasion for participants to increase their knowledge on the site and the context of the Kaunas Fortress Park. The workshop enabled collaborative and constructive discussions - as stated by one participant, 'the environment has been very collaborative, and the proposals generated were analysed collectively and objectively'.

Collaboration among cultural organisations

Early results collected on the outcome related to the increased collaboration between cultural organisations in the area tends to indicate the International Congress 'CoHappiness. Rewilding & Rethinking' contributed to enhancing collaboration between the participants. Cultural organisations and citizens expressed a shared willingness to engage in similar activities related to AIIP in the future. The event seems to have encouraged personal development, and stimulated the interest of participants. However, it is too soon to assess whether and to what extent this result will influence future collaborations on the site. The results of the 'Architectural-urban' workshop were more divided, indicating some cultural organisations and citizens positively engaged by the activities and open to collaborate, but others not interested enough to collaborate in upcoming events. Respondents of the survey indicated that the activity has not been able to involve many local people and that the contact with the citizens and local residents have not yet been sought. Only certain groups in the neighbouring areas were engaged, but the reach of the workshop could have been wider.

Figure 8: outcome proxy for the lecture and discussions at Co-Happiness congress and for the Architectural-urban workshop

| Contribution to impact at Pilot level

The section describes the pilot level changes and considerations gathered through the 'Critical Friend' interview. As anticipated, the interview is aimed at exploring if and how the activities undertaken during the period of reference are contributing towards long term outcomes and impacts of urban regeneration, particularly from the point of view of enhanced strategic, operational and relational dimensions (ref. Methodology section). In the following paragraph we report on the main strengths and weaknesses that emerged through the interview. A self-assessment scoreboard filled out by the Local Coalition is provided at the end of the section. It is important to highlight that the insights and reflections reported in this chapter do not only capture the voice and perceptions of the Local Coalition; they also include and integrate the results of the ongoing observation and support developed by the Transformation Agency over time, in its role of 'critical friend' of the pilot.

Aleksotas Innovation Industry Park (AIIP) is a project of national importance seeking to attract investment for social and economic value creation in Kaunas and for the whole of Lithuania, enhancing the competitiveness of the country in forefront business and R&I domains such as bio-pharma, bio-food and biodiversity, with a strong emphasis on sustainability.

Meanwhile uses are quite new to Kaunas and the broader country, and participatory processes in urban regeneration do not have a strong tradition. Although by law any new development project must be presented publicly, the active involvement of the local communities is rare and mostly takes shape as a way to inform citizens. Thus, the challenges of this pilot are particularly complex and specific, as they touch upon **the fundamental need of advancing participatory cultures and**

mindsets in urban planning and development, in a general context where these are weak not only at institutional level but also within the general participation culture of the city.

The pilot thus has a twofold objective: on the one hand, it aims at creating conditions through which **meanwhile uses can start to be known and position themselves as a viable approach to urban regeneration**; on the other hand, it aims at demonstrating **the potential of meanwhile use to anticipate the creation of vibrant and collaborative communities that may later find a permanent home at the AIIP**, involving the local communities, businesses, social and cultural organisations in co-creative placemaking during the redevelopment period. The meanwhile strategy shall also contribute to raise interest and awareness on the future Park, not least by helping create better conditions for attracting investment.

The development of the AIIP is expected to last until 2046, and is thus **among the longest urban regeneration projects addressed by T-Factor**. Only recently has the Municipality of Kaunas finalised the development guidelines for the future operator of the Park, and investors and developers are yet to be identified although conversations are in place at the time of writing this report. This creates **general uncertainty around the next steps and milestones for the redevelopment, and by extension affects possibilities for meanwhile uses on site**. In addition, **widespread perceptions and feelings of the area as disconnected from the city and poorly attractive as a destination** add complexity to the challenge of activating and implementing meanwhile uses.

From the outset of the engagement process, the Local Coalition worked in order to create information, awareness and momentum around the site through temporary uses, engaging with and attracting a number of actors and stakeholders such as decision makers, academic staff, representatives of social and cultural organisations, university students, and more. Given the underlying challenges, the engagement efforts and the activities implemented so far have seen **some relative success in improving the positioning and reputation of the area**. T-Factor activities proved to be meaningful especially in terms of bringing citizens and in

general first-time visitors on site, while providing especially scientific and creative communities with opportunities to meet each other through the exploration of possibilities and visions for the future AIP. The activities also helped shed light on the history and social and cultural significance that permeate the area, particularly around the **Kaunas Fortress complex**.

Importantly, over the period, the pilot has managed to **strengthen the dialogue with policy-makers at local and national levels**, an effort initiated in the very early stage of T-Factor to create proper conditions for meanwhile uses. This allowed the Local Coalition to identify early opportunities for aligning the meanwhile strategy with local and nationally-relevant initiatives. In particular, early conversations activated with the **Ministry of Communication and Transport on 5G technology** brought the Local Coalition to start exploring meanwhile uses as possibilities for a **R&I sandbox model**, understood as an innovation zone where different technologies and prototypes can be designed and tested under more favourable conditions. 'Technologies' in this context are not limited to tech innovation only, but most importantly include the prototyping of solutions for social innovation powered by the ultimate technology. The **strategic alignment with a wider governmental initiative** has opened up further possibilities for the pilot to engage in an effective dialogue with stakeholders and to discuss the experimental potential of the AIP territory, especially in its tech-oriented R&I focus. Moreover, the pilot is acting as a bridge between the Municipality and stakeholders (technology companies, universities, etc) to propagate the national 5G agenda. In this respect, one of the key achievements highlighted by the Local Coalition is in terms of enhanced dialogue, collaboration and trust, perceived as a direct effect of the T-Factor activities and ongoing conversations.

Regarding operational capacities, the pilot is well employing its resources and the Coalition partners reported to be increasingly aligned. Furthermore, the pilot has **raised additional financial resources** and has already identified new channels for fundraising for the next

implementation period. Moreover, the **recent entry of Kaunas Fortress Park** (a public institution that manages and develops a large part of the unique fortified heritage complex in Kaunas) **as a formal partner of the Local Coalition** brought about an important added value to the strategic planning of the portfolio, strengthening capacities and opportunities for engagement and outreach especially to local communities and informal groups around the site and at broader city level. During the period considered, the Local Coalition has also leveraged the expertise of two Transformation Labs, namely, T-Lab 3 'Citizen-led Smartness' and T-Lab 6 'Social Innovation and Social Inclusion'. Through its members **City of Lodz** and **University of Lodz**, T-Lab 6 has supported the pilot (and will keep on supporting it in the coming period) around **institutional actions and possible strategies and approaches to strengthen participatory engagement in urban redevelopments, with special emphasis on young people and children**. In doing so, the City of Lodz and University of Lodz are leveraging their expertise and recent knowledge gathered through the regeneration of **EC1 and the new centre of Lodz**, one of the Advanced Cases of T-Factor. **Futuribile**, within T-Lab 3, has instead concentrated efforts on possible pathways and approaches to collaborative and inclusive digital placemaking and smart urban planning and development, working in particular on **guidelines and principles for metaverse platforms designed to welcome a plurality of voices and diversities across gender and sexual orientation, cultural background, socio-economic background, and more**. To test this approach next year, it has been anticipated by the local coalition that the platform will focus on engaging, among others, the **LGBTQ+ community**. This stream of activities has already led to the production of a **Manifesto** to consolidate and capture interdisciplinary reflections on urban and civic applications of metaverse platforms.

From an operational point of view, the Local Coalition has highlighted a number of challenges especially related to organising activities on site, due to the **lack of spaces and regulatory limitations on land use and permissioning for temporary structures**. In addition, the early stage of the development coupled with the management and investment structure

that is yet to be defined, create uncertainty around possibilities for meanwhile activities, especially for more regular and stable ones. To partially overcome this limit, the collaboration with Kaunas Fortress is key, as it makes it possible to test temporary uses in their own spaces, adjacent to the AIIP area.

Towards the next implementation period, the Local Coalition has outlined a number of areas for improving its meanwhile strategy. First, more effort shall be invested on outreach and engagement with individuals and organisations around the AIIP site as the current project activities have not fully engaged them. More engagement effort shall also be devoted to universities located nearby the area, especially by facilitating their matchmaking with tech companies and start-ups towards joint proposals and projects that further explore possibilities for the future AIIP.

Furthermore, as already mentioned, the concept and practice of meanwhile uses is lagging behind in Kaunas and beyond, which stands as a unique opportunity to advance novel ways to urban regeneration in the country. The upcoming period should strengthen effort on building, testing, and showcasing concrete examples of meanwhile uses, especially by **shifting to more regular and stable uses in the meanwhile that can start retaining and anchoring people to places**. In this respect, the development of the social dimension for the AIIP requires a coherent integration with the tech innovation aspect of the development strategy; the Coalition is working on finding creative solutions to connect these two diverse yet complementary aspects. An important factor in relation to this could be the collaboration between the Municipality and the Kaunas Fortress Park, towards concrete activities aiming at weaving technology within participatory placemaking. This could also contribute to spark new meanings and narratives around the site and its future positioning as an innovation industry park, putting social, economic and environmental sustainability and innovation at the very centre of the vision of the future Park. To this end, one major aspect emerging from the evaluation concerns the need for the current redevelopment

strategy to strengthen its social dimensions to promote a more inclusive and sustainable regeneration of the territory. The pilot is therefore working towards this key challenge of activating the site by developing a community dimension using culture and creativity-driven meanwhile uses.

'The legacy is towards changing the mindset towards what could happen next, and how cultural and community spaces could influence and find meaningful synergies with the technology and innovation component and vice versa through meanwhile use. T Factor could leave a legacy in the form of showcasing the practice of meanwhile use or urbanism and its potential which could be an inspiration for others' (Local Coalition).

Pilot Self-assessment scoreboard

	Dimensions	1	2	3	4
STRATEGIC	Positioning & Reputation	The portfolio poorly contributes to enhancing the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is not properly valorised.	The portfolio partially contributes to the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is considered but not a driver in the cultural and social evolution of the area	The portfolio brings a great visibility to the area and raises awareness about its heritage	The portfolio has provided the area with a new identity and its heritage is appreciated by diverse audiences.
	Attractiveness	The portfolio is raising limited interest and struggles to attract diverse audiences and target groups.	The portfolio raises the interest of target groups and engages with an unvaried audience on a local level.	The portfolio is compelling for all target groups and attracts a diverse audience both locally and from the surroundings	The portfolio is compelling and raises the interest of new groups and audiences both locally and from the surroundings
	Relevance & Opportunity	The portfolio addresses in a limited way local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are neither investigated nor pursued.	The portfolio addresses some local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are identified	The portfolio inclusively responds to pressing local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Expands opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets	The portfolio is adjusted to address new emerging challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. creates a number of new opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets.
OPERATIONAL	Planning & Delivery Capacities	The portfolio has limited resources and the retrieval of missing resources is yet to be defined.	The portfolio has some available resources and activities that could retrieve resources are under definition.	The portfolio is financially sustainable and activities/fundraising initiatives to retrieve them are in progress .	The portfolio is financially sustainable and has retrieved most fundings.
	Resilience, Flexibility & Adaptability	The portfolio has not identified emerging needs and opportunities that could have influenced the masterplan	The portfolio has identified some emerging needs and opportunities but strong 'evidence' is missing	Emerging needs and opportunities have been identified and masterplan adjustments are under definition	Emerging needs and opportunities have been fully defined and the masterplan has been adapted accordingly
	Interoperability & Connectivity	The pilot is not aware of other initiatives in the area and has not identified relevant policies and plans that could contribute to the meanwhile strategy	The portfolio is aligned with some initiatives in the area or policies and plans relevant to the meanwhile use strategy have been analysed.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are almost established. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy supported by policy programmes.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are concrete. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy is contributing and supported by policy programmes.
RELATIONAL	Impact time & Depth (Too early to assess)	The portfolio results are requiring more time than expected and not all results and impacts will be achieved	The portfolio results are timely and most results and impacts are expected to be achieved.	The portfolio results have been achieved earlier than expected allowing to add additional uses for different groups.	The portfolio is involving and aligning around local innovation missions with a plethora of diverse stakeholders.
	Agency & Legitimacy	The portfolio does not contribute to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors to involve to build multi-sectoral coalitions have not been identified	The portfolio contributes in a limited way to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors have been identified but must define how to involve them in multi-sectoral coalitions	The portfolio contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established	The portfolio strongly contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An inclusive array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established
	Legacy, Sustainability & Scalability	The portfolio does not have a clear legacy.	The portfolio creates certain conditions for long term legacy but remains context-specific (not transferable).	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become more sustainable in the long-term. E.g. Scalability is being investigated	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become fully scalable or transferrable.

AMSTERDAM SCIENCE PARK

Photo credits: Waag

AMSTERDAM SCIENCE PARK

| About Amsterdam Science Park

The Amsterdam Science Park (ASP) is situated in the Amsterdam Eastern district, surrounded by a park, waterside, highway and train track and local neighbourhoods. The Amsterdam Science Park campus currently holds **the highest concentration of university science education and research organisations in the Netherlands, and one of the highest in Europe**. In addition, 170 knowledge-intensive companies, from promising startups to multinationals, make the park a hub for education, research, innovation and entrepreneurship in the field of ICT, life sciences, advanced instrumentation, high tech materials and sustainability. The development of the park in its current science-oriented function was initiated in 1946 and has been developed since the mid 80's, with the ASP masterplan being initiated in 2003 and revised in 2019. The latter 'Development Vision' report runs until 2028, demonstrating the advanced stage of this urban area in development and existence of established practices on site.

The latest update to the masterplan from 2019 subscribes to the following four strategic development goals: 1) **Colouring**: a 'programmatically colouring' of the area, with a certain mix of functions, which creates an optimal interaction environment, with a rich palette of qualities and facilities. 2) **Densification**: Adding a building programme to initiate the desired 'colouring', and to give certain functions 'critical mass' so that they can have even more impact nationally and internationally. 3) **Interweaving**: Stronger internal and external relationships through better routes in public space and traffic connections with the city and region and 4) **Sustainability**: Showcasing the top position in science with sustainable designs and techniques that also contribute to the liveability and environmental quality of the campus.

The site is of ecological significance to the province of North Holland in general and to its surroundings in particular. It functions as an ecological corridor, connecting biodiverse areas in the east and south of Amsterdam with waterways in the north of the city. Therefore, the ASP is given special consideration in terms of development and protection of ecological systems in urban environments.

| Overarching challenge and Innovation Missions in T-Factor

The T-Factor pilot at the Amsterdam Science Park understands and frames temporary uses as ways to *'renew the fundamental relationship between nature and humans in cities, as a way to contribute to the path towards sustainability'*. Temporary uses are seen as drivers for a green and nature-driven regeneration, supporting and enhancing the further development of the ASP towards long term objectives of sustainability, health and wellbeing and, overall, quality of life. Through this challenge, the meanwhile strategy aims to investigate **how community interventions, arts-led practices, and urban greening and wilderness can be brought together to advance novel new ways of understanding and designing the living environment**. In turn, this shall contribute to new modes of engagement, appreciation, and (re)valuation of nature and wilderness in urban settings that contribute to wildlife protection and preservation in urban settings.

The increase in people, buildings and activity in the ASP puts the natural environment and biodiversity in the area under pressure. Although there is a willingness to advance sustainable designs and techniques that can contribute to the campus' liveability and environmental quality, in practice the thematic focus on 'green' is underdeveloped. This tension between the human-functional need versus sustainability and biodiversity goals is also reflected in the green management of the park, which tends to prioritise human needs over biodiversity.

Furthermore, the Amsterdam Science Park is run through a **complex governance structure** including three major organisations - the University of Amsterdam, the Dutch Research Council and the Municipality of Amsterdam, which often makes decision-making slow particularly when it comes to temporary and small scale initiatives.

Moreover, while vibrant with student and work-life during daytime, the park is sparsely used after working hours and almost vacant at weekends and during holidays, with the exception of a few recreational spaces. Half of the area (NWO) side is closed off with a fence after 18:00 and access is granted through a single road dividing the two parts of the park. This results in a **sense of isolation and poor accessibility, further exacerbated by some feelings and perceptions of unsafety** among the residents, mostly around the Flevopark and cycle path on the north-west of the park and under the tunnel that connects it with the train station to the South.

Within this context, the meanwhile strategy is built around three core innovation missions:

Mission 1: Wild and Cultivated Spaces: advancing green and wilderness-centred placemaking and visioning for the ASP, through temporary initiatives that leverage arts practices to advance novel forms of understanding and appreciation of the living environment and its multiple species.

Mission 2: Do-It-Together Eco-Practices: boosting a diversity of collaborative, creative and mutually reinforcing eco-practices across the ASP, giving impetus to both existing and emerging eco-communities and contributing to make the Amsterdam Science Park a lively place for sustainable, active and green lifestyles that embrace nature and the living environment.

Mission 3: Alternative (informal) masterplan: developing an alternative masterplan which can give voice to a plurality of actors on site, including non-humans - with the ultimate aim of influencing the complex governance structure of the site and enabling more participatory forms of development.

Figure 9, Theory of Change of ASP Pilot

| Meanwhile portfolio

The portfolio of the Amsterdam Pilot sees Mission 1 (Wild and Cultivated Spaces) and 2 (Do it Together eco-practices) related activities as the starting point to the development of the temporary use strategy.

Through a number of prompt and regular activities that leverage arts-led spatial practices, these two missions start to thematically position the pilot, attracting different target groups, contributing to community building and creation of relational capital, and engaging people and communities in a collective discovery of nature and wilderness. Activities such as Artist Tracks, and the Monthly Eco-Program mainly serve these purposes, involving different actors and organisations in the co-design and co-delivery of these activities.

Activities around Mission 1 and 2 mainly weave together both relational and operational purposes - engaging different publics in the (re)appreciation of wild and cultivated spaces on site, where the renewed relationship between humans and nature can concretely take on different ways of experiencing natural settings.

Mission 3 envisages two different streams: one is 'physical', working with stakeholders to create an alternative map of the area, collecting stories and use them to create way- and story-finding with physical installations; the second is 'digital', building the framework and the design of the Field Atlas. Towards the longer run, the ambition is to create a Do-It-Together Ecology Hub, as a semi-permanent space that can work as an enabling platform for eco-practices across the site, convening different communities, supporting artistic interventions, and showcasing the multiple stories and 'green' experiences developed across the ASP. New maps and wayfindings are also a possible legacy of the pilot, meant to foster the thematic positioning of the site as a nature-friendly one. The Field Atlas stands as the key innovation area of the Portfolio: by harvesting and showcasing data and initiatives on site, this is a tool meant to support 'eco-practices advocacy', so as to better connect bottom-up practices to institutional and policy aspirations on greening and sustainability for the ASP and beyond.

Figure 10: Meanwhile Portfolio of the ASP Pilot
 Double clic on the text to access the digital version of the Portfolio in Miro

| Portfolio delivery: overview

In the time frame considered for the mid-term evaluation^[11], the ASP pilot has designed and organised six different activities of the portfolio, (1) GMS 'Building messy corners', (2) GMS 'Reading lichen', (3) GMS 'Biodiversity Walk', (4) GMS 'Building for Beasts', (5) GMS 'ASP by night', and (6) GMS 'Wood Wide Web'.

The '**Green Maker Space**' (GMS) is a **monthly open workspace** that consists of a series of hands-on workshops, lectures, and experiences that all together are meant to explore and dig deeper into eco-practices. These practices are ways of engaging with nature in urban settings, bringing together students, university staff, residents and interested people in a collective and collaborative discovery of nature and wilderness in and around the ASP. The program includes topics all across the relationship among placemaking, ecology, biodiversity, arts and science and gradually moves from light practices to more in depth urban-ecological concepts.

Building 'messy corners' was an outdoor workshop organised in March 2022 with the purpose of exploring ways in which **new habitats for urban wildlife can be created** (messy corners), including through the use of organic and non-organic waste. The workshop was guided by the **eco-artist Maurice van der Molen**. The 'messy corners' aimed to enhance the biodiversity for the smallest creatures such as microorganisms and insects. During the workshop, the issue of 'messiness and cleanliness' from the perspective of humans and non-humans was discussed, exploring questions such as 'how and where you might create a messy corner'; 'what materials can be used'; 'which species we might expect to find in these newly created habitats' were elaborated.

Reading lichen was an outdoor workshop delivered in April 2022, aimed at engaging participants in a **citizen science session** where the observation

of lichen is used as an indicator to assess air quality in the local context. Lichen is a symbiosis between a fungi and algae, and is able to grow almost anywhere. Every type of climate has its own lichen. For instance, there are lichens that love nitrogen, whereas other lichens disappear when there is too much nitrogen in the air. The type of lichen that can be found in the surroundings unravels something about the specific environment.

The Biodiversity Walk was a walk and talk session dedicated to urban biodiversity, delivered in May 2022. During the walk, the Local Coalition introduced the participants to the tensions between urban development and biodiversity at the ASP, where wild flora and fauna is under threat. The activity discussed and contrasted different perspectives and perceptions of the participants, especially interrogating 'why' a biodiverse environment is needed and for 'whom'. The participants could take a walk on wild and green initiatives at the ASP - such as '**Anna's Tuin & Ruigte**' Garden, the 'messy corners' of the ASP, the community garden from **Spark Village** and the terrains of the university - together with an urban ecology expert of Waag.

Photo Credits: Waag

[11] Generally, the period considered in this report is February 2022 - October 2022, which is the overall time frame in which the T-Factor Pilots started to implement and run their temporary use strategies. However, it should be noted that the insights and results (especially more qualitative results) captured in this report also refer to the preceding period (the whole 2021), particularly when it comes to preliminary activities of engagement, initial scoping and co-design that started to set the ground for implementing and iterating temporary uses and activities.

[Building for Beasts](#) consisted of several talks and workshops spread out over two days in June 2022. The aim was to explore different aspects of animal-aided design starting from theory towards putting it in (artistic) practice and to enrich the local biodiversity with hands-on knowledge from the participants. This activity saw the close collaboration between Waag and LAND, as part of the support of the latter within the scope of T-Lab 4 'Urban Design for Sociality & Wellbeing'. The programme consisted of:

- Short talks and a panel discussion hosted by LAND and Waag on Nature-Based solutions (NBS): NBS are a relevant topic within urban development. However, the main target group for NBS is often human beings; the talks presented how cities can also be designed for non-human organisms.
- Two different workshops on the design and construction of spaces for two different animal species, namely the small newt and the dragonfly. Questions that were being tackled were 'what would they need to live, to gather food, to mate and to shelter? Where in the area could we add interventions? Does it make any difference to design an outside space from the perspective of beasts?'. These workshops were aimed to broaden and deepen the knowledge of the Local Coalition and of all participants on NBS, while adding an extra layer on the topic from a non-human perspective.

[ASP by night](#) was a walk & talk on urban biodiversity and wildlife at night times. During the activity, various locations on site were visited to spot and discuss how certain animals can be found at night, such as birds of paradise, timid hedgehog and bats. Examples of discussed topics were 'how they behave' and 'where they mostly can be found'. The walk was provided by an ecologist, who elaborated where the human nocturnal animals are nowadays and discovering together what 'happens' while we sleep.

The workshop [Wood Wide Web](#) explored the efficacy of 'improving the soil biome through mycelium' as potential green intervention for the regeneration area. During this practical workshop, the participants had

the chance to look at the ground beneath them. The workshop was composed by the following moments:

- Do-It-Yourself measuring the Wood Wide Web: A biologist elaborated on how he built a homemade mud battery in Waag's Open Wet Lab and how it helps to get to know more about the ground.
- A conversation on biodiverse soils: a talk on the importance of a healthy soil and ecosystem by a soil ecologist.
- Discussion – Who claims the underground? Plants, fungi and people: everyone claims a piece of subsurface. Therefore, it is quite a challenge to get them to live harmoniously together.
- Inoculating tree trunks: the participants received the chance to grow new 'wood-wide-web' networks in dead wood. They filled a few stumps in the park with mycelium and learned how to repeat this yourself at home.

Photo Credits: Waag

Besides the GMS-programme, the ASP pilot has focused on **several preparatory and planning actions, mainly consisting of internal coordination meetings and meetings with local stakeholders,** more specifically:

- Examination of potential plots of ASP to improve the land use and biodiversity.
- Analysis of potential local cooperation partners and communities, in which the first collaboration was created with the primary school 'Montis Montessori' for the workshop Green Maker Space #4 Building for Beasts.
- Final selection of artists, namely Esmee Geerken & De Onkruidenier.
- Start of the design and development phase of the 'Field atlas'.
- Ongoing discussions with local stakeholders, such as UVA, NWO, Amsterdam Science & Business about the (future) role of Waag in filling of temporary vacant spaces and talks with the area broker on involving citizens' perspectives in (re)designing outdoor spaces surrounding the Amsterdam Science Park.
- The design of a pop-up Urban Ecology hub to support lobbying and to inspire the future Hub.

| Stakeholders and Beneficiaries

All Green Maker Space activities were organised by **Waag** in an open workspace at the **Start-up Village at ASP**. However, the pilot needed to work and collaborate with local ecologists and artists that have the right expertise and resources to execute the programme. GMS 1 'the messy corners' has worked with **Maurice van der Molen**, an ecological artist. He creates ecological gardens and landscape objects under the name of 'Groene Tenen' (green toes). He is also a volunteer at the permaculture-project 'Anna's Tuin & Ruigte' Garden located at the ASP. Similarly, GMS 2 'Reading lichen' was accompanied by a researcher and a social designer. Related to GMS 3 'Biodiversity Walk', the partner of the ASP pilot was UVA huisvesting. The pilot was invited by UVA huisvesting to connect the sustainability agenda of UVA, Waag and Anna's Garden & Ruigte as a first collaboration. The workshop was aimed at the visitors from the UVA network. For GMS 4 'Building for Beasts', the ASP pilot collaborated with

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LAND. The activity was co-organised by T-Lab 4 and T-Lab 5, with the support of T-Lab 3. GMS 5 'ASP by Night' event was provided with an explanation of the ecologist Gido Kuijsten along and photos were taken by a multidisciplinary artist, Mini Maxwell. Lastly, for GMS 6 'Wood Wide Web', the ASP pilot has engaged with soil ecologist Elly Morriën (University of Amsterdam) and biologist Kas Houthuijs (BioHack Academy instructor at Waag) to question the living and material infrastructure of the Science Park.

Through the activities, the Local Coalition managed to engage multiple beneficiaries. All the workshops were part of the wider 'eco-practices' mission and served the purpose of building a local eco-community participated by a diversity of persons and groups, including students, academic staff, residents, eco-practitioners, third sector organisations and, more in general, people interested in nature and greening topics.

Activity 1: Building 'messy' corners

Target groups: varied group of local inhabitants, stakeholders connected to the local permaculture project, educational facilities, and interested persons from the wider Amsterdam context

Collaborators: Maurice van der Molen, an ecological artist

Keywords:
#Greening & Biodiversity
#Learning, Skilling, Making

1 session

4 topics addressed: (1) Biodiversity in the city and urban wildlife, (2) Human and non-human needs for 'clean' vs 'messy' cities, (3) How to make a 'messy corner' from found and (4) Creating biodiversity corridors.

Regular use
23/03/2022

Main beneficiaries:

16 participants

1 volunteer from 'Anna's Tuin & Ruigte' Garden

2 people linked to Waag (student or work)

13 citizens from the neighbourhood

Activity 2: Reading lichen

Target groups: varied group of local inhabitants, interested persons in citizen science and data collection and academia.

Collaborators: Social designer (Lotte Sluijs) and a researcher

Keywords:
#Greening & Biodiversity
#Cohesion & Social Justice
#Learning, Skilling, Making

1 session

4 topics addressed: (1) Citizen Science: with more-than-human life, (2) Lichen, (3) Subjectivity and scientific method and (4) Air quality.

Prompt use
13/04/2022

Main beneficiaries:

16 participants

some participants were affiliated with ASP, either as student or worker, some people from the neighbourhood who visited the first edition of the GMS and persons linked to the citizen science community of Amsterdam.

Activity 3: Biodiversity Walk

Target groups: visitors of the UVA network.

Collaborators: UVA huisvesting

Keywords:
#Greening & Biodiversity
#Cohesion & Social Justice
#Learning, Skilling, Making

5 topics addressed: (1) Permaculture gardening, (2) Green Management, (3) Governance - how to include the 'voice' of non-human actors; (4) Co-creative exercise: reimagining wadi as meeting point for more-than-human and human exchange and (5) Mess vs Clean - why natural waste is of benefit to other organisms.

Prompt use
20/05/2022

Main beneficiaries:

4 participants

2 researchers from UvA

Activity 4: Building for Beasts

Target groups: students, workers, and inhabitants.

Collaborators: landscape consultancy 'LAND!', T-Lab3, T-Lab 4 and T-Lab 5

Keywords:
#Greening & Biodiversity
#Cohesion & Social Justice
#Learning, Skilling, Making
#Physical & Mental Health

3 city ecologists

1 other

1 topics addressed: (1) Non Human Perspectives in Urban Space, (2) Animal Oriented Design at Amsterdam Science Park research and (3) Animal Oriented Design in practice.

Prompt use
14/06/2022 - 15/06/2022

Main beneficiaries:
15 participants

1 from municipality

2 residents of the neighbourhood

4 students

2 teachers primary school

2 professors

4 sessions: (1) Talks and a panel discussion, (2) Animal Oriented Design - Deep dive, (3) workshop: The small newt and (4) workshop: The dragonfly.

Mission 1: Do-It-Together Eco-practices

Activity 5: ASP by night

Target groups: varied group of local inhabitants, visitors with loose connection to Amsterdam Science Park, academia, and artists.

Collaborators: ecologist Gido Kuijstenalong and multidisciplinary artist Mini Maxwell

Keywords:
#Greening & Biodiversity
#Cohesion & Social Justice
#Learning, Skilling, Making
#Physical & Mental Health

Regular use

23/03/2022

- 25** Main beneficiaries: participants host and organisers of the music and club scene, residents of the neighbourhood and persons linked to the citizen science community of Amsterdam.
- 2** topics addressed: (1) human nightlife - diversity & inclusion and (2) non-human nightlife at ASP.
- 1** session

Activity 6: Wood Wide Web

Target groups: Varied group of academia, artists, local biodiversity experts and wider audiences related to Waag.

Collaborators: soil ecologist Elly Morriën and biologist Kas Houthuijs

Keywords:
#Greening & Biodiversity
#Cohesion & Social Justice
#Learning, Skilling, Making
#Physical & Mental Health

- 4** topics addressed: (1) Wood Wide Web - vital more-than-human infrastructures; the role fungi & mycelium in ground, (2) World Wide Web - vital human infrastructures & underground area developments in the city, (3) Role healthy soil life and planetary health and (4) How to improve soil biome using mycelium.

Prompt use

31/08/2022

- 6** Main beneficiaries: participants
- 1** from local community
- 2** students
- 1** ecologist
- 1** entrepreneur in green businesses
- 1** artist
- 1** session

Contribution to impact at mission level - Main activities' results

In the paragraphs that follow, an overview of the main results achieved through the activities described earlier is provided. Results are mainly extracted from online surveys addressed to the beneficiaries involved as well as from the self-reporting templates compiled by ASP Pilot coordinator

Empowered to participate in the community/area

General feedback of the surveys indicate that the participants were already motivated to engage with, and contribute to different eco-practices. The success factors of the cycle of events were mainly the possibility to work in a practical way and the opportunity of meeting like-minded people and individuals working in the domain of sustainability, which were critical aspects behind the increasing understanding of eco-practices emerged from the survey. Furthermore, the participants of 'ASP by night' and 'Wood wide web' responded to the following questions (with the following scales: 1. Strongly disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Neutral, 4. Agree and 5. Strongly agree)

Figure 11: outcome proxy empowerment to participate in the community for respective ASP by night and wood wide web

The first interaction between the participants was made through the GMS programme and was highly valued. The main contributor to these events was the collaboration with 'Anna's Tuin & Ruigte' Garden. Visiting the garden was a motivator to participate in the area and was considered as attractive by the participants. During the events, the participants expressed their willingness to participate in (future) initiatives such as the 'Anna's Tuin & Ruigte' garden. However, they stated that they were interested in **joining existing initiatives rather than developing new ones**. Furthermore, the GMS monthly programme had mildly positive results in engaging with local communities around the ASP. The events were communicated both online and on site with posters, with results in terms of attendance varying from event to event. The ASP pilot did not have in advance a good overview of the participants profiles, resulting that the activities attracted inhabitants from all over the city, and only in part reached local communities of students, academics, and neighbours.

The evaluation results on this outcome indicate that the pilot needs to **change its approach to the GMS programme in the near future, focussing more on existing communities in ASP and cultivate eco-practices with them rather than reaching out to the general audience.**

Awareness & value to green spaces and wilderness

Participants to the events were mainly people interested in the themes proposed, and were mostly aware and already engaged on themes such as sustainability and eco-practices. In fact, most of the respondents from the events 'Building for beasts' and 'ASP by night' reported that they already had an attention to green spaces and wilderness. Therefore, for these events, the level of awareness remained relatively constant. Positive feedback emerged regarding the approach adopted, which was very practical and hands-on.

Figure 12: outcome proxy enhanced awareness & value to green spaces and wilderness for respective building for beasts, ASP by night and wood wide web

Lastly, for the 'Wood Wide Web', the participants stated that although they already valued green spaces, the workshop had a positive contribution to enhanced awareness and perceived importance of greening and nature in cities. The reason for this is twofold. First, the world of microorganisms is often a sort of 'black box' and the participants gained insights on the importance of these organisms in the natural world. Second, the event reminded the participants of the importance of soil quality and of allowing soils to develop and mature to obtain significant effects on biodiversity. The workshop provided a comprehensive and conceptual explanation of how soil functions within the greater ecosystem.

Knowledge about biodiversity and urban ecology

Regarding this dimension, as for awareness, most of the participants already had prior knowledge and some understanding of urban ecology and biodiversity. Yet, some specific events were beneficial in terms of adding on new knowledge. Moreover, surveys' feedback gave an indication that the participants are eager to know more about biodiversity and urban ecology, and acquire new knowledge and practical skills. More specifically:

- 'Building for beasts': the event was hands-on with different exercises, and provided new learning perspectives through a rich panel of speakers and experts. Furthermore, the participants specified that they would like to engage further with these learnings and enhance the depth and specifics of the gained knowledge.
- The 'ASP By Night' event provided specific information about animal and behaviour and what the influence is of (green) gardens on the identified animals.
- The respondents of the 'Wood Wide Web' indicated that the speakers and experts brought a clear and comprehensive story about the soil and type of life happening in the ground beneath our feet.

The general feedback of the events was informative for the pilot on how to design the upcoming events of the programme. It turned out that the activities were somehow too simple. The pilot can enrich the programme with deeper knowledge, increasing the expertise level and boost the practical applicability of the urban ecology concepts explored. Therefore, in future events, the organisers will keep using the hands-on element but also try to involve (more) experts to ensure that the awareness and knowledge increases as much as possible.

Figure 13: knowledge about biodiversity and urban ecology for respective Building for beasts, ASP by night and Wood Wide Web

Square metre green and highly biodiverse gardens

The GMS activities were all part of the do-it-together eco-programme which is directly connected to Mission 2 'Do-It-Together Eco-practices' and indirectly connected to Mission 1 'Wild and Cultivated Spaces'. The ASP pilot has indicated that they established an interesting portfolio of Do-It-Together eco-practices. However, these initiatives were happening on a small scale, which was insufficient to achieve the objective to increase the square metre (biodiverse) gardens.

| Contribution to impact at Pilot level

The section describes the pilot level changes and considerations gathered through the 'Critical Friend' interview. As anticipated, the interview is aimed at exploring if and how the activities undertaken during the period of reference are contributing towards long term outcomes and impacts of urban regeneration, particularly from the point of view of enhanced strategic, operational and relational dimensions (ref. Methodology section). In the following paragraph we report on the main strengths and weaknesses that emerged through the interview. A self-assessment scoreboard filled out by the Local Coalition is provided at the end of the section. It is important to highlight that the insights and reflections reported in this chapter do not only capture the voice and perceptions of the Local Coalition; they also include and integrate the results of the ongoing observation and support developed by the Transformation Agency over time, in its role of 'critical friend' of the pilot.

The Amsterdam Science Park (ASP) is in an **advanced stage of development** and is expected to be completed in 2028. The ASP is a driver of innovation acting as a hub for high-quality education, businesses, entrepreneurship, life sciences, and research. Currently, the park is characterised by the highest concentration of university science education and research organisations in the Netherlands. Additionally, it is occupied by 170 knowledge-intensive companies ranging from startups to multinationals. The ASP is embedded within a **tripartite governance model** involving the City of Amsterdam, University of Amsterdam (UvA) and Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO), characterised by a slow and scattered decision-making process that adds to the complexity of implementing the meanwhile strategy.

The park is developed with the area's agricultural heritage and rests on the fertile land reclaimed by the sea which forms a basis of present and potential types of surrounding ecosystems. One of the central visions for the last stages of development is towards **sustainability and interweaving a relationship of the park with the city**. At the same time, there is an increasing presence of built infrastructure, people, and activities in the park, which puts immense pressure on the natural environment and biodiversity.

Within this context, the Local Coalition looks at the ecological relevance of the park as the key topic for creative and collaborative discovery and experimentation through the meanwhile. In line with the local development vision, the pilot is working toward building synergies inside and outside the park through the lens of meanwhile uses and urban ecology. More in particular, the pilot understands meanwhile uses as means to support nature-driven regeneration, **exploring the nexus between urban greening and wilderness through arts-led practices and 'do it together' interventions, as ways to contribute to novel ways of understanding, interacting with, appreciating and (re)valuing nature in cities**.

The monthly eco programme stands as the core meanwhile activity of the pilot. Through the activities of the programme organised during the period, the pilot has managed to **slightly improve the visibility of, and awareness on the importance and value of nature and wildlife in urban settings in general and at ASP in particular**. The activities attracted relatively diverse publics, including first-time visitors. The Local coalition highlights the fact that the topic of urban ecology and the hands-on approach gathered people with similar interests and backgrounds, and helped form a community around these topics. The pilot also worked to foster alliances among 'green' local initiatives in the park such as the Anna's Tuin & Ruigte garden, local artists and students associations. The pilot has initiated collaboration with two artists to develop artistic installations in the park aimed at boosting the green image of the ASP and engaging local stakeholders. Thus, relations have not only been built

among individuals but also among different groups that share similar goals, motivations and interests. The overall purpose of these collaborations is to gain more bargaining power and thus to have more chances to influence higher levels of decision-making at the ASP.

A particular aspect of this pilot is also in the relation between the human and non-human actors in the park. Through what could be considered as a radical approach to participation and following its ecological agenda, the ASP pilot not only addresses people, but also other forms of living and inhabiting urban settings, interrogating crucial aspects such as *'what if other forms of living in cities would have a voice and say on placemaking'*.

“Working with hands, meeting like-minded people, and understanding different perspectives are some gains from T-Factor activities. Also, we can now help in facilitating the exchange among like-minded people through the project” (Local Coalition).

Generally, the topics of greening, biodiversity and urban wildlife seem to be attractive and relevant to a diversity of publics, which may also reflect a more general awareness around climate change and climate-related risks. Moreover, a benefit emerges around **the positive contribution of the pilot towards promoting the image of the site as a green area**, in contrast to general perceptions of it as mainly a business and university district and thus as a destination not eventually suited for general visitors and for free time.

The pilot has worked well so far in generating a recognisable and engaging eco-programme. To this end, **the collaboration with the T-Labs has proven to be of great value in designing and delivering some of the activities of the programme**. More in detail, the pilot is leveraging expertise from three T Labs, namely, T-Lab 3 'Citizen-led Smartness'; T-Lab 4 'Urban design for sociality and well being'; and T-Lab 5 'Circular and Collaborative Economy'. For example, T-Lab 4 supported the research, design, and development of the Animal-oriented design workshop; T-Lab 3 & 4 organised a participatory walk through the ASP to explore the area and its biodiversity, inviting different stakeholders to

to map and share their perceptions and emotions along the main stops of the walk. Over the period considered for mid-term evaluation, the pilot has managed to explore and showcase a rich portfolio of eco practices that could be further advanced and boosted at ASP and beyond. As an additional outcome, a high school adopted the animal-oriented design workshop within their curriculum. Students would be autonomously replicating the program at the park which would further promote the positioning and awareness of the site.

Based on the evolution and critical reflection on the portfolio delivery so far, the pilot has identified a number of areas for improvement in light of the next implementation period. First, most of the activities run so far attracted and involved specific people and publics with some prior knowledge and awareness on the topic(s) proposed. Yet, in order to embrace eco-practices as ways to weaving people in urban nature and foster bottom-up capacity and agency in greening and biodiversity, there is a need to understand how the latter **can be brought to a larger or non-specialistic public, creating interest, motivation and willingness to action**. To this end, there is a specific need to better understand how to engage the residents and communities living around the site, especially those experiencing situations of deprivation or risks of marginalisation, who could thus benefit from collaborative eco-practices. In general, the participation of people in the project activities could be enhanced and the pilot shall be more strategic by focusing on the engagement of the immediate local community. In terms of knowledge building, the current approach of the pilot was to disseminate knowledge on urban ecology, so as to increase chances of outreach and engagement. However, surveys' results generally show a slight increase in knowledge as participants already had some background and therefore would be interested in gaining more advanced knowledge. Therefore, for the next activities, the pilot would aim at delivering activities rich in information and in delivering practical skills that participants can apply in their daily lives.

Overall, the pilot is on track regarding the delivery of the portfolio. It has initiated work streams and activities for Mission 2 "Do it Together Eco Practices" in the form of delivering monthly eco-programs.

Moreover, Mission 2-related activities are also contributing to Mission 1 “Wild and Cultivated Spaces”, allowing to test small experiments of wilderness-led placemaking. However, moving forward there is a need to design more activities under mission 1. The outputs from Mission 1 and 2 would eventually form the basis for addressing Mission 3 “Alternative (Informal) Masterplan”. Fostering changes at institutional levels would require an improved understanding from the point of view of urban planning and regulation, especially in terms of **licencing and permissioning** bottom-up nature-based solutions and wilderness placemaking.

The experience gathered by the pilot team so far have supported **continuous self-reflection and in turn adaptation, re-adjustments, and refinements**. The pilot has pinpointed the necessity to be precise and effective for the implementation of the next round of meanwhile activities. First, the pilot shall focus more on the communities and people residing adjacent to the park and through more activities focused on practical skills' development and knowledge. This could help in generating social and environmental value and in developing an effective narrative, better able to influence and trigger changes at the institutional level. Second, it is key for the pilot to understand how to expand participation and keep momentum around the activities, as a key condition for creating, cultivating, and sustaining a community of practice and place around urban ecology. Third, the pilot team highlights the need to understand the implications of meanwhile uses at policy and urban planning level to demonstrate the relevance of nature and wildlife regeneration practices. In doing so, it is essential to build relations and trust with regeneration stakeholders and officials at the top level of the ASP, which stands as a highly critical point for the pilot as a whole.

As previously introduced, the management of the ASP is mostly run through a tripartite governance model participated by three landowners. This aspect is proving to be particularly hard for a number of reasons, including the complex and scattered system of decision-making that stands at the backbone of land management and development. For instance, one of the major bottlenecks is the lack of institutional approval

park for nature and wildlife driven interventions. In addition, when it comes to synergies with organisations on site such as universities, businesses, research organisations, and startups, the pilot is yet to materialise possible collaborations. Nevertheless, the pilot team develops constant communication and information about the project activities toward the management bodies of the park, which is helping raise awareness regarding the potential to implement meanwhile activities and reinforce the green agenda of the development.

Lastly, we shall highlight that the pilot is addressing a quite specific and challenging topic. Demonstrating the relevance and effectiveness of eco-practices can be hard, especially when considering that nature and wildlife have their own pace of greening and growing which is typically a slow process. Generating evidence on the relevance of nature-driven practices in urban areas generally demands a wider timeframe which further adds to the complexity of effectively engaging the public, institutional actors and other stakeholders. In order to bring nature back to cities, there is a need to advance radical new ways of (re)valuing nature and appreciating nature's time, voices, and even to include them as active actors who have their own rights to the city.

“We want to focus more on existing communities in ASP and cultivate eco practices with them. To achieve an impact at masterplan level, we need to be more focused and precise in our proposition. We want to move to the level of dialogue of green areas management and landscaping. We are refining our approach, we want to have a macro-level approach with continuous micro-interventions through T Factor in the park” (Local Coalition).

Pilot Self-assessment scoreboard

	Dimensions	1	2	3	4
STRATEGIC	Positioning & Reputation	The portfolio poorly contributes to enhancing the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is not properly valorised.	The portfolio partially contributes to the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is considered but not a driver in the cultural and social evolution of the area	The portfolio brings a great visibility to the area and raises awareness about its heritage	The portfolio has provided the area with a new identity and its heritage is appreciated by diverse audiences.
	Attractiveness	The portfolio is raising limited interest and struggles to attract diverse audiences and target groups.	The portfolio raises the interest of target groups and engages with an unvaried audience on a local level.	The portfolio is compelling for all target groups and attracts a diverse audience both locally and from the surroundings	The portfolio is compelling and raises the interest of new groups and audiences both locally and from the surroundings
	Relevance & Opportunity	The portfolio addresses in a limited way local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are neither investigated nor pursued.	The portfolio addresses some local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are identified	The portfolio inclusively responds to pressing local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Expands opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets	The portfolio is adjusted to address new emerging challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. creates a number of new opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets.
OPERATIONAL	Planning & Delivery Capacities	The portfolio has limited resources and the retrieval of missing resources is yet to be defined.	The portfolio has some available resources and activities that could retrieve resources are under definition.	The portfolio is financially sustainable and activities/fundraising initiatives to retrieve them are in progress .	The portfolio is financially sustainable and has retrieved most fundings.
	Resilience, Flexibility & Adaptability	The portfolio has not identified emerging needs and opportunities that could have influenced the masterplan	The portfolio has identified some emerging needs and opportunities but strong 'evidence' is missing	Emerging needs and opportunities have been identified and masterplan adjustments are under definition	Emerging needs and opportunities have been fully defined and the masterplan has been adapted accordingly
	Interoperability & Connectivity	The pilot is not aware of other initiatives in the area and has not identified relevant policies and plans that could contribute to the meanwhile strategy	The portfolio is aligned with some initiatives in the area or policies and plans relevant to the meanwhile use strategy have been analysed.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are almost established. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy supported by policy programmes.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are concrete. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy is contributing and supported by policy programmes.
RELATIONAL	Impact time & Depth (Too early to assess)	The portfolio results are requiring more time than expected and not all results and impacts will be achieved	The portfolio results are timely and most results and impacts are expected to be achieved.	The portfolio results have been achieved earlier than expected allowing to add additional uses for different groups.	The portfolio is involving and aligning around local innovation missions with a plethora of diverse stakeholders.
	Agency & Legitimacy	The portfolio does not contribute to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors to involve to build multi-sectoral coalitions have not been identified	The portfolio contributes in a limited way to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors have been identified but must define how to involve them in multi-sectoral coalitions	The portfolio contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established	The portfolio strongly contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An inclusive array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established
	Legacy, Sustainability & Scalability	The portfolio does not have a clear legacy.	The portfolio creates certain conditions for long term legacy but remains context-specific (not transferable).	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become more sustainable in the long-term. E.g. Scalability is being investigated	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become fully scalable or transferrable.

EUSTON LONDON

EUSTON, LONDON

| About Euston

Euston is located within the **London Borough of Camden**, on the Northern edge of central London. Since the 1830s the area has undergone continuous change predominantly relating to updates in transport infrastructure at Euston Station. The area of Euston is predominantly known as a main transport hub for London, used by approximately 50 million passengers each year.

Surrounding Euston station are densely populated residential areas with a high percentage of social housing, in areas such as Somers Town to the east and Regents Park Estate to the west. Among key routes in close proximity to the station are Drummond Street which is famous for its south asian cuisine, and Charlton Street with a variety of local shops, cafes and a street market. London Euston also neighbours the '**Knowledge Quarter**', a large network of over 100 partner organisations of different kinds including academic, cultural, research, scientific and media organisations, large and small. Euston Road to the South of the station is a main route across London, and is therefore busy with traffic and pollution. In its current formation, Euston station creates a harsh geographical divide between the East and West sides of the station, completely cutting these residential areas off from one another, with few routes across. Despite its proximity to the centre of London, **the residents of Euston continue to face many social, economic, and environmental barriers**. However, the area is also characterised by a **strong sense of community** especially within neighbourhood pockets, and there are many local organisations working to alleviate specific issues, alongside Camden Council.

Euston has a very diverse population with higher populations of people within a range of ethnic groups than Camden overall. A higher proportion of households live in **socially rented accommodation** compared to the rest of Camden. Moreover, areas nearest Euston Station are over twice the density of Camden's average. A high proportion of families have dependent children. There are also many economic challenges in the area relating to **economic inactivity, low household incomes, older people and children living in deprivation, a high proportion of families on tax credits and a high percentage of working age adults in receipt of work benefits**. Economic barriers are often caused in part by a **lack of access to and attainment within education**. Furthermore, despite many residents reporting good health, there are some specific issues such as **high levels of childhood obesity, and high rates of death by lung cancer**. Moreover, Euston has been suffering from **progressive loss of public green open space** due to the current HS2 works in and around Euston. Whilst there is an intention for the regeneration project to actively contribute to these issues, there are substantial embedded issues. There is also a population increase of 11.4% predicted by 2028, which will present challenges and pressures around the integration of new and existing communities.

| Euston's Redevelopment

The **Euston Area Plan (EAP)**^[12] sets a clear vision for the area in 2031: *"The Euston area will be rejuvenated as both a local hub of activity and a gateway to London through new high quality comprehensive and transformational development above and around a world class transport interchange at Euston Station"*. One of the key projects to achieve this vision is the HS2, the new high speed railway terminus station that will serve as a transport superhub acting as a gateway to the North of the country. The HS2 is envisioned as a world-class '*infrastructure led regeneration project that will more than double the capacity of Euston station in peak hours, free up space for local and long distance commuter services and improve the connection with the London Underground*'.

^[12] The Euston Area Plan is a policy document put together by Camden Council and adopted in 2015, outlining the development criteria for Euston as an Opportunity Area for Growth (defined within the Camden Plan 2017 and with the London Plan 2016 published by the Greater London Authority). A revised Euston Area Plan is currently being produced by Camden council (alongside the Greater London Authority and Transport for London) informed by community engagement which is due to be finalised by 2023.

The **Over Station Development (OSD)** will reconnect the neighbourhoods that have been separated by the railway infrastructure by building above, between and around Euston's HS2 and the Network Rail Stations. In doing so, the OSD aims to have positive long-term impacts in a number of areas including: Increasing the housing supply, including affordable homes; offering more and better parks and open spaces; improving the connections between surrounding streets and neighbourhoods; creating new jobs; reducing noise and pollution; and creating new amenities, community, leisure and entertainment facilities. CrossRail 2 is envisioned as a contemporary transport hub that will connect the stations in the North-East and South-West of Greater London. Lastly, the re-development of the existing Network Rail station will increase the capacity of the station to get passengers to where they need to be more effectively and efficiently.

Numerous parties are involved in Euston's redevelopment. Back in 2012 - which, according to Camden Council marked the start of the planning of the regeneration project - Camden set up the 'Euston Strategic Board' and 'Management Board' to bring together key stakeholders in the regeneration of Euston – Camden, GLA, TfL, Network Rail and HS2 along with Crossrail 2 and The Department for Transport. As part of their mandate, these bodies were to ensure that the redevelopment of Euston would go beyond a purely national infrastructure project but as a project that could unlock benefits to the regeneration of Euston as a neighbourhood.

In 2020, the **Euston Partnership** was established with the sponsorship of the Department for Transport, in order to enable a better governance system that would act as a single gateway for overseeing all works in Euston. The Partnership consists of members from High Speed 2 Limited, the Department for Transport, Camden Borough, Lendlease, Transport for London, the Greater London Authority and Network Rail. The Euston Partnership aims to drive a singular focus on Euston, and achieve the benefits of integration across the three capital projects on the site via improved decision making, effective collaboration and risk management.

Lendlease was appointed 'Master Development Partner' (MDP) by the Secretary of State for Transport and Network Rail in 2018. At time of writing, the **masterplan is in development, and there is currently little information available about the specifics of the OSD**. Lendlease is responsible for the planning and building of everything above the HS2 and Network Rail stations. The site is almost 60 acres, encompassing where the current station sits all the way down to Euston Road to the South, until Eversholt Street to the East, areas of streets and buildings to the West, and all of the exposed rail track network to the North of the station up until the Parkway Road. This will include new offices, homes, cafés, shops, community, leisure and entertainment facilities, and new public spaces including squares and green space. Whilst they are not actually building the stations themselves, they are working closely with HS2 who are responsible for delivering the new HS2 tracks and station. In their role as Master Development Partner, Lendlease are working with the Department for Transport, Network Rail, Camden, HS2, the Greater London Authority, Transport for London, and the local communities to set out how Euston will be transformed. The current earliest estimate of when the Over Station Development construction phase can commence is **between 2026 and 2028, with the current estimate of first HS2 trains between 2029- 2033**.

| Overall challenge and Innovation Missions in T-Factor

Within T-Factor, the overall challenge addressed by the Euston pilot is '**leveraging temporary uses to demonstrate and bring forward the benefits of inclusive, equitable and regenerative development**'. Despite its central location, parts of Euston are some of the most disadvantaged areas within the London Borough of Camden. The arrival of HS2 and the vast changes to this already challenging situation have further impacted on the lives of those living and working in the area, and this will continue for another thirty years. Within this context, the key challenge for the Euston Pilot is to look at temporary

uses as a way to demonstrate the possibilities, and explore the potential, to bring forward the benefits of the development to those who already live and work in the area. The intention is to eventually contribute to the wider masterplanning and policy-making for these areas, towards inclusivity, equality and regenerative practices that improve quality of life in the short to medium term.

Key to this challenge is the recognition of the complex web of community organisations and residents' groups who are active on site to alleviate the existing issues, with a rich capital of knowledge and practices developed over the years, as well as with close contacts and relationships with people and communities who are mostly being impacted by such issues. Similarly, this challenge acknowledges a certain 'consultation fatigue' that has been permeating the site and the redevelopment, where residents are often asked similar questions by different consultation groups and experts, and yet their answers may remain substantially unheard, thus exacerbating feelings of frustration and mistrust towards the regeneration project.

The meanwhile strategy for the pilot is thus understood as the opportunity for *better weaving and infrastructuring existing engagement and consultation processes*, developing spaces (including physical meanwhile spaces), tools and methods that can support collaborative and reciprocal engagement, and in turn contribute to build trust between the residents and regeneration stakeholders. Besides, it aims at developing widespread opportunities of empowerment and capacity-building for individuals and organisations at Euston that can contribute to their adaptation and resilience to ongoing and future transformations of the area. Lastly, temporary uses are seen as ways to address pressing issues experienced by the local communities such as safety and loss of public spaces, exploring new uses that also foster better synergies and cross-connections amongst the plethora of (meanwhile and more permanent) initiatives already present in Euston.

Four innovation missions contextualise and set the ground for the meanwhile strategy of the Euston pilot in T-Factor:

Mission 1: Arts, Culture & Heritage: This mission aims to support art, architecture and public realm improvements that stimulate creative expression, foster identity, and make Euston's culture, community, heritage and history accessible to all, visible in the streets, and contributing to add beauty to them in the process.

Mission 2: Collaborative & Circular Economy & Enterprise: This mission aims to foster an inclusive and regenerative economy in and around Euston, including providing active support for local residents, especially young people, to start up new (social) businesses. This includes promoting and investing in local markets, new and existing, to activate the public realm, increase footfall and support and promote local business activity.

Mission 3: Growing & Greening: This mission aims to deliver networked, accessible and ambitious green and open spaces in the Euston area. With many green spaces lost to development and the future densification of the area, it is crucial that green and open spaces of many scales are available to those that live and work in the area. It is important to promote and prioritise community 'ownership' of spaces, and involvement in their ongoing transformation, supervision and maintenance.

Mission 4: Safe & Convivial Streets and Spaces: This mission aims to ensure that streets and spaces are clean, welcoming and safe, and designed to reduce crime and anti-social behaviour whilst connecting cultural and community activities. It also aims at ensuring that streets and spaces are adequately maintained and cared for by council and community.

EUSTON LONDON THEORY OF CHANGE

How can we leverage temporary uses to demonstrate and bring forward the benefits of inclusive, equitable and regenerative development

- #PROMPT USES:** one off events that attract people in places
- #REGULAR USES:** regular activities that retain people in places
- #STABLE USES:** temporary uses that anchor people to places
- #COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE**
- #INVESTMENT & FUNDING**
- #SMART PLANNING, POLICY & REGULATION**

Missions (if we)

Mission 1: Arts, Culture and Heritage

Mission 2: Collaborative and Circular economy and enterprise

Mission 3: Growing and greening

Mission 4: Safe and convivial street and spaces

Figure 14: Theory of Change – London Euston

| Meanwhile portfolio

Through local and resident-led projects, the Euston portfolio aims to develop a diverse and wide-ranging meanwhile strategy that is aligned with existing local resources and priorities (governing bodies, community groups, academic institutions, etc.). The four missions laid out for the pilot are connected through several prompt and regular activities.

Firstly, participatory arts and design practices will be used to stimulate cultural expression and celebrate local heritage (mission 1: arts, culture, and heritage). As a main temporary use, this mission shall explore the creation of a **3D Digital Archive** as a live resource constructed with diverse local community groups using digital tools, so as to provide opportunities for the community to record and valorise their cultural heritage, acquire new skills and open their historical sites and artefacts to wider audiences.

Within Mission 2 ‘Collaborative and Circular Economy & Enterprise’, workshops, events, enterprise programs and collaborative platforms will try to stimulate circular and collaborative strategies within local neighbourhoods and Chalton Street Market. The main temporary use that supports this mission is the co-creation of a **Circular Market Enterprise Hub on Chalton Street**.

To attain Mission 3 ‘Greening and growing’, local strategies will be devised to connect existing and create new and accessible open and green spaces.

Lastly, the improvement of places and streets in need of care and maintenance will contribute to increase community safety, facilitated by community events to share experiences (Mission 4: safe and convivial streets and spaces). Within this mission, the main temporary use envisaged is a **Story Trail** that shall provide a walking route connecting green spaces and supporting wayfindings across Regents Park Estate to Regents Park. The Story Trail shall also promote local cultural identities and histories by sharing stories via physical and digital ‘touchpoints’ along the route. Story Trail ‘touchpoints’ may also act as ‘help points’ and ‘information points’ providing residents with information on local public amenities and activities, public events, and updates on development activities.

The meanwhile activities shall promote resident leadership through learning recognition (i) and tailored support (ii). The first initiative gives meanwhile leaders the opportunity to support their activities with learning recognition which is provided in two forms. Either in the form of an extended project qualification which provides residents with 20 hours of project support from CSM-UAL CoP and 20 hours study support leading to a formally recognised level 3 accreditation, or, through an experience-based learning framework (REBEL) which entitles leaders to a certification that is valued by local employers. Under the second initiative, resident meanwhile leaders/social activists may benefit from tailored support to remove barriers that prevent them from participating in meanwhile uses/social action. Tailored support may consist of childcare, necessary equipment, payment, or training.

<https://miro.com/app/board/uxjVORBP8QI/>

| Portfolio delivery: overview

In the time frame considered for the mid-term evaluation of T-Factor^[14], the Euston pilot has designed and organised nine activities of the portfolio:

1) Workshops in Regents Park, (2) Community voices workshop, (3) Cumberland Fun Fest, (4) Unveiling the Euston canvas hoardings/artwork, (5) Everton Mews/Prince of Wales passage, (6) Somers Town Future Neighbourhood Workshop, (7) Regents Park Estate Community Festival, (8) Story trail, (9) Meeting between the Meanwhile Use Working Group and the Community Champions.

Workshops in Regents Park consisted of a series of participatory workshops organised between January and March 2022. They were delivered in close collaboration with Regents Park Community Champions, a group of residents concerned with the health and wellbeing of people that live in Regents Park Estate, a housing estate that borders the Euston development site. The objective was to design and deliver a series of structured activities that could help define and scope out **challenges and opportunities that residents experience and perceive in Euston**, and that they would like to address through meanwhile projects. The activity went through the following stages over a three month period:

- Several iterations of mapping activities, supporting residents to identify locations to be celebrated and locations that have problems that need addressing within the Regents Park Estate. These mapping activities included drawing and plotting on maps of the area (2D) placing models and markers on large scale maps of the area (3D) and sharing these sites on google maps so that they can be added to and iterated over time (digital). These mapping activities were delivered as part of regular 'social events' that the Champions host for the residents of Regents Park Estate.
- A 'wellbeing walk' with residents, council officers and development stakeholders, which entailed walking the estate together and identifying 'sites of significance' - i.e., places that residents feel are significantly linked to stories, histories, and places, and that would deserve (re)appreciation and improvement.

- An 'idea workshop' where residents and development stakeholders identified the challenges, opportunities and possible interventions to be undertaken in the area. To create the workshop materials for this event the T-Factor team synthesised the findings of consultation delivered by multiple agencies across the development area over the last five years and helped residents to 'join the dots' between the results of past consultation and current meanwhile proposals. This is significant in the local context as citizens can see how the results of past consultations are informing the current work - rather than repeating the same 'extractive' questioning that has led to consultation fatigue amongst some residents in the area.
- A voting workshop where residents selected the most popular project ideas.
- A timeline workshop where residents planned the timelines for delivering the projects prioritised for address.

Similarly to the Regents Park Workshops, the **Community Voices workshop** involved the **Community Organisers in Somers Town** in a collaborative process of identification and discussion of the challenges experienced in the area, the desirable futures imagined by the participants, the missions that would help unlock such futures, and the meanwhile projects that would substantiate the defined missions. As for the previous activity, workshop materials synthesised the findings of consultation processes over the last 5 years. Furthermore, the contributions of Community organiser participants were informed by the results of recent survey work they had been doing in the neighbourhood.

The **Cumberland Fun Fest** was a community festival organised in June 2022, led by the **Community Champions** and delivered in Cumberland Market at the centre of Regents Park Estate. The Festival included art and crafts spots, music and dance stages and food. During the Festival, The Community Champions and the T-Factor (UAL) team hosted story gathering activities, propaedeutic to the creation of the Story Trail.

^[14] Generally, the period considered in this report is February 2022 - October 2022, which is the overall time frame in which the T-Factor Pilots started to implement and run their temporary use strategies. However, it should be noted that the insights and results (especially more qualitative results) captured in this report also refer to the preceding period (the whole 2021), particularly when it comes to preliminary activities of engagement, initial scoping and co-design that started to set the ground for implementing and iterating temporary uses and activities.

Unveiling the Euston canvas hoardings/artwork convened young people across Euston and Regent's Park Estate that worked together with artists in order to create two murals which have been put on two hoardings of the Euston/HS2 development. The project was initiated and facilitated by MA Service Design students from London College of Communication working with the T-Factor team from the University of the Arts London. The young people involved contributed to the artworks through a series of workshops coordinated by Fitzrovia Youth in Action association. The hoardings were installed by MACE Dragados, the lead constructor for the HS2 development. The unveiling of the hoardings was part of a wider set of engagement activities promoted by the Euston Partnership. The project was an action research into what is required to support local residents to be able to make use of meanwhile opportunities, in this case the Euston hoardings. Learnings from this process are now feeding into the establishment of a process for inclusive and equitable access to hoardings around the Euston development.

Everton Mews/Prince of Wales passage - gateway to estate was a public engagement event held in July 2022 in Prince of Wales Passage/Everton Mews (PoWP/EM), which is a site particularly renowned for fly-tipping and anti-social behaviour. Since the commencement of works around Euston, the placement of hoardings and barriers has meant that Prince of Wales passage has become a more significant pedestrian access route into Regent's Park Estate. This has led residents to propose the 'Gateway to the Estate' project, which will transform PoWP/EM into a welcoming gateway for pedestrian access to the estate. The event ran for half a day and was delivered by the **Community Champions** in collaboration with the T-Factor (UAL) team. Residents and passers-by were asked to write their ideas around prompts such as '*What would make the space more welcoming?*' and '*What could make this space cleaner and greener?*', writing their ideas on a mirror displayed behind a door, which were then added to an 'ideas forest' behind another door. Other activities and games were set up down the street with residents invited to draw their ideas for the future of the space on images of the site. The activity served to activate the site and **gathered 60 ideas from residents and passers-by** about how to make the site 'greener, cleaner and more welcoming'. These ideas have been used to inform proposals for improvements to the site,

including wall art and lighting, that will be prototyped with support from the UAL T Factor team and regeneration stakeholders.

Somers Town Future Neighbourhood Workshop was a workshop organised in July 2022 in close collaboration between Somers Town Community Association, Camden Council and the T-Factor team of UAL. The workshop was part of the project led by Somers Town Community Association, dedicated to prototype solutions in address to climate resilience at neighbourhood level, funded by the Greater London Authority via the Future Neighbourhood Programme. This funding provides capital funding that can complement T-Factor operational funding for meanwhile projects. Through the workshop, opportunities and roots for synergies and alignment between T-Factor and Future Neighbourhood projects were explored, and a synthesis of workshop materials produced.

Photo Credits:
University of
the Arts
London

The **Regents Park Estate Community Festival** provided the opportunity for the Euston pilot, alongside the Community Champions and **Old Diorama Arts Centre**, to progress the creation of the Story Trail. During the festival, stories were collected through the spontaneous contribution of participants and visitors who visited the Story Line stall and added their stories. Furthermore, residents participated in the creation of a clay tree. The clay tree was built beneath the branches of a 300 year old London Plane tree that sits at the centre of **Clarence Gardens**. Residents call this old tree the 'Story Tree' because of the stories they imagine it could tell of all the events that it has witnessed over hundreds of years. The Story Tree has been identified as a key location within the Story Trail. The 2-metre-high clay tree that was built beneath the real tree was an example of the kind of 3-dimensional installation that could be implemented as part of the Story Trail. The festival was staged across the estate in Triton Square, Clarence Gardens and Cumberland Market. The Story Trail prototype provided wayfinding between the sites and shared stories about the locations.

Clay Tree with story characters under the 300 year old Story Tree in Clarence Gardens, Photo Credits: UAL

Installation of the story trail. As part of the Regents Park Estate Community Festival in August 2022, a 'Story Trail' (ST) prototype was tested. The ST drew upon historical stories about the area to create **eight freestanding boards with photographs, text and QR codes to harvest feedback**. The boards were placed at strategic points between Triton Square and Cumberland Market to support wayfinding for the Community Festival and gauge resident interest in the Story Trail. The boards were removed after the festival. However, Camden Council Green Space team received **positive feedback and thus granted permission to re-install the Story Trail boards**. The boards were re-installed two weeks later and remained **in place for 2 months**, until November 2022. The ST has been welcomed by residents and, to the surprise of the Council, **has not been damaged or defaced in any way**. The historical stories have inspired further interventions including an illuminated market that is to be held in December 2022 in Clarence Gardens - inspired by the fact that the site was designed as a market square in the 1800's.

Story Trail Prototypes installed as wayfinding for Regents Park Community Festival (Festival of Stories), Photo Credits, UAL

The text on the promotional material produced by the Community Champions reads "Did you know Clarence Gardens used to be Clarence Market? We are organising a small outdoor event 2nd December and looking to involve local residents being able to sell their business/items as part of a small pop up market after our successful stalls at Regent's Park Community Festival. We welcome youth or community members to run activities or sell items. The event is part of the development of the Story Trail across the estate developing over the next year. It is also part of a campaign to light up areas of the estate or enable people to feel safer travelling and to connect the community with local support services, especially with the existing cost of living, winter isolation and lower wellbeing in mind".

Lastly, we shall mention the **Meetings with the Meanwhile Use Working Group (MUWG)**, a group responsible for the management of the Euston meanwhile, and part of the Place & Social Value panel convened through the Euston Partnership. Since the early stages of T-Factor, the Local Coalition has been seeking collaboration with the MUWG, so as to be better able to grasp existing and emerging opportunities for meanwhile intervention. In 2022, the meetings with the Group have become more oriented towards seeking specific support, especially for the meanwhile activities developed by, or in close collaboration with the Community Champions. In preparation for this meeting, the Local Coalition delivered some workshops with the Champions to refine the proposals, which were finally well received. The MUWG will now find ways to support the implementation of the proposals.

For more information: www.communitychampionscamden.co.uk

Twitter and Instagram icons followed by @COMCHAMPCAMDEN IF YOU HAVE ANY QUESTIONS CONTACT ELLIE.RUDD@FYA.ORG.UK 07923849277

Flyer for Illumination Market event inspired by local heritage research linked to 'Story Gathering' and 'Story Trail' activities, Credits, Regent's Park Community Champions

| Stakeholders and Beneficiaries

Through the activities implemented so far, the Euston coalition managed to approach and engage with a variety of stakeholders and collaborators.

Coherently with the meanwhile strategy defined by the Local Coalition, a lot of emphasis was dedicated to the involvement of **local charities, informal groups and associations already active in and around Euston**. Indeed, many of them are already part of the relational capital of the UNiversity of the Arts London, as collaborations are in place since years and have evolved over time through increasingly shared ambitions and objectives of inclusive placemaking. Amongst the stakeholders and collaborators, **Somers Town Community Association, the Community Champions, Fitzrovia Youth in Action, the UAL/CSM Community of Practice** and of course **Camden Council and Lendlease** are the organisations and groups who have been mostly and repeatedly involved across the activities developed over time. From activity to activity, a second tier of organisations and actors have been approached and engaged, such as **cultural, community and faith organisations**, generally with the overall goal of leveraging their own social capital and knowledge of the area to reach out to communities and groups that the Local Coalition would have hardly reached alone. Furthermore, the relationship with the **Meanwhile Use Working Group** has been increasingly important over time, as this group may not only be a gateway to meanwhile spaces and opportunities in the coming period, but also an important vehicle of concrete and meaningful legacy when T-Factor will be over. It is also worth mentioning the collaboration of the Euston Pilot with the **Knowledge Quarter**, the knowledge district that gathers together a large number of organisations of different types and sizes. The collaboration with the KQ is deemed particularly important for the full delivery of the Portfolio, especially in the possibility to create meaningful collaborations with businesses that address economic issues in Euston. However, at the time of writing the report, the collaboration still has to materialise in more concrete activities and proposals.

When it comes to the activities' beneficiaries, the pilot has managed to address a **large variety of groups, often with a priority on vulnerable residents in Euston**. All of the activities delivered in Regents Park Estate aim to improve the quality of life for people that live in the estate. Across the various activities delivered in Regents Park Estate participants have been representative of the wider population of the area. Groups such as **young people, children** (of whom 44.6% are living in poverty and 47.8% are on the children's social care system), **low income families** (87.3% of whom are receiving tax credits), **older people** (of whom 42.9% are living in deprivation and 3 out of 5 are in the top 10% in Londond for probability of loneliness), **economically inactive people** (43.2% of working age people are economically inactive and 12% are receiving ESA or incapacity benefit), **ethnic groups** (6.2% cannot speak English) have been directly involved.

Activity 1: Workshops in Regents Park

Target groups: residents or
the Regents Park Estate

Collaborators: Community
Champions, Community
of Practice and
Camden Council

Keywords:
#Local Identity & Heritage, #Inclusion
& Equal Opportunities,
#Physical & Mental Health, #Safety &
Security
Cohesion & Social Justice

Prompt use

24/01/2022
23/02/2022
30/03/2022

Actual beneficiaries:

70 residents

Activity 2: Community voices workshop

Target groups: Residents of
Somers Town

Collaborators:
Community Champions
and Somers town
community association

Keywords:
#Efficient use of resources,
#Cohesion
& Social Justice

Prompt use

24/03/2022

Actual beneficiaries:

350 residents (based on
a distributed survey)

Activity 4: Unveiling the Euston canvas hoardings/artwork**Prompt use****25/06/2022**

Target groups: young people across Euston and Regent's Park Estate

Main beneficiaries:

20 young persons

Collaborators: MA Service Design, Fitzrovia Youth in action, Camden council and two construction companies

Keywords:

#Local Identity & Heritage,
#Inclusion & Equal Opportunities,
#Creativity & Talent,
#Physical & Mental Health

Activity 5: Everton Mews/Prince of Wales passage - gateway to estate event**Prompt use****15/07/2022**

Target groups: Local residents

Main beneficiaries:

40 residents

Collaborators: Community Champions, Community of Practice and Surma Community Centre

Keywords:

#Safety & Security, #Solidarity & Belonging, #Cohesion & Social Justice, #Physical & Mental Health, #Well-maintained, user friendly public spaces

Activity 6: Somers Town Future Neighbourhood Workshop**Prompt use****14/07/2022**

Target groups: Somers Town residents and stakeholders

Main beneficiaries:

40 residents

Collaborators: Camden Council, Somers Town Community Association and Greater London Authority

Keywords:

#Creativity & Talent, #Physical & Mental Health,
#Efficient use of resources,
#Inclusion & Equal Opportunities, #Circular value chain

Activity 7: Regents Park Estate Community Festival**Prompt use****06/08/2022**

Target groups:
residents or the
Regents Park Estate

Main beneficiaries:

200 residents and passers-by

Collaborators: Community
Champions and Old Diorama Arts
Centre

Keywords:
#Creativity & Talent,
#Cohesion & Social Justice,
#Inclusion & Equal
Opportunities

Activity 8: Installation of story trail**Prompt use****06/08/2022
14/11/2022**

Target groups:
Local residents

Main beneficiaries:

200 residents and passers-by

Collaborators: Camden
and Council and
Community Champions

Keywords:
#Local Identity & Heritage,
#Creativity & Talent,
#Physical & Mental Health,
#Well-maintained, user friendly
public spaces,
#Cohesion & Social Justice

Activity 9: Meeting between meanwhile working group and the community champions**Prompt use****21/09/2022**

Target groups: The main
beneficiaries were the
community champions who
presented the proposals to
MUWG

Main beneficiaries:

**Community
champions
and 4 private
organisations**

Collaborators: MUWG, Old
Diorama Arts Centre and Camden
Council

Keywords:
Physical & Mental Health

| Contribution to impact at mission level - Main activities' results

In the paragraphs that follow, we provide an overview of the main results achieved through the activities described earlier, mainly extracted from online surveys addressed to the beneficiaries involved, observation templates and informal interviews.

Enhanced perceptions of the area that acknowledge and valorise local identity and historical narratives

Through the 'Workshops in Regents Park', the residents experienced a collective desire to improve the safety of the area, something that they hadn't necessarily felt before and that happened through the opportunity of entering into a temporary partnership with local organisations and government. Furthermore, the participants indicated that the collective walk in Regents Park had a positive influence on their **perceptions of safety and conviviality of the site**. Walking together through the neighbourhood, identifying challenges and proposing solutions enabled a collective and positive occupation of public streets and spaces within the site, **fostering a sense of ownership and guardianship** amongst participants. Such activities align with the strategies of Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design which aim to *"reduce victimisation, deter offender decisions that precede criminal acts, and build a sense of community among inhabitants so they can gain territorial control of areas, reduce crime, and minimise fear of crime"* [15]. Similarly, the 'Unveiling the Euston canvas hoardings/artwork' also demonstrated positive contribution to **local identity and social and cultural significance of places**. The participants reported that the experience had a positive influence on their ability to contribute to the visibility and value of local identities within the development area. Furthermore, the 'installation of the Story Trail' contributed to **build trust between place managers and the community regarding appreciation of creative interventions in the public realm**. Many participants were positively surprised to discover that there had been no damage done to the Story Trail boards that were installed for several weeks. Residents have demonstrated interest in extending the Story Trail through additional boards. Lastly, the community champions and the Euston pilot hosted story gathering activities including a story timeline and recorded conversations with residents at the 'Cumberland Fun Fest', which gathered more than 30 stories for use in the Story Trail. This willingness to share personal narratives about the area demonstrates the **desire of residents to have a say in communicating the identity of their neighbourhood**.

Enhanced and more equitable opportunities to access arts and culture and to express in a creative manner

The Euston pilot has co-organised multiple activities aimed at providing enhanced and more equitable access to arts or culture:

- During the 'Workshops in Regents Park', the Community Champions and residents expressed their ideas for the estate's improvement, through creative and collaborative approaches to exploration and ideation.
- Through the 'Unveiling of the Euston canvas hoardings/artwork', young people across Euston and Regents Park Estate came together with artists to create two murals which have been put on two hoardings of the Euston/HS2 development. The young residents that were involved in the art creation reported that they highly enjoyed the activity and that they would like to participate more in similar activities in the future.
- The 'Everton Mews/Prince of Wales passage - gateway to estate event' was a success in terms of giving participants the chance to get in contact with design, agency, and social actions contributing to 60 ideas for improving the site. Participants responded that they would come back if the event would be organised again and that they are open to engage with initiatives that improve the neighbourhood.
- Lastly, when asking participants at the Regents Park Estate Community Festival, the respondent stated that it felt like there was a sense of community and intimacy due to the chance to get together and do something out of the ordinary.

[15] <https://www.cpted.net>

Empowered to collaborate in the community through inclusivity

The evaluation of the 'Cumberland fun fest' reported on positive results around participants' willingness and capacity to collaborate with each other for neighbourhood improvement. Many older residents and residents that were not born in the UK were sharing stories, which are both groups that are often unheard. Furthermore, young people involved in 'Unveiling the Euston canvas hoardings/artwork' have reported feelings and perceptions of **enhanced empowerment to deliver placemaking interventions**. The Euston Meanwhile Use Working Group is seeking ways to ensure that young residents and community groups will have opportunities to contribute to hoardings in future, with the aim of continuously expanding bottom-up engagement and empowerment in collaboration, and enhance creativity of young people, a group that is also not often heard in the area.

The 'Somers Town Future Neighbourhood Workshop' engaged with multiple, vulnerable groups. As previously mentioned, groups that are often 'forgotten' are older residents and residents who do not speak English. The latter group often needs a person to translate for them, which was observed to be the case at the workshop. Many participants who did not speak English brought friends who could translate the workshop. Another group consisted of women from the British-Bangladeshi community. They were generally satisfied of the workshop and actively shared their concerns and ideas.

Regarding 'Everton Mews/Prince of Wales passage - gateway to estate event', this also proved to be highly beneficial around sense of agency and empowerment through inclusive placemaking. Many respondents highlighted that previously, this residential area did not have an identity. The Community Champions and allied organisations were able to bring the concerns of the residents to the forefront, and there was interest in improving the mews/passage, especially making an intervention in the 'gateway' area that is currently a site of fly-tipping and anti-social behaviour. Lastly, when asking participants at the 'Regents Park Estate Community Festival', the respondents stated that the event was a nice thing to take place in such a compact neighbourhood. It was well managed and organised, and showed what can be done to engage people in creative ways.

Engagement with collaborative and circular economy practices and initiatives

When it comes to new collaborative and circular economy initiatives, the 'Somers Town Future Neighbourhood Workshop' valorised and elaborated activities proposed within the Portfolio, linked to Mission 2 (Circular and Collaborative Economy and Enterprise). Through the workshop T Factor proposals were aligned with those of the Greater London Authority funded Future Neighbourhoods project. This alignment allows resources and efforts to be combined towards collective delivery of the following activities:

- A meanwhile circular economy market enterprise hub to be located in Chalton Street to support new traders seeking to implement circular strategies.
- Meanwhile storage for community market stalls and equipment available for use by local residents to enable them to 'have a go' at trading on Chalton Street market. Residents can use the community stalls free of charge up to three times, after which those that wish to continue will be supported to register with the Camden markets team as independent market traders.
- Meanwhile storage and brokering support for products made by residents from reclaimed materials. Residents that make products from reclaimed materials will be supported to supply their goods to traders who will sell them on Chalton Street market.
- 'Give and take' day for Somers Town, where residents can 'give away' unwanted homewares on the street. This proposal is also inspired by Barcelona's 'junk day', a case study proposed by T-Lab 5 'Circular and Collaborative Economy' as part of its own support to the Euston pilot.

Increased motivation and desire to engage in interventions that enhance safety and security

Initiatives such as the 'Workshops in Regents Park' have been observed to influence participants' motivation to improve safety in the area. These workshops, supported by the Community Champions, gave residents the chance to share their concerns about the area, and propose ideas for public realm improvements. These ideas will contribute to the 'Story Trail' that foregrounds local history and identity whilst improving the public realm and creating safe routes across the estate. Furthermore, the Champions have been curating groups' work to take ideas forward and seek resources for their implementation. These activities demonstrated residents' desire to engage to improve the safety of the neighbourhood, leading to the introduction of a '**Community Guardians' programme** funded by Camden Council and supported by the Council Community safety team and the Community Champions. The Euston pilot made the council officers responsible for the programme aware of the Community Champions concerns and commitment for improving the safety of the estate. As a result, the Council Community Safety team contacted the Community Champions and **20 Community champions** have signed up to the Community Guardians programme and are receiving training and support to implement community safety projects.

Sustainable and mutually beneficial relationships

There were multiple initiatives and actions that could turn into sustainable relationships among stakeholders and beneficiaries, such as:

- The 'Workshops in Regents Park' have brought members of the Euston pilot and Community of Practice into collaboration with Community Champions and residents, which have contributed to the co-development of future projects and introduction to other stakeholder groups e.g., Euston development and construction partners through the Meanwhile Use Working Group that T-Factor has introduced them to.
- The 'Cumberland fun fest' collaboration demonstrated that the Euston pilot, Fitzrovia Youth in Action, Old Diorama and Community Champions and Euston Partners and Council could collaborate successfully to deliver events and collect stories. The event demonstrated capacity for further successful partnerships such as the Everton Mews event and Community Festival that followed later in the summer.
- The co-creation of artworks and their unveiling added to the relationship by prototyping a process for inclusive and equitable access to hoardings that is now informing access to meanwhile processes developed and delivered by the Euston Meanwhile Use Working Group.
- To create and deliver in 'The Somers Town Future Neighbourhood Workshop', the workshop members of the Euston pilot collaborated with Council and Community Organisations responsible for the development and delivery of the GLA Funded Future Neighbourhoods Programme which runs until 2025. The workshop brought the T-Factor programme into alignment with the Future Neighbourhoods programme and supported the development of sustainable relationships between the delivery organisations.
- The 'installation of the story trail' has brought together members of the Euston pilot, Community of Practice, Community Champions and residents and have contributed to the development of future projects and introduction to other stakeholder groups e.g., Future ambitions for Story Trail.

| Contribution to impact at Pilot level

The section describes the pilot level changes and considerations gathered through the 'Critical Friend' interview. As anticipated, the interview is aimed at exploring if and how the activities undertaken during the period of reference are contributing towards long term outcomes and impacts of urban regeneration, particularly from the point of view of enhanced strategic, operational and relational dimensions (ref. Methodology section). In the following paragraph we report on the main strengths and weaknesses that emerged through the interview. A self-assessment scoreboard filled out by the Local Coalition is provided at the end of the section. It is important to highlight that the insights and reflections reported in this chapter do not only capture the voice and perceptions of the Local Coalition; they also include and integrate the results of the ongoing observation and support developed by the Transformation Agency over time, in its role of 'critical friend' of the pilot.

The redevelopment of Euston will be one of the largest redevelopment projects to take place in London in the coming decades, adding another chapter to a long series of large-scale and long-term urban transformations that, throughout the history of the city's development, have often changed entire districts and skylines radically. Indeed, the T-Factor pilot in Euston **cannot be understood without considering the much broader, complex and often contradictory path of development in contemporary's London**. Over decades, major requalification projects such as King's Cross, the Olympics site, Elephant & Castle, South Bermondsey - amongst many others - have amply demonstrated the city's ability to attract investment at scale and scope, leveraging infrastructure-led regeneration to unleash a variety of benefits in multiple domains. Yet, London has also often been at the forefront of

dynamics of real estate financialisation and market speculation which have then been observed in other major European cities. Increasingly in time, the topic of 'inclusive growth' has got high on the agenda of local authorities, and developers are (claiming to) making efforts to include communities in their regeneration plans, ensuring that opportunities are created for those who already live in and around the development areas. However, **how inclusive and effective these efforts are is still contested, and the ongoing trend in property prices means that the spectre of gentrification is always present, with arguments around what can be considered affordable in terms of rental and purchase prices**. Moreover, when it comes to the 'meanwhile' and meanwhile interventions, London has largely been a pioneer of these practices, and yet 'the meanwhile' often stands as a topic and field of action surrounded by contradictory imaginaries, perceptions and feelings, where perceived risks of gentrification associated to 'regeneration' and 'redevelopment' often extend to terms such as 'meanwhile' and 'activation', with concerns and fears of losing access to spaces.

Within this context, the meanwhile strategy of the pilot attempted from the very beginning to position itself as a **platform for hosting and convening already ongoing efforts of bottom-up activation and engagement**, contributing to strengthen existing efforts by means of enhanced synergies and cross-collaborations across the plethora of local charities, informal groups and residents' associations active on site.

Meanwhile interventions are primarily understood as ways to create **trust and dialogue** between the local communities and regeneration stakeholders, making **engagement and consultation efforts more coordinated and reciprocal while enhancing opportunities to influence the redevelopment's plans**. Vis-à-vis a redevelopment which will run for nearly thirty years and that is already creating disruptions, meanwhile projects offer the chance to address short term issues such as loss of public green and open spaces, while creating capacity-building and skills that support adaptation and resilience towards the long run. Overall, the

pilot's strategy works to enhance the liveability of the site, voicing the interests, needs, and priorities of the existing communities while simultaneously boosting the sociocultural and economic attributes of the area. In doing so, the pilot has adopted a **citizen-led approach** that is at the core of its meanwhile strategy.

“The local challenges are related to the future development of the area. The development is connected to the citizens and residents and their issues, we are bridging this aspect by putting the needs of residents first and creating a dialogue and opportunities for long-term development through T-Factor” (Local Coalition).

The Local Coalition has dedicated considerable effort to the deep exploration of the local context and the complex web of actors and agendas present at Euston. The engagement process has **actively involved a variety of communities** in a collective inquiry of challenges and aspirations for the future of Euston, and the Local Coalition has been quite **successful in establishing growing, collaborative relationships**. On the other hand, the ongoing dialogue and collaboration with Camden Council and Lendlease were often key in seizing and capturing early opportunities for intervention, as well as for checking rooms and viability for meanwhile activities early in time.

What emerges as particularly valuable is the strategic approach of the Local Coalition to act as much as possible within the existing landscape of engagement initiatives, contributing to their **strategic infrastructuring** as a broader yet connected portfolio of locally-rooted meanwhile experiments - while mitigating the risks of cold start engagement. In addition, the pilot invested considerable effort in harvesting and synthesising the insights emerging from the past 5 years of consultation, as a way to address coordination gaps and **mitigate consultation fatigue**. Overall, the activities implemented so far and the participatory approach allowed the pilot to ground the missions on residents' wishes and wants, unveiling qualities, attributes and values around (the present and future of) spaces that can give direction and meaning to temporary projects in Euston. Moreover, the strong

networking and continuous engagement efforts **are contributing to make T-Factor present and visible on site**.

As a main result of this approach, the Local Coalition reports on an emerging, **increasing alignment between local agendas and priorities, and possibly a better use of competencies, capacities and resources** that are present in the relational ecosystem of the pilot. As a concrete evidence of this result, the Local Coalition managed to convene some of the engaged actors around **new proposals and applications** for local funding meant to enrich and expand the portfolio, with three different funding streams already activated successfully (in addition to the T-Factor's funding), including:

- An application to Keep Britain Tidy fund for £912 to prototype public realm improvements to Everton Mews/Prince of Wales Passage (Gateway to Estate) - led by RPE Community Champions
- An application to HS2 for £150,000 to implement the Story Trail - led by RPE Community Champions
- An application for £45,000 to the Greater London Authority (GLA) funded Future Neighbourhood 2030 programme (Phase 2) to support implementation of Mission 2 T Factor prototypes (Circular Market Enterprise Office and Give and Take days) linked to FN 2030 Chalton Street Circular Economy Market. The GLA funding requires 40% match funding and part of the T Factor EU funding allocated to Mission 2 Pilot delivery is being leveraged as part of this match funding.
- An application for £29,000 to the Greater London Authority (GLA) funded Future Neighbourhood 2030 programme (Phase 2) to support prototyping of Learning Recognition for Social Action.

“The main achievement of the period is that we have integrated the goals and ambitions of local partners, in both Regents Park Estate and Somers Town, with the missions of the T-Factor. We're making shared funding applications aligned with the missions” (Local Coalition).

A critical point in the strategic and relational ecosystem of the pilot emerges around the Community of Practice (CoP), a group of artists and designers from Central Saint Martins College of Arts and Design, and

actors from Knowledge Quarter organisations, interested or involved in publicly engaged practices. The Local Coalition points out that the relationship with the CoP has worked well in bringing capacity to the co-design and realisation of the portfolio. However, **the pilot faces some blockages in terms of broadening the CoP**. The Local Coalition highlights instances raised where the engagement with partners is not strong enough due to a lack of clear propositions for involvement. For example, the Euston area lies within the catchment area of the **Knowledge Quarter**, a large network including organisations of all sizes and types, including academic, cultural, research, scientific and media organisations. The collaboration and potential of KQ participation in the project is yet to be realised. Moving forward, one of the needs highlighted by the pilot is to define a concrete proposal for the Knowledge Quarter in order to broaden opportunities for meanwhile interventions.

Another area of positive results relates to cultural and creativity-led placemaking and capacity-building in this field. Especially within the scope of Mission 1 and 2 (respectively, 'Arts, Culture and Heritage' and 'Safe and Convivial Streets and Spaces'), the pilot has engaged with different types of creative practices that explored alternative use of spaces, particularly from the point of view of narratives and social-cultural significances, material and immaterial heritage. The evaluation of these activities often reported positive outcomes around **enhanced empowerment and capacities in co-creative placemaking processes**, as well as desire for more activities of this type. Participants saw the value and potential of the activities in transforming spaces, and often expressed interest and willingness to make the area safer through collective action.

It is also worth mentioning the ongoing efforts of the pilot to develop local capacities in novel ways, via a learning recognition program for social action. The Local Coalition is in the process of designing a level 3 (UK A level) qualification comprising a 10-week course for citizens who want to deliver social projects through a design-led approach. The projects developed through the course would be supported to apply for

funding linked to Future Neighbourhood themes and T-Factor Missions. The Local Coalition argues that empowering and building capacities of the local communities in the short term could eventually support them in mobilising rapidly in the future when meanwhile spaces and opportunities start to materialise in and around the site.

Glancing at the work streams for other missions, the pilot has initiated efforts for Mission 2 "Collaborative and Circular Economy" mainly by engaging stakeholders and by activating funding streams for the upcoming activities planned under this mission. However, **with regard to Mission 3 "Growing and Greening", the pilot still stands in a phase of detailed design**.

From a mainly operational perspective, the Local Coalition has been facing several challenges, many of them with direct implications in the strategic evolution of the portfolio. In the first instance, **access to space for meanwhile interventions has turned out to be a major issue**, often pushing the Local Coalition towards a **focus on public spaces and open air meanwhile activities**.

Another major challenge stems from the **difficulty in aligning the T-Factor timeline and requirements with the reality (and timing) of the redevelopment**. Participatory placemaking processes are based on a continuous relational work which typically takes time and energies; moreover, if we are to remain sensitive and open to new voices and perspectives over time, the shift from 'listening to proposition' can hardly follow a detailed and strict roadmap, as it requires flexible planning able to incorporate and embrace adjustments and modifications along the run. Nonetheless, the Local Coalition has tried to overcome this issue at best, particularly by means of **seeking ongoing coordination and synergies with the Euston Meanwhile Use Working group** to seize emerging opportunities and align efforts and timelines.

A similar operational challenge can be mentioned for **funding and spending**. The requirements of the T-Factor funding and its spending locally are often averse to the flexibility and quickness in action required

by temporary interventions, thus creating **limits in the real possibilities of experimentation and reciprocal engagement.**

In recent months the developer Lendlease has released their early stage plans for the Over Station Development. In the heart of the plans is a site described as a **Cultural Anchor**, considered necessary to ensure that people are 'drawn up' into the 'new piece of city' to be created. Towards the next period, the pilot recognised the opportunity to broaden its understanding and knowledge in contextualising the concept of Cultural Anchor within Euston in order to further support the local conversation around the development. Linked to this, the knowledge exchanges and learnings from La Friche in Marseille, one of the advanced cases of T-Factor, has inspired the pilot to further explore the potential to support capacity building in cultural production in the area, bringing together local arts and cultural organisations, such as Old Diorama Arts Centre, with pioneers such as La Friche, may contribute a long term legacy of the project. The pilot aspires to leverage the strength of its existing network; creative and cultural partnerships; and artistic and cultural interventions to explore the potential of, and for, a model similar to La Friche in Euston.

Pilot Self-assessment scoreboard

	Dimensions	1	2	3	4
STRATEGIC	Positioning & Reputation	The portfolio poorly contributes to enhancing the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is not properly valorised.	The portfolio partially contributes to the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is considered but not a driver in the cultural and social evolution of the area	The portfolio brings a great visibility to the area and raises awareness about its heritage	The portfolio has provided the area with a new identity and its heritage is appreciated by diverse audiences.
	Attractiveness	The portfolio is raising limited interest and struggles to attract diverse audiences and target groups.	The portfolio raises the interest of target groups and engages with an unvaried audience on a local level.	The portfolio is compelling for all target groups and attracts a diverse audience both locally and from the surroundings	The portfolio is compelling and raises the interest of new groups and audiences both locally and from the surroundings
	Relevance & Opportunity	The portfolio addresses in a limited way local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are neither investigated nor pursued.	The portfolio addresses some local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are identified	The portfolio inclusively responds to pressing local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Expands opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets	The portfolio is adjusted to address new emerging challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. creates a number of new opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets.
OPERATIONAL	Planning & Delivery Capacities	The portfolio has limited resources and the retrieval of missing resources is yet to be defined.	The portfolio has some available resources and activities that could retrieve resources are under definition.	The portfolio is financially sustainable and activities/fundraising initiatives to retrieve them are in progress .	The portfolio is financially sustainable and has retrieved most fundings.
	Resilience, Flexibility & Adaptability	The portfolio has not identified emerging needs and opportunities that could have influenced the masterplan	The portfolio has identified some emerging needs and opportunities but strong 'evidence' is missing	Emerging needs and opportunities have been identified and masterplan adjustments are under definition	Emerging needs and opportunities have been fully defined and the masterplan has been adapted accordingly
	Interoperability & Connectivity	The pilot is not aware of other initiatives in the area and has not identified relevant policies and plans that could contribute to the meanwhile strategy	The portfolio is aligned with some initiatives in the area or policies and plans relevant to the meanwhile use strategy have been analysed.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are almost established. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy supported by policy programmes.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are concrete. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy is contributing and supported by policy programmes.
RELATIONAL	Impact time & Depth (Too early to assess)	The portfolio results are requiring more time than expected and not all results and impacts will be achieved	The portfolio results are timely and most results and impacts are expected to be achieved.	The portfolio results have been achieved earlier than expected allowing to add additional uses for different groups.	The portfolio is involving and aligning around local innovation missions with a plethora of diverse stakeholders.
	Agency & Legitimacy	The portfolio does not contribute to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors to involve to build multi-sectoral coalitions have not been identified	The portfolio contributes in a limited way to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors have been identified but must define how to involve them in multi-sectoral coalitions	The portfolio contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established	The portfolio strongly contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An inclusive array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established
	Legacy, Sustainability & Scalability	The portfolio does not have a clear legacy.	The portfolio creates certain conditions for long term legacy but remains context-specific (not transferable).	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become more sustainable in the long-term. E.g. Scalability is being investigated	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become fully scalable or transferrable.

**MIND
MILAN**

| About the area

MIND is the iconic site of the 2015 EXPO “Feeding the planet, Energy for life”, which attracted 21 million visitors from 141 Countries across the globe. It is a large area of nearly 1 million square metres, located in a suburban area at the north-west periphery of Milan, right on the border delimited by Milan’s outer ring road and connected to the city centre by tube and train. The area is also located at the convergence of two main types of suburban space, namely small sized urban sprawls and a former industrialised area which has undergone a process of deindustrialisation.

The area around MIND is made up of 16 small municipalities which belong to the Greater Metropolitan Area of Milan. Compared to the capital city, the area is much lesser urbanised (25% compared to Milan’s 60% rate, source PlusValue, 2021), and is characterised by a strong **spatial and socio-demographic fragmentation** mainly due to the scarcity in road, pedestrians and bike lanes connections between MIND and the surrounding areas. Throughout the last century, the territory has gone through deep transformations, evolving from an agricultural area to an industrial site, and further experiencing disruptions from deindustrialisation processes and subsequent decay.

At present, the area faces a number of socio-economic challenges, including **weak connectivity and integration** with the surrounding Municipalities, **lack of basic services and infrastructure**, **scarcity in social and cultural amenities**, **soil and air pollution**, as well as **unemployment and low educational attainments** that particularly affect the area, often in a contradictory relationship with Milan. Moreover, **access to housing** is an increasingly emerging challenge, vis-à-vis an ongoing post-pandemic trend which is rapidly rising accommodation’s prices and rents all across the Greater Milan, making this city amongst the most expensive ones in Europe for housing costs [16]. Furthermore, while the 2015 EXPO brought about high visibility to the area and helped unlock a series of developments and infrastructure works necessary for the event, its legacy is surrounded by mixed feelings and is quite contested across the communities living nearby.

| Milan Innovation District (MIND)

The creation of Milan Innovation District (MIND) is amongst the most high profile redevelopments currently ongoing in the city of Milan. The project is developed through a **public-private partnership (PPP)** between Arexpo (a majority public company owning the area) and the international real estate developer Lendlease. The regeneration plan foresees the creation of a **new centre for scientific excellence and ‘ahead-of-time’ lifestyles**, realising a **mixed-use area where forefront research & innovation, enterprising and job creation unfold hand in hand with new ways of living and enjoying urban districts**. Sustainability, health and wellbeing, and social inclusion are the keywords of the regeneration, thus making MIND well beyond an economic-led project of urban district. As we can read in MIND’s official website: *‘All along the streets and buildings of the district, people will experience new ways of working and living, getting in contact with novel technologies and experiencing a more virtuous way of moving and living. As a ‘city and district of the future’, MIND is the most effective tool for spreading the culture of sustainability and demonstrating the collective value of scientific progress’.*

According to this vision, MIND is built around two main clusters:

- **City of the Future** – a large-scale demonstrator for carbon-neutral districts. MIND partners are developing the district with a view of turning it into a living lab where novel technologies, products, services and processes dedicated to health, wellbeing and sustainability can be tested and scaled.
- **Life Science** – an extensive network of research-intensive companies, multinationals, SMEs, start-ups, top international research staff, doctors, and patients can experiment and test innovative solutions for health, at the intersection between tech and open innovation practices.

The masterplan foresees the development of 480,000 sqm of public use that includes students' accommodation, social housing and leisure, sports and cultural activities and the Public Anchors headquarters. Amongst them, the **Galeazzi Research Hospital** will host around 9,000 workers in health fields such as orthopaedics and cardiology. The **Human Technopole**, an international Hub connecting Universities, Research Institutes and Hospitals to develop personalised medicine in address to cancer and neurodegenerative diseases, will host 1,000 researchers and 500 administrative and technical staff. The scientific campus of the **University of Milan Statale** will host around 18,000 students and 2,000 staff. 480,000 sqm will be dedicated to private uses such as offices, residential, retail, light industry and hospitality, culture and sport-related uses. At completion expected in 2031, the district will be likely to host around 60,000 people a day. Furthermore, the Masterplan promotes walkability and innovative mobility to enhance health and well-being. It fosters outdoor working areas and training activities, providing tenants and passers-by with the opportunity to walk through buildings in a natural way, creating continuous green infrastructures, public spaces that incentivise social interactions, and easier access to water canals.

| Overall challenge and Innovation Missions in T-Factor

Within T-Factor, the overall challenge of the MIND pilot is understood as *'unlocking a new identity for MIND centred on nature, health and wellbeing, doing so through co-creative processes that bring new actors on site and anticipate novel collaborations and cross-sectoral alliances'*. This challenge acknowledges that the lack of connectivity and integration of MIND with the surrounding territories is a structural barrier that may reinforce widespread perceptions and feelings of the area as 'far, isolated and poorly attractive', and thus limit engagement during and beyond the meanwhile of the construction period.

In a redevelopment which will take nearly a decade to unveil and transform infrastructural conditions, addressing **accessibility and attraction** in the meanwhile is perceived by the Local Coalition as a fundamental step for unlocking MIND's vision, especially in its social sustainability dimension. Bringing a variety of publics on site - children, young people, families, local associations, etc. - is key to create dialogue and social connectivity between actors inside and outside the district, so as to prevent and mitigate the risk of MIND becoming an 'urban island' not integrated with the surrounding territories. At the same time, the creation of MIND's innovation ecosystem - which is unleashing a critical mass of researchers, doctors, scientists and experts from multiple fields of R&D - stands as a unique opportunity to create and unlock short and medium term co-benefits that can in turn help accelerate the creation of a new identity for the site, transforming negative perceptions towards a sense of place and belonging.

Three innovation missions contextualise and set the ground for the meanwhile strategy of T-Factor in MIND:

Mission 1: Vibrant community disseminating and exchanging research and scientific knowledge: this mission seeks to support the active exchange of knowledge, skills, resources and initiatives both within the MIND internal ecosystem of people and organisations, which is growing day by day, and to the outside. Specifically, the mission aims to disseminate the scientific knowledge produced at MIND with the final aim on one side of creating a broader community of people aware of what is happening and will happen in MIND in terms of research, and more importantly, about the impact that R&D can have on their wellbeing and society, on the other hand to create bonds with external stakeholder and target groups that may benefit from the research carried out at MIND.

Mission 2: Conscious and Sustainable Lifestyles: this mission aims to promote well-being through green practices and open air activities that help make MIND a site of reference for more conscious, healthy, and sustainable lifestyles, through awareness-raising, educational, cultural and recreational temporary interventions that explore nature and biodiversity in urban spaces.

Mission 3: Accessibility & Identity: this mission seeks to support the osmosis between MIND and the surrounding territory, making MIND a recognizable and accessible place, expanding the relationship with the neighbouring municipalities and the broader city, towards a greater integration of the district into the city of Milan.

MIND MILAN THEORY OF CHANGE

How can we create an open and vibrant community and build a new identity for MIND based on nature, health and wellbeing?

- #PROMPT USES: one off events that attract people in places
- #REGULAR USES: regular activities that retain people in places
- #STABLE USES: temporary uses that anchor people to places
- #COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE
- #INVESTMENT & FUNDING
- #SMART PLANNING, POLICY & REGULATION

Contributing to
And eventually in
This will result in

Missions (if we)

- Mission 1: Vibrant community disseminating and exchanging research and scientific knowledge
- Mission 2: Conscious and Sustainable Lifestyles
- Mission 3: Accessibility & Identity

Figure 14: Theory of Change – Milan Mind

Meanwhile Portfolio

The Portfolio of the MIND Pilot is conceived as part of the process of creating a renewed identity of the area and new collaborative networks, supporting MIND's development as an open and vibrant ecosystem for forefront economic, tech and social innovations. There are two main bundles of activities addressed in the portfolio, that revolve around three main temporary uses:

1. A **Community House**, understood as both a physical and symbolic space that gathers together the multitude of actors within and outside MIND, in order to foster collaboration especially between businesses and non profit organisations. The Community House shall be built on a collaborative governance and management model that can be adapted to host different events, initiatives and services, jointly conceived by a mix of internal and external stakeholders. In the short term, the space will host the prototype of a joint initiative by a selected tenant and a local organisation, as demonstrator of the synergies that can be created and promoted by the ecosystem.
2. A **Life Science Open Hub (LSOH)**, where art and science meets in one place to create an immersive experience in the world of healthcare and personalised medicine. The LSOH will be available for universities, companies, and Life Science clusters who seek to engage with a wider public (expert and non-expert, as well as policymakers). The space will be mainly dedicated to **dissemination** and **education** purposes, but it will also host events and collaborative initiatives for the companies of the MIND ecosystem willing to present products and engage with third-parties, fostering **collaboration** and **cross-pollination**.
3. An **experimental and educational garden** called **Herbula Garden**, devoted to the link between nature and wellbeing, aimed at raising awareness on urban biodiversity and the valorisation of natural resources. It will consist of an herbal garden dedicated to the cultivation of indigenous herbs and flowers, fostering local biodiversity and the smart use of its products. The garden will have the functions of educating surrounding communities to the benefits of urban biodiversity and the use of natural products, preserving the natural environment, and providing a space for learning and experimentation for students of different ages.

Figure 15: MIND's Portfolio

Double clic on the text to access the digital version of the Portfolio

Portfolio Progress

In the time frame considered for the mid-term evaluation of T-Factor [17], the Local Coalition has delivered five main activities relevant to the portfolio: (1) The 'Impact Innovations with the local communities' event; (2) T-Lab 2 Field Visits focussed on the topic of open innovation ecosystems; (3) Crash course 3D printing LDM[18]: tools 4 animals & plants; (4) Launch of the Call for Ideas 'Open Food Factory'; (5) collective gardening and preparatory activities for Herbula.

'Impact Innovations with the local communities' (original title, 'Innovazioni di Impatto con le comunità: come valorizzarle?') was an online conference organised in February 2022 by Planet Idea and promoted by Fondazione Triulza, one of the most important social anchors in MIND. The event aimed at discussing novel measurement frameworks and approaches for place-based social innovations, starting with the analysis of concrete projects and initiatives. As part of the Local Coalition, PlusValue brought about the experience of T-Factor and the topic of temporary uses. Besides exploring the important topic of impact measurement of temporary uses, the event was also instrumental to establish and further reinforce the collaboration with Fondazione Triulza, as better explained later in the document.

The second activity brought members of the T-Lab 2 'Urban Production and Digitalisation' to MIND in an immersive **field visit and discussion** about the key characteristics and qualities of **open innovation ecosystems for urban districts**. The aim of the visit, held in May 2022, was to leverage the expertise of the T-Lab on this topic, so as to provide the Local Coalition and stakeholders on site (particularly, Lendlease and the University of Milan) with inputs and insights that could feed the Portfolio and, more broadly, the innovation ecosystem' strategy of MIND.

As a follow up, a **case study report**[19] was prepared by T-Lab 2 exploring ten different cases of open innovation ecosystems. In October 2022, this activity evolved in a **field visit of the Local Coalition (including Lendlease) in Bilbao**, aimed at gathering knowledge and inspiration from a number of R&D and knowledge clusters in and around Bilbao and the Basque Country.

The **Crash course 3D printing LDM: tools 4 animals & plants** consisted of an extracurricular training course delivered by Polifactory (the Makerspace/Fablab of Politecnico di Milano) as part of the 'Passion In Action' programme. Every year, Polifactory runs a series of intensive training sessions called 'Crash Courses', with the aim of introducing students to digital fabrication techniques. Each course has a duration of two full days and usually involves 10 to 30 students. In 2022, the course explored 3D printing of ceramics through circularity principles. Amongst the design briefs proposed to students, one was dedicated to ideas and solutions for protecting and enhancing urban biodiversity throughout MIND's development, with the plan of integrating the proposed projects within the biodiversity kit which is envisaged in the T-Factor portfolio.

[17] Generally, the period considered in this report is February 2022 - October 2022, which is the overall time frame in which the T-Factor Pilots started to implement and run their temporary use strategies. However, it should be noted that the insights and results (especially more qualitative results) captured in this report also refer to the preceding period (the whole 2021), particularly when it comes to preliminary activities of engagement, initial scoping and co-design that started to set the ground for implementing and iterating temporary uses and activities.

[18] LDM stands for Liquid Deposition Modelling.

[19] See: <https://www.t-factor.eu/life-science-openhub-study/>

The **Launch of the Call for Ideas 'Open Food Factory'** was developed in close collaboration with the **Distributed Design Platform**, a Creative Europe project partnered by Polifactory-Politecnico di Milano and aimed at boosting the spread of the global Fab Lab network by means of strategic connections and collaborations between designers and makers with the European market. The **Open Food Factory** is a design action developed by Polifactory within the Distributed Design Platform, which seeks to explore the relationship between distributed design and food processing to develop open-source solutions dedicated to the fermentation and distillation or extraction of food, stimulating the circularity of urban food systems. During this event, the Open Food Factory initiative was presented to the audience and the Open call for ideas was officially launched, with the aim to develop and prototype 2 tools for fermentation and distillation proposed by young designers studying at Politecnico di Milano. During the launch of the call, **Stefano Tosoni** from **Wooding Wild Food Lab** was invited to guide the students in the design of instruments to be tested on plants of 'Herbula', the T-Factor temporary herbal garden of MIND (see activity portfolio). The prototypes will be tested with the herbs and flowers of the Herbula Garden.

In 2022, the Local Coalition also started the prototyping and testing of **Herbula garden**, the T-Factor temporary garden lab dedicated to wild and indigenous herbs and flowers. Preparatory activities such as field visits, analysis of requirements and permissioning and actual garden design, have engaged the partners in a tight dialogue with Lendlease to identify collaborative procedures for the realisation and future maintenance of the garden, and for its harmonious integration into their broader meanwhile landscape programme which has been implemented since April 2022 on site.

Herbula is designed to be a **demonstrator for collective greening and biodiversity management in urban regeneration, by deploying training and educational activities to involve the local community**. It consists of:

- A set of herb planters dedicated to the cultivation of aromatic and officinal herbs and flowers for home-made preparations.
- An experimental area dedicated to the cultivation of species that can be processed through dedicated tools and technologies and turned into innovative products for human use.
- A natural lawn dedicated to spontaneous vegetation that can attract pollinators and enhance urban biodiversity.

Two main events were organised to start running and testing this temporary use. First, in April 2022, a **'WILD FOOD LAB'** workshop was organised and curated by the Local Coalition as a part of a broader MIND's festival dedicated to opening the site to the general public (PrimaVera MIND on 30/04 and 01/05/2022). The workshop was dedicated to the use of wild ingredients for alcohol-free cocktails, through a talk and demonstrations and tasting of alcohol-free cocktails prepared with herbs such as spruce. Later in October 2022, the Local Coalition organised the **Herbula's opening event** with an activity of collective gardening that mainly involved MIND's workers and tenants. The opening event was **mainly addressed to the community of people working at MIND** with the purpose of introducing them to the meanwhile uses of T-Factor. The event was dedicated to aromatic herbs, which is also hosting a parterre of benches designed to run educational activities. The selection of plants, which was curated by LAND, focused on species that can be used for gastronomic, herbal, or cosmetic purposes.

Although these are the main activities implemented and (some of them) evaluated during the period of reference, it should be noted that they represented milestones of a broader process developed over time, including several preparatory actions such as internal coordination meetings, co-design sessions (within the Local Coalition, but also with local external actors, members of the Transformation Agency and the collaborating T-Lab), on site visits. Examples include:

- Exploratory conversations with the **School Institute Pareto (High School)** on the possibility to work on the Herbula Garden to experiment new seeds cultivation. This included initial presentations in class to students and early engagement.
- Exploratory conversations and design sessions with **Progetto Natura Onlus** for the creation of an educational course on urban biodiversity for primary and secondary schools in MIND. This is now evolving in the phase of engaging at least 6 classes from neighbouring municipalities with the support of Fondazione Triulza.
- Exploratory conversations with a MIND tenant (**ROLD**) and a social cooperative of the area (**CooperRho**) for the ideation of the Community House project.

Additionally other activities have enabled the dissemination of the pilot's outcomes beyond local outreach, the cultivation of promising crosscutting relations with local stakeholders, and fostered the debate on meanwhile uses across practitioners, investors and public authorities:

- Exchange with the **e-PIC** land project, financed by the regional government to promote citizens awareness and accessibility to cultural heritage in the area around MIND;
- Participation in the **MIND Community Park series** promoted by Arexpo and Fondazione Triulza, a format to debate on innovative governance models for the future park of MIND;
- Participation in the final award of **MIND Education programme** to get in touch with the selected projects by the students;
- Organisation of a workshop and site visit on sustainable urban regeneration in collaboration with the format **Rebuilding Europe** ideated by **Drees&Sommer** and **LAND**;
- Organisation of a conference and site visit on meanwhile uses with the delegation of the city of **Bozen** and the **Suedtirool Association of Landscape architects (LAS)**.

| Stakeholders and Beneficiaries

Throughout the period of reference, the Local Coalition has been working with a variety of local stakeholders and collaborators in order to leverage proper expertise and resources to design and deliver the portfolio. First, several private organisations were involved across the three missions in order to leverage their specific expertise throughout the co-design and testing of temporary uses such as Herbula and the Community House. Amongst them, **Planet Idea**, **Wooding Wild Food Lab**, **Progetto Natura Onlus** were particularly important for supporting the development of Herbula, given their thematic expertise on greening and biodiversity practices. Similarly, **ROLD** and **Cooperho** are two organisations that have been involved and will keep an important role in the development of the Community House. Over time, the Local Coalition has also worked to strengthen the relationship with **Fondazione Triulza**, one key tenant in MIND that convenes +70 organisations committed to social and environmental impact. Especially in the current and next iteration of the Portfolio, the role of Fondazione Triulza is planned to be increased particularly around Herbula-related activities in address to schools and biodiversity education, so as to build proper conditions for this temporary uses to keep on running and evolving beyond the T-Factor's time frame. The involvement of **Lendlease** (MIND's developer) has been indeed crucial throughout the period and before, allowing the Local Coalition to better integrate the planned activities within the broader strategy for the development, as well as to overcome ongoing barriers and difficulties in access to space for temporary activities and uses. Furthermore, the Local Coalition received support of T-Lab 2 'Urban Production and Digitalisation' to deep dive in the context of the innovation ecosystem for the T-Lab 2 Field Visit.

The Local Coalition has also worked during the period to look for sponsors and partners who could support the physical construction of the temporary spaces. For example, the Herbula is sponsored by **WoodBlocX** and **Harpo**. Other important conversations have been established with companies such as **WoodBeton**, **Leroy Merlin**, **StoraEnso**, in order to retrieve additional resources for the Community House.

Regarding the activities' beneficiaries, there were three main types of beneficiaries addressed during the period. First, many activities were addressed to the **community of MIND's workers and tenants**, in order to make T-Factor visible and well positioned in the area, while starting exploring possible synergies and collaborations with existing initiatives on site. A second important group is mainly represented by **young students, both at secondary and tertiary education levels**. In the next iteration, there will be enhanced emphasis on this target-group, as temporary uses such as Herbula and the Community House could be further explored towards addressing capacity-building and empowerment of young people, also considering key challenges around MIND such as high levels of NEETs (not in education, employment or training) and social exclusion. Lastly, a third group was represented by a **general public** interested in MIND's development and the future of the area. Some activities were designed to attract this type of public; however, as reported later in the document, this was the most difficult group to engage, especially due to the (real and perceived) low accessibility and attractiveness of MIND as a destination.

Photo credits: LAND

Activity 1: Fondazione Triulza event in MIND talking about social innovation and community impact

Prompt use

10/02/2022

Target groups: persons interested in social innovation and community impact in urban regeneration

68 online viewers

1 recorded video of the event

Collaborators: Planet Idea, Polimi and PlusValue

Keywords:
#Learning, Skilling, Making
#Local enterprising

Activity 2: -Lab 2 Immersion expedition to MIND + meetings with stakeholder on site/online (Tecnalia visit)

Prompt use

17/05/2022

Target groups: Tecnalia and stakeholders related to MIND

Main beneficiary:

Tecnalia

1 report with

10 case studies

Collaborators: Lendlease, UniMi, 3D printing laboratory, PlusValue and Polimi

Keywords:
#Learning, Skilling, Making
#Creativity & Talent

Activity 3: Crash course 3D printing LDM: tools 4 animals & plants

Prompt use

18/07/2022
19/07/2022

Target groups: students

Collaborators: Polimi

Keywords:
#Physical & Mental Health
#Greening & Biodiversity

Main beneficiaries: 12
50 - 80 beneficiaries indirectly involved Polifactory and Design school community

50-80 beneficiaries indirectly involved Polifactory and Design school community

12 students

3 concepts developed by students

Activity 4: Call for ideas launch (Distributed Design)

Prompt use

21/09/2022

Target groups: students

20 students

Collaborators: Polimi

6 applications for the call for ideas by 6 different teams

Keywords:
#Cohesion & Social Justice
#Greening & Biodiversity

4 presentations by guest speakers

Activity 5: Collective gardening event

Prompt use

12/10/2022

Target groups: Persons working in the MIND site

15 participants that work in MIND

Collaborators: LAND and Polimi

2 products: (1) a set of three planters were installed as part of the meanwhile use "Herbula Garden" and (2) labels for identifying the planted species were designed and produced at Polifactory

Keywords:
#Cohesion & Social Justice
#Greening & Biodiversity

| Main activities' results

In the paragraphs that follow, we provide an overview of the main results achieved through the activities described earlier, extracted from the self-reporting templates of the past activities.

Enhanced positioning of T-Factor and temporary uses as collaboration's catalysts

As MIND is a complex ecosystem made of big multinationals and companies, making T-Factor visible and recognisable in the area was a key objective since the very beginning. Generally, the activities run so far have helped **spread the voice of the presence** of T-Factor on site, as well as its positioning as a catalyst for collaborations through the meanwhile. The 'Collective gardening' event, which was the first activity of the Herbula garden, provided MIND's tenants with an introduction to the meanwhile strategies and uses proposed by T-Factor. It was also a call to action for them to be part of the future activities at the garden, so as to foster collective ownership and maintenance of the garden as a key legacy of T-Factor. In the upcoming months, Herbula will keep on hosting several activities dedicated to the internal community of MIND and the surrounding municipalities with the objective to raise awareness on the importance of preserving and respecting the natural ecosystem of the area, rich in animal and plant species. Furthermore, the garden will host an interactive exhibition where visitors could discover the urban biodiversity and learn how to interact with it, in a relationship aimed at preserving the environment on the one hand, and at improving personal wellbeing and quality of life on the other hand.

Besides creating awareness that T-Factor exists in the area, the pilot also aimed to **position** itself as a **platform to gather knowledge and information that exists in the area**. The activities 'Impact Innovations with the local communities' event and 'T-Lab 2 Field Visits' **gave the beneficiaries support in capacity building in social innovation and innovation ecosystem**. More specifically, the main topic of the Fondazione Triulza event in MIND was about social innovation and how to create impact in regeneration processes, explicitly targeting issues such as monitoring and evaluation, meanwhile activities and community engagement. PlusValue gave a review of the essential concepts for setting up a social impact assessment by bringing examples of innovative interventions capable of generating social impact. The activity gave an interesting overview about methodologies and tools to use for community engagement processes, in which the MIND pilot received positive feedback from the organiser after the event. Feedback from the participants was more difficult to gather since it was an online conference and there were no interaction possibilities, unless the participants raised questions in the chat. Regarding the T-Lab 2 Field Visits, Tecnalìa got to discover a very complex but interesting ecosystem with many opportunities to explore in the MIND area. Tecnalìa received the chance to deep dive in the context of the innovation ecosystem and meet various stakeholders at the site so that they could support the MIND pilot with the research activity. Furthermore, Tecnalìa has indicated that the visit enhanced their understanding on how to design and implement an 'Open Innovation ecosystem' in Life Science in MIND.

Cross-sector collaborations with multiple organisations

The activities have let the MIND pilot work together with organisations from different sectors. **The cross-sector collaborations were a leverage point to disseminate knowledge and expertise to other local communities and were used for the design and development of meanwhile activities**. For the Herbula garden, the collaboration with organisations Planet Idea, Wooding Wild Food Lab, Progetto Natura Onlus were activated for their expertise on greening and biodiversity practices. Learnings from these entities were disseminated during the 'Collective gardening' event to workers of the MIND site and will be further spread to other (local) stakeholders in future activities related to the Herbula garden.

Furthermore, the MIND pilot has had several exploratory conversations with Fondazione Triulza, a network association pertaining to different sectors with the aim to make social and environmental impact in the development of the area Milano Innovation District. The relationship with Fondazione Triulza will be intensified in the coming period through the engagement of local schools in green and biodiversity-led practices at Herbula and other green initiatives of spaces in the area.

For the development of the Community House, the Local Coalition has worked with two organisations, namely ROLD and Cooperho. Moreover, the involvement of Lendlease, a globally integrated real estate company, was crucial for the MIND pilot to enhance the integration of the planned activities in relation to the urban regeneration strategy and to receive support in tackling issues in the access to space for temporary activities.

Lastly, other organisations such as Istituto di Istruzione Superiore Vilfredo F. Pareto, Valore Italia, CoopeRho, Villa Arconati, Merits, WoodBlocX, and Harpo were involved to equip the Local Coalition with the right expertise and resources needed to unlock the activities defined in the portfolio.

Enhanced knowledge and capacity to engage in more conscious and sustainable lifestyles

The MIND pilot attracted and engaged with (young) individuals other than businesses in the MIND area. The activities Crash course 3D printing and Call for ideas launch have worked with students regarding the topics sustainability, wellbeing, biodiversity and circularity. For the 'Crash course 3D printing LDM: tools 4 animals & plants, the students needed to form working groups to deliver projects which are included in the curriculum. Four out of five working groups took the challenge to design an object that protects or increases biodiversity in an urban context. Additionally, three out of these four working groups have developed feeder nests or animal shelters and the other group designed a pot to encourage mycelium growth. Furthermore, for the Launch of the Call for Ideas 'Open Food Factory', a panel of guests talked about the design and experimental experiences in the field of fermentation and distillation to stimulate the reflection on the relationship between design and plant-based food. Polimi has indicated that this activity made approx. all participants aware of the topic of plant-based nutrition and the role of designers in the development of sustainable products for the food industry. Many students have attended the call presentation and asked a lot of questions to the guest speakers, which is an indication that these topics are relatively close to the world of product design & development and the sensibilities of designers.

Figure 16: outcome proxy for 'Collective gardening' event

Furthermore, the 'WILD FOOD LAB' workshop brought the participants closer to T-Factor activities linked to Nature, Sustainability and Health. For instance, the content of the workshop was in tune with the Herbula garden. The audience was heterogeneous in terms of age, from adolescents to elderly people: children accompanied by parents, young students, green and foraging enthusiasts, and a few journalists. The participants showed interest in the different topics and in general it was a very engaging activity, also considering the increasing number of people gathering around the workshop area. Learning how to recognise the edible parts of some plants, where to find them, and how to pick them proved to be a way to expand knowledge of the participants and increase the understanding of Nature.

Lastly, the 'Collective gardening' event was aimed at people that work in MIND. First Polimi gave a short introduction of the overall purpose and plan of the meanwhile space and thereafter LAND shared some curiosities about the plants and their uses. The activity had a positive effect on the engagement of the participants, as 90% of the participants have indicated that their interest to participate in T-factor events, such as the 'co-gardening' event, has increased after this event. Lastly, the activity also positively affected the motivation and desire to develop/maintain a healthy and green lifestyle.

Photo credits: Polimi

| Contribution to impact at Pilot level

The section describes the pilot level changes and considerations gathered through the 'Critical Friend' interview. As anticipated, the interview is aimed at exploring if and how the activities undertaken during the period of reference are contributing towards long term outcomes and impacts of urban regeneration, particularly from the point of view of enhanced strategic, operational and relational dimensions (ref. Methodology section). In the following paragraph we report on the main strengths and weaknesses that emerged through the interview. A self-assessment scoreboard filled out by the Local Coalition is provided at the end of the section. It is important to highlight that the insights and reflections reported in this chapter do not only capture the voice and perceptions of the Local Coalition; they also include and integrate the results of the ongoing observation and support developed by the Transformation Agency over time, in its role of 'critical friend' of the pilot.

Building upon the legacy of EXPO 2015, Milan Innovation District shall become a **lively district for research & innovation, particularly in the domain of life sciences and advanced tech solutions** that can contribute to preventative health and wellbeing, sustainable lifestyles, and climate-friendly production, consumption and ways of living. The masterplan envisages a rich variety of uses such as residential, commercial, and offices, research and higher education, leisure and public open and green and blue spaces. Amongst the T-Factor pilots, the Milanese one stands amongst the most complex redevelopments when it comes to scale and ambitions in the diversity of uses envisaged, as well as in terms of diversity of interests, agendas and priorities at play.

The redevelopment is run via a **public-private partnership (PPP)** between the public company **Arexpo** (which involves a range of shareholders: the Ministry of Economy and Finance; Lombardy Region, Municipality of Milan, Milan Fair Foundation, Metropolitan City of Milan, and Municipality of Rho) and the international developer **Lendlease**. Furthermore, MIND's innovation ecosystem is steered by the so-called **Federated Innovation™@MIND**, a large partnership model involving top companies from different industries and sectors with proven track record in frontier R&D (at today, 38 companies among which: AstraZeneca, Novartis, Illumina, Stora Enso, E.ON). The Federated Innovation@MIND plays a pivotal role in supporting and accelerating innovation in MIND, and works through an ambitious **model of participatory governance for district innovation**. Overall, MIND is characterised by a **complex layer of management and decision-making structures that make this case quite unique in the landscape of PPP-led redevelopments in Europe - yet also challenging for meanwhile interventions**.

Within this context, the pilot is working towards activating and fostering engagement at two different yet complementary levels. On the one hand, the meanwhile strategy seeks to **activate and engage with the existing and upcoming tenants**, with the overall aim of supporting the creation of a community of place which can help accelerate the transformation of the site as a lively, vibrant and innovative district where different types of audiences and uses coexist and collaborate with each other towards new forms of sustainable, healthy and active living. On the other hand, meanwhile interventions shall **support the discovery of MIND by external audiences and communities, particularly the ones that reside around the area where the impacts of EXPO 2015 were quite contested**. Overall, the meanwhile strategy is understood as a way to anticipate and accelerate the transformation of the identity of the site, by means of showcasing alternative uses, sustaining cross-sector collaborations, and exploring novel thematic crossovers through placemaking that, all together, can show possible ways forward to urban districts rooted in health and wellbeing.

The strategy acknowledges that current perceptions of MIND as a hardly accessible and isolated area, not yet integrated through (driving, walking and cycling) routes all across the surrounding municipalities, is a major challenge for the broad redevelopment and more immediately for activation during the meanwhile. Yet, it also offers opportunities to explore and co-create new imaginaries and meanings of places through the involvement of a variety of actors, especially those 'unusual' ones who would otherwise have less chances to discover MIND in its early transformation and contribute to it.

MIND is an ambitious and risky project, sustained by an equally ambitious strategy of branding, marketing and activation which however targets primarily the world of businesses and frontier R&D. The added value of T-Factor is that **it complements this strategy with a focus on publics - young people, families, social and cultural associations, education institutions, etc. - who will indeed be present or have a stake in MIND's future, but that are not a priority in engagement so far.** Therefore, T-Factor will try to expand and enhance the spectrum and scope of participation through the meanwhile, activating voices and perspectives that can help make the site more sensitive to diverse needs in the short to medium term, and more inclusive and socially sustainable in the long term.

To this end, in the period considered, the Local Coalition has been running activities aimed at **establishing strategic alliances with actors within and outside MIND.**

First, an important relation has been established with **Fondazione Triulza**, a large network of third sector organisations and an important tenant in MIND. The collaboration with Fondazione Triulza is deemed to be highly strategic, especially in terms of building a legacy that the Foundation can keep on maintaining and evolving when T-Factor will be over. While during the reported period there were mainly exploratory conversations, the current and next iteration of the Portfolio will see a stronger and more continuous collaboration through the engagement of local schools in green and biodiversity-led practices at Herbula and in

other green spaces in and around MIND. At the same time, initial conversation with business organisations within and outside the area (such as Rold, Astrazeneca, Bio4Dreams, Euromilano, Nhood) were carried out to explore their interest and potential involvement in T-Factor, as well as to support the positioning of the project within such a large, complex and multifaceted context.

Other organisations including **Wood*ing-Wild Food Lab, Progetto Natura Onlus, Istituto di Istruzione Superiore Vilfredo F. Pareto, Valore Italia, CoopeRho, Villa Arconati, Merits** have been approached throughout the period with the aim of both enlarging the pool of possibilities for meanwhile activities to bloom and to pool expertise and capacities around the activities developed or to be developed. A key relationship is indeed the one with **Lendlease**, who has been following and actively participating throughout the main steps of the pilot, providing strategic indications but also helping to solve practical issues over time. Overall, the Local Coalition reported that there has been **growing alignment over time around the challenges to be prioritised**, despite the growing changes in the Masterplan priorities and the different timings of T-Factor and the redevelopment.

"The work of T-Factor is very relevant for MIND. Our portfolio is aligned with the long-term vision of the redevelopment; however, it is challenging as the timeline and priorities of the Masterplan changes continuously and are different from the Temporary Uses ones." (Local Coalition)

The engagement efforts and activities delivered so far has enabled the pilot to **make MIND's tenants more aware of the value that meanwhile uses and T-Factor could bring to the district**, especially in terms of raising its positioning and visibility. The pilot has achieved initial success in **establishing a prominent presence of T-Factor** within the district. In doing so, the Local Coalition also stressed a positive influence of the activities in **raising awareness and knowledge on meanwhile practices** as viable tools for innovative and creative placemaking. However it must be said that despite being aware of T-Factor, sometimes it is difficult to

get in contact and activate the tenants as most of them are still in the process of settling in the area and often overwhelmed by the many initiatives proposed by anchors, the Federated Innovation, etc.

“We have spent a lot of time in building this network, and now many actors at MIND have a good overview of what T-Factor is. They know that we are here and our expectations in terms of activities. We reinforce the positioning of T-Factor in MIND by speaking and networking as much as possible, and our presence in MIND helps in that aspect. The Stakeholders see the value of meanwhile uses and what T-factor can bring to the area” (Local Coalition)

Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that the engagement strategy of the pilot has been approached in ways that could **leverage additional resources - including financial - from a diversity of local actors**. The Local Coalition has committed to find sponsors and partner suppliers who could support the construction of temporary spaces. For example, Herbula garden has been co-financed by **WoodBlocX and Harpo** (leader companies in the landscape sectors), while for the Community House conversations have been established with major retailers such as **Leroy Merlin**, yet to be concretised in some forms of sponsorship or donation. When it comes to the activities implemented, the ones particularly addressed to students and young people turned out to be particularly relevant for the next iteration of the Portfolio, especially in address to Mission 2 ‘Active, Healthy and Sustainable Lifestyles’. Youngsters have largely enjoyed the proposed activities, and demonstrated interest and commitment in engaging in placemaking practices at the crossroads between nature-based solutions, digital manufacturing, circularity principles and design. As outputs from activities such as the Crash Course and the Call for ideas within the Open Food Factory, some prototypes developed by the students such as bird nests would become part of **Herbula**, and in turn documented within the **Smart Urban Biodiversity** kit expected to be released in 2023. Furthermore, there are several ongoing efforts to strengthen the collaboration with students; in this regard, as anticipated above, the pilot is **collaborating with high schools** to design activities and involve students in the activation of

Herbula and other green spaces at MIND. In the upcoming period, **5 school classes** are expected to be involved in greening and biodiversity-related activities, thus contributing to enrich and further explore Herbula and related temporary experiments. Similarly, the pilot is also seeking ways to involve MIND’s tenants in novel ways of managing and maintaining natural and built assets, for example Herbula but also the Community House. A conversation on this has been initiated with T-Lab 6 ‘Social Innovation and Inclusion’, aimed at seeking support from this T-Lab in order to explore possible forms of bottom-up and participatory governance (especially around the Community House) in the next iteration of the Portfolio.

From an operational perspective, the Local Coalition highlighted a number of challenges and barriers that affected the T-Factor meanwhile strategy. First, **organising activities in the district is generally difficult as most of the spaces are under construction and lack basic facilities and infrastructure**. The Coalition points out that currently, spaces are available mainly for prompt and mostly outdoor activities, but not for stable uses. This also explains why the Local Coalition is **focussing on temporary activities and uses on open and green spaces, and working on light installations** (such as for the Community House) which can be eventually **moved easily** to other locations across MIND’ site. Additionally, the district suffers from the main challenge of poor accessibility in general, and the Local Coalition stressed a **certain difficulty in accessing the site on a continuous basis**, due to a relatively weak connectivity with Milan where most of the T-Factor team is based. Furthermore, there are **regulatory barriers** at the Municipal level that limit temporary uses to a duration of six months, which requires the Local Coalition to be extremely creative especially in the types of stable uses that can be tested on site and eventually left as main legacies of T-Factor. These challenges, coupled with the complex governance system of MIND, brought about some uncertainties especially in the planning stages, and sometimes slowed down time to decision making and activity delivery.

Furthermore, the Local Coalition has gone through moments of

divergent views and blockages over time. The Coalition is formed by four organisations (Plus Value as Coalition's Coordinator, Politecnico di Milano, Università di Milano and LAND Italia), accounting to an overall team of more than 10 people with expertise in different fields and (scientific) disciplines. These organisations have different types and degrees of stake in MIND - some of them being more consultants and collaborators for the redevelopment, while others being near future tenants. Thus, **agendas, interests and motivations may somehow differ, and this has meant dedicated time, throughout planning and delivery, to get to shared decisions and definitions of roles and responsibilities.** In this respect, it is worth mentioning that one activity, a course on Indoor Foraging, was planned for October 2022 and entailed an important effort in terms of planning and preparation. Yet, the activity did not finally materialise due to low subscriptions. This apparent failure represented an important milestone for the meanwhile strategy and for the Local Coalition as a team; **it brought about the need to 'sit down together' to interrogate again the portfolio, and to eventually revisit it through the learning of this failure, and the strengths of past activities.** As a result, the Local Coalition revised the portfolio in light of the current and next iteration, giving more emphasis on a fewer regular uses that insist on publics such as students and schools and that would have more chances of 'anchoring' to MIND - reducing instead prompt uses that typically require high costs and efforts of activation.

During the Critical Friend interview, the Local Coalition also mentioned a certain **weakness of the pilot around communication.** Given the complexity of MIND and its specific location, communication is a crucial component of the meanwhile strategy, and would require specific expertise and dedicated effort which is currently covered by the Local Coalition to a certain extent. In particular, while MIND is equipped with several channels of internal and external communication that have huge outreach, integrating T-Factor within such channels on a continuous basis is sometimes difficult, as it requires addressing some requirements, including early coordination with MIND's communication offices, that the Local Coalition is not always able to match. Therefore,

the Local Coalition is currently exploring ways for improving this aspect, including by leveraging expertise within T-Factor's partners to formulate a clearer and target-oriented communication strategy, as well as by considering additional resources to be allocated on communication.

Lastly, one point can be mentioned around the collaboration of the MIND Pilot with the Transformation Labs. During the period of reference, the Local Coalition mainly collaborated with T-Labs 2 'Urban Production and Digitisation' and 4 'Urban design for sociality and well being'. Especially the collaboration with T-Lab 2 was relatively limited in scope and oriented to the broad topic of open innovation ecosystems. For the next iteration, one important reflection at stake is how to make a better use of the thematic expertise that sits within the T-Labs, particularly in terms of making it more relevant to specific temporary uses' challenges and opportunities attached to the Pilot Portfolio. A conversation is currently underway with T-Lab 6 'Social Innovation and Inclusion' aimed at leveraging expertise around possible governance models for the Community House.

Towards the next period, the pilot will work as much as possible to fully unlock and realise all the activities and temporary uses planned in the Portfolio. As anticipated above, emphasis will be placed on stable uses such as Herbula and the Community House, developing a range of activities that can demonstrate uses and functions at the crossroads between awareness, education, capacity building and skills' development - with a lens on wellbeing, health, urban nature and biodiversity, as well as on social inclusion and social innovation. One important point will be the exploration of citizen science approaches, with the production of a 'Smart Urban Biodiversity Kit' meant as a product-service prototype for bottom-up mapping and monitoring urban biodiversity, developed through concepts and approaches of augmented citizen science. A new stream of activities will be also activated for Mission 1, with the specific aim of supporting scientific dissemination and knowledge sharing within and beyond the R&D

communities of MIND's innovation ecosystem. This stream of activity will be led by Università di Milano and will combine both expert workshops and an open exhibition.

One key point for the next period will be to **engage the local communities and vulnerable groups adjacent to the site and expand opportunities for addressing social issues around MIND**. The Local Coalition recognises that MIND sits within a challenging context where major social and economic issues exist, including unemployment, access to housing, educational attainment, niches of deprivation, amongst others. Addressing these issues through meanwhile interventions is indeed challenging, especially when considering the relatively limited budget available, and the time constraints of T-Factor, and the physical position of MIND, which is partially disconnected from the neighbouring areas. Nonetheless, temporary interventions can help create more awareness, willingness and capacities across current and future tenants, especially by means of unlocking new collaborations through placemaking that can keep on working and evolving beyond T-Factor, supporting the shift of inclusion on top of MIND's agenda.

	Dimensions	1	2	3	4
STRATEGIC	Positioning & Reputation	The portfolio poorly contributes to enhancing the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is not properly valorised.	The portfolio partially contributes to the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is considered but not a driver in the cultural and social evolution of the area	The portfolio brings a great visibility to the area and raises awareness about its heritage	The portfolio has provided the area with a new identity and its heritage is appreciated by diverse audiences.
	Attractiveness	The portfolio is raising limited interest and struggles to attract diverse audiences and target groups.	The portfolio raises the interest of target groups and engages with an unvaried audience on a local level.	The portfolio is compelling for all target groups and attracts a diverse audience both locally and from the surroundings	The portfolio is compelling and raises the interest of new groups and audiences both locally and from the surroundings
	Relevance & Opportunity	The portfolio addresses in a limited way local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are neither investigated nor pursued.	The portfolio addresses some local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are identified	The portfolio inclusively responds to pressing local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Expands opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets	The portfolio is adjusted to address new emerging challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. creates a number of new opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets.
OPERATIONAL	Planning & Delivery Capacities	The portfolio has limited resources and the retrieval of missing resources is yet to be defined.	The portfolio has some available resources and activities that could retrieve resources are under definition.	The portfolio is financially sustainable and activities/fundraising initiatives to retrieve them are in progress .	The portfolio is financially sustainable and has retrieved most fundings.
	Resilience, Flexibility & Adaptability	The portfolio has not identified emerging needs and opportunities that could have influenced the masterplan	The portfolio has identified some emerging needs and opportunities but strong 'evidence' is missing	Emerging needs and opportunities have been identified and masterplan adjustments are under definition	Emerging needs and opportunities have been fully defined and the masterplan has been adapted accordingly
	Interoperability & Connectivity	The pilot is not aware of other initiatives in the area and has not identified relevant policies and plans that could contribute to the meanwhile strategy	The portfolio is aligned with some initiatives in the area or policies and plans relevant to the meanwhile use strategy have been analysed.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are almost established. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy supported by policy programmes.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are concrete. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy is contributing and supported by policy programmes.
RELATIONAL	Impact time & Depth (Too early to assess)	The portfolio results are requiring more time than expected and not all results and impacts will be achieved	The portfolio results are timely and most results and impacts are expected to be achieved.	The portfolio results have been achieved earlier than expected allowing to add additional uses for different groups.	The portfolio is involving and aligning around local innovation missions with a plethora of diverse stakeholders.
	Agency & Legitimacy	The portfolio does not contribute to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors to involve to build multi-sectoral coalitions have not been identified	The portfolio contributes in a limited way to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors have been identified but must define how to involve them in multi-sectoral coalitions	The portfolio contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established	The portfolio strongly contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An inclusive array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established
	Legacy, Sustainability & Scalability	The portfolio does not have a clear legacy.	The portfolio creates certain conditions for long term legacy but remains context-specific (not transferable).	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become more sustainable in the long-term. E.g. Scalability is being investigated	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become fully scalable or transferrable.

TRAFARIA LISBON

TRAFARIA, LISBON

| About Trafaria

Trafaria is an old fishermen village that belongs to the Municipality of Almada and to the Lisbon Metropolitan Area on a larger scale. The village is delimited by the Tagus River on its northern bank, the Atlantic Ocean on the West and a mountain ridge that separates Trafaria from Almada city centre on the East. Despite its proximity to Lisbon, the *vila* is quite isolated from the capital, especially in terms of accessibility via public transportation.

Although there is no certain date for the origin of the village, we can date it back to the XVI century, when a first agglomeration of fishermen settled in the area. Over the centuries, fishing activities and the relationship of the locals with the Ocean have accompanied, and deeply influenced, the history and development of Trafaria. It is a relationship that still pervades the site, although globalisation, the intensive exploitation of the marine ecosystem, and waves of *touristification* have greatly changed, mostly depriving the social, cultural and economic fabric of the village. Back in history, Trafaria also hosted military and defence functions, adding on multiple layers of complexity in the definition of an identity which still remains somehow fragile and ambiguous, especially in its connection with a past of maritime power and colonialism, with the subsequent waves of immigration and emigration over centuries.

Indeed, the proximity to Lisbon has often represented a contradictory factor in the development of the village, bringing about waves of investment and disinvestment, settlements and abandonment. Today, the village accounts for a population of nearly 6.000 people, with high concentration of population with a migrant background, as well as with structural problems such as decaying infrastructure, unemployment, poverty and deprivation that particularly affect neighbourhoods such as the Segundo Torrão, Cova do Vapor, and Bairro dos Pescadores. In particular, the Segundo Torrão is one of the largest informal settlements in Portugal that is currently experiencing an escalation in the social conflict, due to recent evictions and plans of temporary resettlement which in many cases are being resisted by the local communities. However, Trafaria is also rich in cultural and social activities, with many formal and informal associations and community groups that daily contribute to keep the village and its traditions alive and vibrant. Similarly, Trafaria also hosts a number of historical buildings and architectural heritage, though some of them stand in a bad state of conservation.

| The Presidio and the IAT@T - NOVA Institute of Arts and Technology at Trafaria

Amongst the historical buildings, the Presidio stands as a symbol of the village's history. It is a 7-buildings complex built in 1565 to host mainly military and defence functions which have been generally maintained over centuries, until 1981 when the complex was finally abandoned. In 2020, after decades of abandonment, an agreement between the Municipality of Almada and NOVA University – one of the largest higher education institutions in Portugal – was signed, opening a new chapter in the history of the Presidio.

The redevelopment of the Presidio will see the establishment of NOVA Institute of Arts and Technology (IAT), transforming this iconic yet decaying complex into a pole of higher education, research and innovation dedicated to the intersection between arts and technology. The regeneration, which is expected to be completed by 2024, is part of the urban development strategy of Almada Municipality, aimed at boosting local economic development, fostering cultural and educational activities, and sparking a fresh approach to the requalification of public spaces hand in hand with the preservation and protection of the local heritage. The establishment of the IAT stands as an important vehicle for the delivery of the set strategy, particularly from the point of view of creating education, job and enterprise opportunities that can benefit the local communities, while attracting new publics, especially the younger generations.

The IAT will be the first university centre dedicated to cultural production and art in the Greater Lisbon region, with a specific focus on culture and heritage related. The development of the IAT is also understood as a driver for attracting investment and contributing to the renovation and development of basic infrastructure and services in Trafaria, thus generating positive cascading effects across the area and its surroundings. To attain this goal, NOVA University's Faculty of Science and Technology (FCT) and the School of Social Sciences and Humanities (FSCH) will work closely together to generate knowledge and value with a focus on sustainable impact for the local communities, while also showing a way forward to the creation of R&I poles on arts, culture and heritage in peripheral urban areas that can be both nationally and internationally relevant.

■ | Overall challenge and Innovation Missions in T-Factor

The overall challenge that orients the meanwhile strategy of the Trafaria pilot is understood as '*bridging the gap between Academia and society, contributing to unlock value and meaningful impact for the local communities*'. This challenge reflects the composition of the Local Coalition (which is formed by members of NOVA University, mainly from two different faculties), as well as the nature and objective of the redevelopment itself. As a higher education institution which is about to create a new location in an unusual and challenging context such as Trafaria, the topic of '*what challenge and for what possible benefits*' is necessarily framed as a question of how a University can positively contribute to pressing issues of sustainable urban development within its fundamental mission of education, research and innovation. This is particularly important for the specific context of Trafaria, where the variety, complexity and urgency of existing and emerging needs may put a question mark on what problems are to be prioritised for address, but also what a University can contribute to both in the relatively short term of T-Factor, and in the longer term of the IAT. As we will see later in the document, this also helps explain and critically reflect on the strategic choices (i.e. innovation missions) made by the Local Coalition, but also on the challenges and difficulties it has experienced along the way, particularly when it comes to the relationship between the meanwhile activities proposed so far vis-à-vis the rising tensions in Trafaria related to housing, waste management and basic infrastructure.

Within this context, the set challenge recognises that the development of the IAT can unlock a number of co-benefits especially across employment, educational and cultural dimensions, yet it also risks reinforcing dynamics of gentrification and uneven urban development that may exacerbate and accelerate the social conflict. At the same time, it recognises that for the IAT to become an integrated piece of the local urban fabric, an in-depth listening of the local communities is needed, hand in hand with the establishment of close relations and collaborations with the existing landscape of social and cultural initiatives in and around Trafaria. Accordingly, temporary uses are understood and leveraged to embrace and link these two aspects, engaging with the local communities to better understand the site and its heritage, anticipate educational and cultural activities that can become permanent, raise awareness and momentum around the regeneration plan, and overall contributing to weave people in places through the lens of cultural and creativity-led community building.

Three innovation missions contextualise and set the ground for temporary uses in Trafaria:

Mission 1: Shared, Locally rooted identities: This mission looks at temporary uses as ways to explore the history, memories and social and cultural significances that are present in Trafaria, engaging the local communities in a collective discovery, (re)appreciation and sharing of the key cultural dimensions that stand as the backbone of its own identity. Harvesting and collecting these stories is a fundamental step for the Local Coalition towards creating a strong identity for the IAT, protecting and promoting the heritage and the social and cultural values that exist on site. Besides, this mission is the entry point of the pilot to community-building, with the ultimate purpose of enhancing a widespread sense of solidarity and belonging that (re)connects people and places, while unlocking new types of both formal and informal relations and connections (i.e. Academia-local communities).

Mission 2: Innovative Education and Training: This mission understands temporary uses as ways to prototype and anticipate functions and activities that can become more permanent features of the future IAT. Given the nature of the IAT, the mission specifically looks at educational, knowledge and skills-oriented activities and programmes that explores the thematic focus of the IAT - i.e. arts, culture and technology in their various facets, and that can start providing short term opportunities of learning and skilling, while attracting young and creative energies and talent from Lisbon and the Almada sub-region.

Mission 3: Attractive & Accessible Area: This mission seeks to explore how temporary uses can contribute to make Trafaria more attractive and accessible, creating and/or testing basic services that can start addressing some of the urgent needs that are present in the area. However, as further explained later in the document, at the time of writing this report this mission still lacks of a specific intervention focus, mainly due to the difficulty for the Local Coalition in concretising ongoing conversations with the Municipality of Almada, in turn driven by a certain lack of agency and legitimacy of the University to have a concrete say on major issues such as housing and development of basic infrastructure.

Aerial view of the Presidio, Photo credits: NOVA University

TRAFARIA LISBON THEORY OF CHANGE

How can we bridge the gap between Academia and local communities and contribute to meaningful impact?

- #PROMPT USES: one off events that attract people in places
- #REGULAR USES: regular activities that retain people in places
- #STABLE USES: temporary uses that anchor people to places
- #COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE
- #INVESTMENT & FUNDING
- #SMART PLANNING, POLICY & REGULATION

Missions (if we)

Mission 1:
Shared, locally rooted identities

Mission 2:
Innovative education & training

Mission 3:
Attractive & accessible area

Figure 17: Theory of Change – Lisbon Trafaria

| Meanwhile Portfolio

According to the previously described missions, the meanwhile Portfolio of the pilot is built around two main streams of activities.

The first stream (reference Mission 1 'Shared, locally-rooted identities') develops a number of **cultural and creativity-led activities of community-building and action-research** that engage the local communities in a collective (re)discovery of the narratives, meanings, and stories of Trafaria. While working as the fundamental layer of activities that help establish direct connections and listen to a diversity of voices in the area, these activities are also propaedeutic to the development of one of the main temporary uses of the Portfolio, the so-called "**Bottom-Up Museum**". The Bottom-up Museum imagines the museum in a new light, being a kind of antithesis to what is generally understood by the word museum as we know it. Instead of experts deciding what the museum and its collection will be, it is the population themselves who get to choose and make the "collection". The museum begins without a building and fixed collection and is above all a social tool and an ongoing process. In this way, it is not a museum at all, and the population will create the new nomenclature. This entails ongoing engagement with the people of Trafaria to expose their cultural expression and collective memory. This becomes an avenue for fostering relationships, community development, a sense of belonging, and empowerment. These activities range from meetings, thematic gatherings creative experiences, centred on the values of the population, to interviews focused on the preservation of their memories. Throughout the process, materials coming from these interactions are collected. Concretely, the Bottom-up museum will consist of a virtual "document" of the whole process, hosted in an online platform called the Web of Stories.

The second stream (reference Mission 2 'Innovative Education and Training') focuses on **innovative training programs for master's and PhD students in the field of art and technology**. Two main activities - the Critical Futures programme and the Digital Media Festival - are envisaged to test and prototype some of the educational, cultural and knowledge exchange offers that the IAT may keep on organising beyond T-Factor, as a

way to bring in Trafaria new ways of understanding and exploring the intersection between arts, culture and technology, and the multiple innovations - including in terms of R&I topics, skills domains, business models for artistic and cultural production, amongst other aspects - it can unleash.

When it comes to Mission 3, this stream is yet to be defined in terms of concrete temporary use experiments. The Local Coalition started a conversation with the Municipality of Almada early in time in order to depict possible areas of integration and contribution to the local strategy of sustainable urban development. However, at present **there are no concrete roots defined for meanwhile intervention**, and new rounds of strategic conversations with the Municipality are required to scope out and fully unveil this mission.

Double clic to access the digital version of the portfolio

| Portfolio delivery: overview

In the time frame considered for the mid-term evaluation of T-Factor [20], the Local Coalition has delivered four main activities of the Portfolio: **Vida das Margens, Poetry Slam, and Nomadic territories** related to Mission 1, while **Critical Futures** part 1 is the main implemented activity for Mission 2.

Vida das Margens consisted of a cycle of three participatory events aimed at **harvesting stories and memories of Trafaria**. The events were delivered in different sites of the area (i.e. Café Convívio in the Segundo Torrão; Association Moradores da Cova do Vapor, Trafaria's cultural centre), in order to reach out to different communities and types of publics - senior citizens, young people, migrant people, mainly - and thus embracing a diversity of perspectives and voices. While supporting the ongoing process of listening and action-research from the NOVA team, Vida das Margens was also propaedeutic to the construction of the **Bottom-Up Museum**, as it allowed to collect materials and documentation for the ongoing digital archiving process. Vida das Margens was developed in close collaboration between the NOVA team, the Canto do Curiò Association and the local parish of Trafaria.

Poetry Slam was a poetry-based performance that involved young people of Trafaria (particularly from Segundo Torrão) in the exploration of **novel narratives and forms of expression at the intersection of words, voice and body**. Similarly to Vida das Margens, this activity aimed at engaging the community in the Segundo Torrão, proposing a form of cultural expression that could better fit with the forms of communication and self-expression of this audience, while giving voice to their perceptions and feelings about the area. The Poetry Slam developed through two main phases: a preliminary workshop aimed at preparing and training the participants, and a second phase which saw an open competition with symbolic awards.

[20] Generally, the period considered in this report is February 2022 - October 2022, which is the overall time frame in which the T-Factor Pilots started to implement and run their temporary use strategies. However, it should be noted that the insights and results (especially more qualitative results) captured in this report also refer to the preceding period (the whole 2021), particularly when it comes to preliminary activities of engagement, initial scoping and co-design that started to set the ground for implementing and iterating temporary uses and activities.

Photo credits: Dario Marmo

Internal view of the Presidio, Photo credits: NOVA University

Nomadic Territories consisted of a cycle of four different walksapes [21] aimed at convening both Trafaria's residents and first-time visitors in a collective discovery of the most iconic and symbolic sites of Trafaria, through the facilitation of expert guides. Based on routes defined by the invited participants, Trafaria was crossed by different perspectives and approached not only as a territory with specific geographic and physical features, but also as a place that embodies stories and memories, as a political and social space. The walksapes went through the following routes: Walk 1 - Our beach, which is the river, our sea which is home; Walk 2 - Journey to the In-Between - Centre & Periphery; Walk 3 - Os passos em volta – Trafaria; Walk 4 - Caminhar em rede.

Critical Futures is a programme of thematic seminars focused on arts, critical theories, and political ecologies. Mainly addressed to NOVA's students of the course on Advanced Themes in Artistic Studies, a PhD seminar which is part of the NOVA PhD program in Art Studies, the seminars were also opened to the general public. A first round of seminars took place in March-April 2022, exploring the theme of 'Curating and Social Practice'. This series of six workshops was delivered online in collaboration with Prof. Alison Green, a Senior Lecturer on BA Culture, Criticism and Curation from University of the Arts London. A second round were held between May-June 2022 on the topic of 'Active citizenship(s)' towards communal spaces of care'; the seminar was curated and delivered by Prof. Basia Sliwinska, Senior Lecturer in Cultural and Historical Studies at the University of the Arts London. To complement the online dynamic, a gathering and a walk in Trafaria, together with both professors have also been organised by NOVA.

More generally, all these activities fit within a broader process of local engagement and listening to a diversity of voices undertaken by the Local Coalition over time, which included meetings with local associations, informal community groups, cultural institutions and the Almada Municipality - to convene visions and perspectives around the site, as well as to start communicating and positioning the T-Factor project and the broader plan of regeneration and creation of the IAT.

[21] A walkscape is a walk to explore an area, a landscape, a territory and learn about its transformations. Typically, a walkscape invites people to look, listen, draw, write, photograph, collect, store and finally reconstruct the history and identity of a place through hidden tracks and seemingly insignificant details.

Stakeholders and Beneficiaries

For the delivery of the activities, the LC activated a number of collaborations with local stakeholders. The Trafaria pilot mainly worked with stakeholders that have a strong link with the local communities. In fact, **NOVA is an outsider to the local context**, and the temporary use strategy is largely understood as the opportunity for NOVA to enter in contact with local actors, understand existing and emerging needs, while starting to communicate the future IAT and inquire into its possible benefits for Trafaria and beyond.

Vida das Margens was co-organized with local associations such as **Canto do Curió** (based in Segundo Torrão), **Madame Faber Commission** (based in Madame Faber's district) and **Margem de Coragem/Biblioteca da Cova do Vapor** (based in Cova do Vapor's neighbourhood). Furthermore, the Trafaria pilot collaborated with private organisations such as **Teatro do Silêncio**, **Atelier Artéria**, **Associação Descampado Ocupado** and individual experts in the design and delivery of Nomadic territories. Critical Futures and the Poetry slam were both led by stakeholders from academia, with the collaboration of professors from the **University of the Arts London**, who is also a partner of the T-Factor project.

The activities managed to engage with a relatively large diversity of publics. Vida das Margens mainly addressed **residents in Trafaria**, Cova do Vapor, II^o Torrao and M.me Faber neighbourhoods. The Poetry Slam brought together residents, particularly **young people**, and **cultural organisations** across different neighbourhoods, although with a focus on the Segundo Torrao. Nomadic territories invited community members, residents, academic staff, and private organisations throughout the walks. Lastly, Critical futures mainly addressed **University students and academic staff** from both NOVA and UAL Universities.

**Activity 1:
Vida das Margens****Prompt use****27/03/2022
29/05/2022**

Target groups: senior citizens, young people, people with migrant background and other publics in Trafaria and its nearby surroundings

Main beneficiaries:

143 participants in total; mainly Trafaria residents and people from specific local communities (neighbourhoods, social and cultural associations).

Collaborators:
Local cultural associations, faith organisations.

Keywords:
#solidarity & belonging
#local identity & heritage

**Activity 3:
Poetry Slam****Prompt use****19/06/2022
26/06/2022**

Target groups: young people mainly from Segundo Torrao

Main beneficiaries:

98 participants in the preparatory workshop and 90 participants in the open competition.

Collaborators: Poetry Slam experts and residents associations

Keywords:
#local identity & heritage
#solidarity & belonging
#agency & legitimacy

**Activity 4: Nomadic
territories - Walkscapes****Prompt use****2021-2022**

Target groups: various types of groups from Trafaria and first-time visitors from surrounding areas, including from Lisbon

Main beneficiaries:

104 participants, mainly Trafaria's residents and first-time visitors.

Collaborators: Expert guides and local cultural and social associations

Keywords:
#local identity & heritage
#solidarity & belonging

**Activity 2:
Critical futures seminar****April 2022 - June 2022****Regular use**

Target groups: University students and academic staff; general interested publics.

20 participants
University students and academic staff

Collaborators:
University of the Arts London

Keywords:
#learning & skilling
#creativity & talent

Contribution to impact at mission level - Main activities' results

In the paragraphs that follow, we provide an overview of the main results achieved through the activities described earlier, mainly extracted from online surveys addressed to the beneficiaries involved, observation templates and informal interviews.

Enhanced social connection and sense of belonging

Figure 18: outcome proxy for Nomadic territories

The evaluation of Vida das Margens, Poetry Slam and Nomadic Territories indicates that all these activities were beneficial when it comes to **strengthening a sense of personal connectedness and belonging to Trafaria**. The activities also turned out to be a relevant gateway for the participants to get to know each other and **discover the complex identity of the site**. As stated by a participant during an evaluation interview: *“One thing is to experience Trafaria through its food offer, the boats, the local stores and small retails... but exploring it through its culture opens to new perspectives and understandings”*. In particular, the evaluation of Nomadic territories revealed that the presence of local residents during the walk was an added value, as it allowed the participants to know personal and living stories of the site that in turn helped **create meaning and an engaging narrative around Trafaria**. The Poetry Slam also led to an increase in the perceived **feeling of connectivity and belonging** of the participants, as reported through the interviews conducted. Moreover, this activity helped perceive Trafaria as **less isolated**, as it involved people from outside Trafaria through a creative and engaging form of individual expression and exchange. Furthermore, a common comment related to the participation of teenagers, which, according to the comments, is quite a rare sight in Trafaria, where you can mostly see young kids and the elder population.

Awareness of the existing heritage and identity

Vida das Margens, Poetry Slam and Nomadic territories were reported as significant activities when it comes to the **awareness of both the natural and cultural heritage of Trafaria**. Some interviewees noticed how often the local heritage and identity is safeguarded and kept alive by the older population, with the risk that if not properly transmitted to young people it will soon vanish. A number of symbolic buildings and activities such as the Presidio, the Casino, the local festivities and the typical restaurants often emerged as key elements of Trafaria’s heritage and identity. Furthermore, some interviewees pointed to the contribution of the activities (in particular, Nomadic Territories) in bringing external and first-time visitors to Trafaria, mainly from nearby areas and from Lisbon. Finally, the activities helped create more awareness and knowledge on the redevelopment and future IAT,

Shared sensemaking of pressing local challenges

Particularly in the evaluation of Vida das Margens, respondents reported on positive outcomes mostly related to **shared and collaborative sensemaking and understanding of the main urban development challenges** that affect Trafaria and its surroundings. The activity allowed the participants to reflect on these challenges, as well as on their evolution and transformation over time. Major issues such as high tides in some areas of Trafaria (especially Segundo Torrão and Cova do Vapor; the relationship with the Ocean and the marine ecosystem; the lack of social and physical connections between different neighbourhoods of the area; the scarcity in cultural and social events for younger publics and the lack of opportunities for valorising the local heritage were all challenges discussed. This somehow proved to contribute to awareness-raising, while also providing the NOVA team with valuable insights and indications for the planning of the IAT and its future identity and meaning.

Empowerment and capacity in participatory and collaborative processes

Particularly for the Poetry Slam, the interviewee stated that *'for people to feel empowered to engage in the area, the local community needs to feel like the area belongs to them, and the space is being rehabilitated with their needs in mind'*. Participants generally perceived the poetry slam as worthwhile and felt more **empowered to collaborate with each other**. Furthermore, one of the interviewees stated that *'Trafaria can be perceived as a small village, everybody knows each other at least from sight. Since it's a quiet village, these activities help people get together and interact on a deeper and more intimate level'*. Lastly, as a result of the evaluation, the Trafaria pilot clearly got the sense that participants are eager to have a more active voice regarding the planning and cultural activities going on in Trafaria; similarly, they also expressed the need to be more aware of the plans and proposals of the future IAT, and how it can create opportunities for the local and surrounding communities.

Outcome proxy:
Skills and capacities in collaborative and participatory placemaking after the activity (score out of 5)

Figure 19: outcome proxy Critical Futures part 1

A similar result can be mentioned for the seminars within the context of the Critical Futures programme. For this activity, a score of 3,3 out of 5 was measured related to the question: *"How would you rate your skills and capacities in "collaborative and participatory placemaking" after participating in Artistic Studies Seminar?* When asked about the most valuable aspects contributing to capacity-building, the respondents stated that the contribution of the (international) speakers was an added value. *'The debates were very inspiring'*, says one of the respondents, who stated that *'the main contribution came through debates, intimacy and communal matters'*. The participants were generally satisfied by the programme.

How much was agreed with the following statements (score out of 5)	Score out of 5
I have learnt about the context and place of Trafaria	4,1
I am more aware to the colonial dynamics that are present in doing this kind of work of cross- and trans-cultural, or cross-class encounters, and the importance of recognizing difference.	3,8
I've encountered some ways of reading together in ways that enable different engagements and different expressions	4
I've explored some 'tools' for me to work with.	4
I've had the opportunity to discuss and learn about ideas care, active citizenship(s) and the commons to understand how we create relationships with spaces	4,2
I've participated in a collective dialogue by a walk in an imaginary community and create an itinerary for a collective 'we' that accounts for the co-nutrition, co-growth and co-existence for all.	3,7

Unleashing creativity and talent

The Poetry Slam was said to have enhanced the creativity and talent of participants. The workshop allowed the participant to learn about 'every corner of the poetry slam world' and to build their confidence to participate in a poetry slam event. The poetry slam was also identified by the participants as a good example of how co-creative activities, that involve different stakeholders, can have an effect on the creativity of people and that they could create partnerships in the long run. Another interviewee stated that 'each new event or activity', such as the poetry slam, is welcomed at Trafaria since it can lead to enhanced interactions between people and ultimately be the basis of a formation of a stronger community'. Furthermore, the interactions between the participants can trigger creativity. In the same interview, another participant stated that the poetry slam can be viewed as a 'form of people to express what they feel or think about experiences they had in life'.

| Contribution to impact at Pilot level

The section describes the pilot level changes and considerations gathered through the 'Critical Friend' interview. As anticipated, the interview is aimed at exploring if and how the activities undertaken during the period of reference are contributing towards long term outcomes and impacts of urban regeneration, particularly from the point of view of enhanced strategic, operational and relational dimensions (ref. Methodology section). In the following paragraph we report on the main strengths and weaknesses that emerged through the interview. A self-assessment scoreboard filled out by the Local Coalition is provided at the end of the section. It is important to highlight that the insights and reflections reported in this chapter do not only capture the voice and perceptions of the Local Coalition; they also include and integrate the results of the ongoing observation and support developed by the Transformation Agency over time, in its role of 'critical friend' of the pilot.

The pilot in Trafaria is operating in a highly challenging and complex socio-economic context where **tensions and social conflicts are currently escalating, due to recent evictions and rising housing problems** in some neighbourhoods (particularly the Segundo Torrao) which risk exacerbating dynamics of deprivation and exclusion.

The identity of the site is changing rapidly; what was once a characteristic village of fishermen with a relatively self-sufficient economy, has been evolving over decades in a contradictory relation with the near Lisbon, suffering from waves of settlement and abandonment, investment and disinvestment. In the recent past, Trafaria has seen the emergence of dynamics of *touristification* which are bringing about new types of population (including foreigners) and

renewed attention to the area, creating opportunities for local development but also **major risks of displacing the existing communities.**

The close relationship of Trafaria's residents with the Ocean is largely at the heart of the identity of the site, and yet it increasingly shapes through **widespread feelings of fear and uncertainty vis-à-vis the climate crisis and rising threats to safety, health, sustainability and, overall, liveability.**

Furthermore, Trafaria is rich in both tangible and intangible heritage, and yet the bad state of conservation of many historical buildings - coupled with an ageing population which is often the guardian of local memories, put such a **heritage at risk of loss.**

Within this context, and considering the core mission of the IAT but also the fact that NOVA is an **outsider in the territory**, the meanwhile strategy is primarily framed by the Local Coalition as a process of **knowing and be known in the area**, activating temporary interventions that could start establishing bonds with the social and cultural 'hubs' in Trafaria, making sense of the local identity and heritage, understanding needs and opportunities, while contributing to communicate and position the T-Factor project and anticipating a sense of the future IAT.

The activities implemented so far generally show a positive progress throughout these dimensions. In the first instance, **several partnerships have been established** with different degrees of formalisation, particularly with social, cultural and residents associations such as Ensaios & Diálogos (EDA), Canto do Curiò, Marchas, Margem de Coragem, Moradores Bairro Madame Faber, but also with known artists such as the composer and designer Victor Gama. Generally, all the activities have been implemented in close collaboration with these local organisations, allowing the Local Coalition to better integrate the proposed meanwhile activities within the social and cultural landscape, but also to strengthen engagement and outreach. The collaboration with EDA Association is deemed to be particularly important for the near future evolution of meanwhile interventions, due to its deep knowledge of the territory and its capital of temporary use practices already developed on site. However,

it is also a relationship which requires more strategic and long term thinking, so as to fully enable the shift from a transactional to a fully transformative alliance. Overall, as main effects of this networking process, there is positive evidence emerging across aspects such as a **growingly recognised presence of T-Factor and NOVA within the area**, as well as **enhanced awareness and knowledge by the local communities about the regeneration plan**.

Furthermore, the activities generally showed a positive contribution to the emergence and **collective (re)appreciation of the local tangible and intangible heritage and identity** - a key step along the Mission "Shared and locally-rooted identities".

The activities brought in Trafaria **new cultural and social offers** that in turn convened different types of publics that would not otherwise meet or interact, including first-time visitors who had the chance to explore and discover Trafaria and its history. The activities also created **opportunities of expression and participation for deprived communities** such as the ones in the Segundo Torrao, especially by involving the younger generations in forms of cultural expression that could better match their type of language and communication. Activities such as Vida das Margens and Poetry Slam were key in providing otherwise lacking opportunities for the local communities to openly discuss and share fears and feelings about the future of Trafaria and the redevelopment of the Presidio. Similarly, they somehow contributed to **explore the fundamental topic of bottom-up agency and legitimacy in placemaking processes, although this aspect remains highly critical and challenging well beyond the T-Factor project**. Nonetheless, the Local Coalition attempted to explicitly address this issue, particularly by means of establishing a Committee involving leaders from local associations in charge of supervising and steering the process of the Bottom-Up Museum. Lastly, the activities were finally propaedeutic in harvesting perceptions, memories and stories that can be showcased in the Bottom-Up Museum, as a future cultural commons for Trafaria.

"Through T-Factor, we are trying to build relationships between people, raise awareness about the existing needs, empower people, and create a

sense of belonging" (Local Coalition).

When it comes to Mission 2 'Innovative Education & Training', to date the pilot has addressed this mission by means of thematic (online) seminars mainly addressed to NOVA (Phd) students, yet opened to the public. This activity helped introduce University students to the reality of Trafaria, through the lenses of how arts, culture, and creativity-led practices can contribute to protect and valorise local heritage while unleashing novel forms of academia-community collaboration.

Although this was a preliminary and relatively small activity, it helped explore the opportunity for Trafaria to become a living context for novel research and action research, which would eventually help raise visibility to the area and its heritage among the academic population.

From a strategic and relational perspective, **one critical point emerges when it comes to the relationship with the Municipality of Almada**. Indeed, the IAT can be a powerful lever for the concrete delivery of Almada's urban development strategy. There are close relationships and ongoing dialogue when it comes to the future IAT, and the Municipality is trying to support the Local Coalition within the scope of T-Factor, particularly by **providing access to alternative spaces for meanwhile interventions**. Currently, the renovation of the Presidio is experiencing some delays, and there is no possibility of meanwhile access due to the very bad state of conservation of the complex and safety and security risks. An alternative space next to the Presidio has been offered to the Local Coalition and to other actors (including EDA Association), thus solving a major problem which would otherwise limit the pilot seriously. Yet, when it comes to how meanwhile interventions could contribute to address basic needs such as housing, clean water and sanitation, or lack of basic infrastructure - all urgent needs in Trafaria - the conversations between the Municipality and NOVA **have not yet materialised in concrete and agreed areas of exploration**. De facto, Mission 3 of the portfolio - the one explicitly addressing accessibility and attractiveness - **still stands vague and mostly unaddressed**, thus requiring more work and strategic thinking. However, the recent situation of evictions and temporary resettlements in the Segundo Torrao are possibly making the

conversation harder and more sensitive, as it risks **escalating frictions and tensions** all along the choice of the Municipality to host a University in Trafaria, the presence of NOVA as an outsider in the area, and some communities feeling unheard in their fundamental needs. Currently, this is a very critical situation that is requiring the Local Coalition to be particularly careful and aware of the context, not least by **questioning the extent of agency and legitimacy that NOVA may have in addressing or contributing to address these major issues**. Nevertheless, there are ongoing efforts in place to discuss possible areas of viable actions, particularly by leveraging the experience and learning of some T-Factor's partners, in particular the University of the Arts London and La Friche within the T-Lab 1 "Art, Culture and Creativity".

When it comes to more operational dimensions of overall pilot management and running, there are both positive and critical elements.

First, the Local Coalition is substantially formed by one organisation, NOVA, yet it involves a relatively large number of professors, researchers and management staff from two main faculties. The overall (more stable) team comprises nearly eight people, with richness in terms of thematic expertise across arts, culture and tech-related domains. While this indeed stands as an added value especially for creative engagement practices in the meanwhile, along the run it has also created divergent perspectives, sometimes **slowing down time to shared decision-making and collaborative action**. This aspect may also help explain a certain difficulty observed by the Transformation Agency in the collaboration of the pilot with the T-Labs. In this respect, conversations and rooms of collaborations have been discussed over time particularly with T-Lab 1, which also led to two field visits of the T-Lab team. However, to date the pilot-T-Labs collaboration requires more scoping and concrete focus, possibly by means of a more tailored and strategic support of the Lab in addressing the most critical aspects of the pilot as mentioned in the previous passage.

An additional criticality relates to **funding and spending**. Generally, the whole Portfolio is sustained by the T-Factor (EU) funding, with no additional sources leveraged so far or planned to be leveraged. More than that, as typically with public bodies, spending processes are often rigid, highly bureaucratic and time consuming, posing a **serious limit vis-à-vis the**

flexibility and quickness in action required by temporary interventions. Although the Local Coalition managed to address and overcome the issue at best, this has indeed affected - and is still affecting the pilot, not least by bringing **feelings of limitation in possibilities of novel placemaking practices in the meanwhile.** Lastly, we shall also mention the issue of **accessibility to the Presidio** due to delays of construction works. This is a structural problem which will limit the possibility of prototyping IAT's spaces and functions in the meanwhile. However, the Local Coalition managed to find meaningful solutions, including by leveraging alternative spaces next to the Presidio, but also organising temporary activities across symbolic sites of Trafaria, which may in turn be a valuable approach for reaching out to communities and individuals who otherwise would not be reached nor engaged.

Overall, the Trafaria pilot seems to be in a good stage of development when it comes to 'know and be known' in the local context, as well as in terms of positively contributing to community engagement through the lenses of identity and heritage. Most of the communities engaged so far are demonstrating **interest and willingness to contribute to T-Factor and to the future IAT,** which in turn may help unlock more distributed agency and legitimacy in collaborative placemaking and thus establish fundamental, enabling conditions for meaningful impact. Moreover, the ongoing Academia-community collaboration may turn out to be a fundamental lever for (re)imagining and expanding Universities' core mission towards goals of sustainable urban development, making it closer to local needs and priorities.

Towards the next period, there are a number of both strategic and operational aspects for the Local Coalition to be prioritised in its own T-Factor's agenda, including a **more goal-oriented conversation with the Municipality of Almada, enhanced strategic thinking on some pivotal collaborations with local cultural and social associations, as well as a better scoping of how international collaboration within T-Factor (particularly with T-Labs) can be leveraged in address to local issues.**

Furthermore, the upcoming iterations of already developed and new activities shall be oriented as much as possible to further strengthen outreach and engagement, involving new communities and types of publics over time from both Trafaria and outside the site, with a special emphasis on the migrant communities living on site. More broadly, while the Bottom-Up Museum can be a powerful and concrete legacy of T-Factor that contributes to local identity, heritage preservation and visibility, a point of attention is on **additional yet connected experimentations that can reinforce value creation in the area,** leaving a meaningful legacy that the future IAT can keep on nurturing and expanding towards the long run.

	Dimensions	1	2	3	4
STRATEGIC	Positioning & Reputation	The portfolio poorly contributes to enhancing the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is not properly valorised.	The portfolio partially contributes to the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is considered but not a driver in the cultural and social evolution of the area	The portfolio brings a great visibility to the area and raises awareness about its heritage	The portfolio has provided the area with a new identity and its heritage is appreciated by diverse audiences.
	Attractiveness	The portfolio is raising limited interest and struggles to attract diverse audiences and target groups.	The portfolio raises the interest of target groups and engages with an unvaried audience on a local level.	The portfolio is compelling for all target groups and attracts a diverse audience both locally and from the surroundings	The portfolio is compelling and raises the interest of new groups and audiences both locally and from the surroundings
	Relevance & Opportunity	The portfolio addresses in a limited way local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are neither investigated nor pursued.	The portfolio addresses some local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are identified	The portfolio inclusively responds to pressing local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Expands opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets	The portfolio is adjusted to address new emerging challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. creates a number of new opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets.
OPERATIONAL	Planning & Delivery Capacities	The portfolio has limited available resources and the retrieval of missing resources is yet to be defined.	The portfolio has some available resources and activities that could retrieve resources are under definition.	The portfolio is financially sustainable and activities/fundraising initiatives to retrieve them are in progress .	The portfolio is financially sustainable and has retrieved most fundings.
	Resilience, Flexibility & Adaptability	The portfolio has not identified emerging needs and opportunities that could have influenced the masterplan	The portfolio has identified some emerging needs and opportunities but strong 'evidence' is missing	Emerging needs and opportunities have been identified and masterplan adjustments are under definition	Emerging needs and opportunities have been fully defined and the masterplan has been adapted accordingly
	Interoperability & Connectivity	The pilot is not aware of other initiatives in the area and has not identified relevant policies and plans that could contribute to the meanwhile strategy	The portfolio is aligned with some initiatives in the area or policies and plans relevant to the meanwhile use strategy have been analysed.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are almost established. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy supported by policy programmes.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are concrete. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy is contributing and supported by policy programmes.
RELATIONAL	Impact time & Depth (Too early to assess)	The portfolio results are requiring more time than expected and not all results and impacts will be achieved	The portfolio results are timely and most results and impacts are expected to be achieved.	The portfolio results have been achieved earlier than expected allowing to add additional uses for different groups.	The portfolio is involving and aligning around local innovation missions with a plethora of diverse stakeholders.
	Agency & Legitimacy	The portfolio does not contribute to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors to involve to build multi-sectoral coalitions have not been identified	The portfolio contributes in a limited way to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors have been identified but must define how to involve them in multi-sectoral coalitions	The portfolio contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established	The portfolio strongly contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An inclusive array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established
	Legacy, Sustainability & Scalability	The portfolio does not have a clear legacy.	The portfolio creates certain conditions for long term legacy but remains context-specific (not transferable).	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become more sustainable in the long-term. E.g. Scalability is being investigated	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become fully scalable or transferrable.

ZORROTZAURRE BILBAO

ZORROTZAURRE, BILBAO

| About Zorrotzaurre (ZZ) and the redevelopment

Zorrotzaurre is an artificial island located within the Deusto district of Bilbao. For decades, Zorrotzaurre has been an important **industrial site** specialised in the iron, steel and shipbuilding industry. The decline of the area started in the 1980s as the consequence of the global industrial crisis which forced many local industries to close or relocate elsewhere. During the subsequent period, the area went through progressive disinvestment and abandonment; iconic industrial buildings such as **Artiach** and **Coromina** are still there witnessing what was once the skyline of Zorrotzaurre, and yet they also show the degradation and decay experienced in the area over decades. Nowadays, barely 500 people live in the area, which is one of the most deprived and with lower incomes of Bilbao. However, ZZ is also home to a diversity of **cultural and creative activities and spaces** that in recent years have located in former industrial sites, contributing to the emergence of a “meanwhile” that has provided Zorrotzaurre with social and cultural life, as well as with economic activity.

The Zorrotzaurre project is the most recent, major redevelopment in Bilbao. The regeneration is meant to transform the island into a mixed used space where housing and knowledge-based economic activities will coexist side by side – further boosting the culture-led transformation of the city that started in the 90s with the Guggenheim Museum. The masterplan was designed by the Anglo-Iraqi architect **Zaha Hadid** in 2004 and further revised in 2007 to incorporate the full opening of the Canal. It envisions Zorrotzaurre as a **sustainable, innovative, knowledge-based island** that will have life 24/7. Following the narrative of “becoming an island”, the plan converts the waterfronts into pathways with green spaces and educational, sports and cultural services, and it lays out housing in strips, perpendicular to the river and the canal, to ensure that everywhere has a sight of water. In terms of environmental sustainability, the island will be equipped with flood risk reduction systems, zero-emissions buildings, 100% electric public transport, and a pumping and cleaning system for street cleaning and irrigation.

| Overall challenge and innovation missions in T-Factor

Zorrotzaurre is currently the largest redevelopment in Bilbao, which aims to transform this former industrial site into a landmark of innovation, with a special focus on cultural and creative industries. Prestigious universities such as **IED Kunsthall**, **DigiPen**, **Mondragon University** have recently settled in the island and others will soon come, joining an already existing ecosystem of cultural and creative grassroots organisations that in the past 10 years have contributed to keeping the site alive and vibrant. This will provide the opportunity to further boost the transformation of the whole of Bilbao from an industrial to a knowledge-based and cultural urban hub. Yet, the redevelopment of Zorrotzaurre holds massive challenges. Not only is there a question mark around whether the regeneration will be able to replicate the well-known **Bilbao's effect**; a key question is also around the future of the organisations and communities that are already active on site, and how we can mitigate the risk of disrupting and displacing their relational capital and social and economic value. In this context, the overarching challenge for the T-Factor pilot in Bilbao is to explore **how temporary uses can drive novel forms of multi-stakeholder collaboration**, particularly through ‘**co-creation alliances**’ between **Universities and grassroots initiatives** that can contribute to build a **diverse, pluralistic and creative urban fabric**. This broad and complex challenge comprises a number of key issues spotted during the first phases of exploration and early engagement in T-Factor, including the **fragility and isolation of cultural and creative actors already on site**; a widespread **feeling of uncertainty and fear about the future of the island** and associated risks of **displacement and disruption** of the existing economic and social capital; the general **lack of basic services and amenities** coupled with **low standards of living**; difficult accessibility and movement across the island.

With this overarching challenge in mind, the ZZ pilot works in address to the following three innovation missions:

Mission 1 / Triggering collaboration: This mission stands as the core of the meanwhile strategy in ZZ, as it seeks to create the conditions and the proper spaces and tools for strengthening the collaboration between Universities and grassroots initiatives. More in detail, this mission leverages the meanwhile in ZZ as a testbed for novel 'civic curricula' that address local challenges of urban development, focussing on the design of new learning and teaching methodologies that can better link theory and design practice on the ground, while steering the latter towards urban transformation and sustainable change.

Mission 2 / Collaborative & Participatory Governance: Developing collaborative and participatory schemes of governance for the innovation ecosystem is largely perceived as a key step for the success of the redevelopment and the creation of a more inclusive, resilient, and trust-based framework of regeneration. This mission seeks to explore viable options for ZZ, taking inspiration from models of collaborative governance at district level already existing across European cities.

Mission 3 / Enabling Regulation: Developing clearer and more reliable regulations for temporary uses is another area of experimentation that could support both existing and future cultural and creative initiatives in the island and in the broader city, giving impetus to the meanwhile as a viable approach to bottom-up placemaking.

Piugaz Climbing School, Photo Credits: Bilbao Ekintza

ZORROTZAURRE BILBAO THEORY OF CHANGE

How can we foster an Innovative ecosystem between grassroots movements and HEIs?

- #PROMPT USES: one off events that attract people in places
- #REGULAR USES: regular activities that retain people in places
- #STABLE USES: temporary uses that anchor people to places
- #COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE
- #INVESTMENT & FUNDING
- #SMART PLANNING, POLICY & REGULATION

Missions (if we)

Mission 1:
Triggering Collaboration

Mission 2:
Collaborative & Participatory Governance

Mission 3:
Enabling Regulation for
Meanwhile Uses

By (Portfolio of temporary activities)

PROMPT
Co- design
workshops

PROMPT
High level policy
event

#REGULAR & STABLE
#FUNDING
Call for meanwhile
initiatives 2

REGULAR & STABLE
#FUNDING
Call for meanwhile
initiatives 1

#REGULAR & STABLE
#FUNDING
Call for meanwhile
initiatives 3

#COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE
Collaborative Governance Model
(Proof of Concept)

#SMART PLANNING,
POLICY & REGULATION
Temporary Uses
Regulatory Framework

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

Contributing to

And eventually in

This will result in

Figure 20: Theory of Change - Zorrotzaurre Bilbao

| Meanwhile Portfolio

ZZ's portfolio envisages three main clusters of specific yet connected activities, each linked to the missions explained in the previous section.

At the core of the portfolio stands the **meanwhile co-creation programme**: an urban challenges-driven programme that involves three local universities (i.e. **Mondragon University, University of Deusto and IED Kunsthal**), a number of local grassroots organisations and experts from T-Factor in the delivery of novel learning and co-creation paths ultimately addressed to students. The programme is structured into **three thematic challenges - climate adaptation and resilience, circularity, and sociality & wellbeing**, - that represent the general briefs for students in the design and prototyping of temporary uses. The overall purpose of the programme is to activate and create synergies between the capacities and knowledge that already exist in the area, in order to give life to a lively community of practice and place in Zorrotzaurre.

Next to this core activity, ZZ's portfolio envisages a **combination of research, design and engagement activities** respectively related to Mission 2 and 3, that we understand as 'enabling conditions' for long term collaborations in ZZ. For Mission 2, the portfolio's entry point is a research stream that looks at pioneering cases of collaborative governance across different districts in European cities. This is followed by a series of local events and workshops aimed at discussing the initial research insights, and understanding how these can be turned into **recommendations or even proofs of concept** for the future governance of ZZ's innovation ecosystem. Similarly, mission 3 envisages a stream of research and engagement activities that can support the development of a clearer regulatory framework for temporary uses in ZZ and beyond. However, it should be noted that **this third stream of work (and broadly the mission) is currently under discussion for a possible re-definition**. In the recent past, the redevelopment of ZZ has been experiencing a rapid acceleration with the purchase of some industrial buildings by the Basque government; the fear of displacement is now becoming a reality for many

of the local grassroots that are on site, as in the case of the **Escuela de Creación Cinematográfica de Bilbao (ECCBI)**. This situation is likely to further exacerbate the social conflict in the island, and is thus requiring T-Factor to acknowledge this rapid change and evolve accordingly. Currently, the pilot is evaluating the opportunity to reframe Mission 3 as a way for convening all the grassroots together, so as to make **shared proposals for a clearer, more transparent and meaningful transition plan in the island**. A key point for both activities in Mission 2 and 3 is that they both insist on the active involvement of local policy-makers, as a key precondition for trust, dialogue and collaboration towards a fair and sustainable future of Zorrotzaurre.

Double clic to access the digital version of the Portfolio on Miro

Portfolio delivery: overview

In the time frame considered for the mid-term evaluation of T-Factor [22], the Local Coalition has organised three main activities relevant to the portfolio: 1. **Collaborative Governance Workshop** (reference Mission 2); 2. **Innovation Ecosystem Analysis** (reference Mission 2); 3. **Innovation Jam** (reference Mission 1). Although these activities were delivered in address to specific missions of the Portfolio, it should be noted that they were designed and delivered so as to bring meaningful insights and contributions across all missions, and in turn to the broader challenge addressed in T-Factor that is to foster trust creation and collaboration across the different stakeholders and communities that are mostly at play in the redevelopment of the island. Furthermore, it is worth highlighting that in October 2022 the Local Coalition officially **started the meanwhile co-creation programme**; however, this key activity (regular use) of the Portfolio is not captured in this report as it will run until June 2023.

The **Collaborative Governance Workshop** represented a major milestone and follow up moment after the development of a research stream on collaborative governance models across European cities, led by TU Dortmund University as part of the support provided by T-Lab 6 ‘Social Innovation and Inclusion’ to the ZZ pilot [23]. The workshop, co-organised by Bilbao Ekintza and TU Dortmund University, consisted of a two-day event involving - and addressed to - **local decision makers** in Bilbao, aimed at fostering a critical discussion about possible outlines of a collaborative governance model for the island and district of Zorrotzaurre. The first day was organised at Euskalduna Palace of Bilbao (one of the major congress locations in Bilbao) and was attended by high level decision makers at the Municipality of Bilbao. Representatives from collaborative governance models applied in **Barcelona, Gothenburg, Dortmund, Copenhagen** were invited and participated as speakers. Day 1 was also attended by a delegation of T-Factor’s partners from Italy, which for the occasion was accompanied by a group of policymakers including the vice-mayors of Florence and Prato, the Councillor of Urban Planning

and the General Director of Urban Planning and Development of the Tuscany Region. Day 2 was instead conceived as a more restricted event for the top level planning and decision-making of the ZZ redevelopment, with a more focused conversation on the regeneration plan and its possible connections with temporary uses and collaborative governance models. Both days were facilitated by a senior expert from ARUP, one of the major consultancies across the globe on sustainable urban development.

[22] As explained in the Introduction, the period considered in this report is February 2022 - October 2022. However, it should be noted that the insights and results (especially more qualitative results) captured in this report also refer to the preceding period of early engagement and co-design of temporary uses, in order to reflect on the overall journey of the pilot towards inclusive, sustainable and thriving urban regeneration.

[23] The report can be found at this link: <https://www.t-factor.eu/collaborative-governance-models-for-district-management-2/>

The **Innovation Ecosystem Analysis** consisted of a social network analysis on cultural and creative industries in Bilbao and within the specific context of Zorrotzaurre. This activity was led by **Bottom-Up.City**, a German start-up with expertise in geo-social data analysis, activated by the City of Dortmund and TU Dortmund University as part of their support to Bilbao within the umbrella of T-Lab 6. With this work, the aim was to provide the grassroots initiatives and other key stakeholders surrounding the Local Coalition (such as Universities and local decision makers) with insights and evidences on the social and relational capital of cultural and creative actors in Bilbao, and more importantly within the context of Zorrotzaurre. More in detail, three key aspects were explored through the study: 1) The Social Capital mobilizable for/by Zorrotzaurre through its ecosystem; 2) The activities in the Culture & Creative Industries in Bilbao; 3) the topics mostly at stake, outreach capacities and influential actors. The ecosystem analysis started in May 2022 and was finalised in October 2022. Results and insights will feed the upcoming activities across Mission 1 and 2 especially, providing the grassroots with evidence to reinforce their positioning and collaboration towards a bottom-up cultural and creative ecosystem in Zorrotzaurre, while also informing the work to be delivered with students within the meanwhile co-creation programme.

Figure 21: Outreach capacity of Zorrotzaurre's Cultural and Creative Ecosystem, credits: Bottom-Up.City

Top 20 Hashtags Zorrotzaurre

Top 20 Hashtags Zorrotzaurre (Secondary Network)

Figure 22: Top hashtags in Zorrotzaurre, Credits: Bottom-Up.City

Thematic Categorization

45.203 hashtags
11 categories

Figure 23: Thematic ecosystem of Bilbao's Cultural & Creative Industries, Credits: Bottom-Up.City

The [Innovation Jam](#) followed the engagement process initiated by the pilot in early 2021, with the objective of exploring opportunities for HEIs-grassroots collaboration throughout the 'meanwhile' of ZZ's redevelopment. The Innovation Jam was a two-day event aimed at co-designing the meanwhile co-creation programme. The Jam involved the Local Coalition, local Universities, Grassroots Organisations and a number of T-Labs in a creative and collaborative definition of the design prompts and learning methodologies and pathways to be delivered through the meanwhile co-creation programme. For the preparation and delivery of the Jam, a specific methodology was designed by the team of T-Lab 7 'Climate Change and Regenerative Cities', as part of its support to the pilot, in close collaboration with the other T-Labs involved in the programme (T-Lab 4

'Urban Design for Sociality & Wellbeing'; T-Lab 5 'Circular and Collaborative Economy'), as well as with the members of the Local Coalition. During the Jam, the T-Labs prompted several examples of temporary uses in address to urban challenges relevant to the ZZ pilot, and worked with the invited grassroots initiatives and Universities throughout a process of co-design and knowledge exchange for the definition of the programme. This was followed by several meetings and further co-design sessions (both online and offline) throughout the summer, in order to finalise the details of the programme and be ready to launch it at the start of the academic year 2022/2023. As a result of the process, **three briefs were created** (one for each thematic track of the programme), and disseminated across prospective students as well as through the main T-Factor's channels.

Besides these three main activities, during the period of reference the Local Coalition has run several preparatory and planning actions, mainly consisting of internal coordination meetings and meetings with Universities and grassroots initiatives, co-design sessions and on site visits. It is also important to notice that according to the Portfolio's timeline, the core meanwhile activities and uses will be fully implemented in 2023, while 2022's activities were mainly dedicated to set the proper ground for implementation.

Photo credits: Bilbao Ekintza

Photo credits: Bilbao Ekintza

Activity 1: Collaborative Governance workshop**Preparatory/
Enabling activity** **24/03/2022
25/03/2022**

Target-groups: local policy and decision makers

Actual beneficiaries:

Collaborators:
TU Dortmund University (T-Lab 6), Experts from public and private organisations from Barcelona, Dortmund, Gothenburg and Copenhagen

- 31** participants, mainly from Municipalities and other local authorities
- 7** European Cities represented
- 4** European Cities represented
- 4** Cases of Collaborative Governance Models explored
- 4** Youtube Videos

Keywords:
#solidarity & belonging
#local identity & heritage**Activity 2: Innovation Ecosystem Analysis****Preparatory/
Enabling activity** **May 2022
October 2022**

Target groups: cultural and creative organisations in Bilbao; local policy makers in Bilbao.

Actual beneficiaries:

Collaborators:
Bottom-Up.City
City of Dortmund (T-Lab 6)

- 155.280** accounts and
- 244.686** relations analysed
- 45.203** hashtags considered

Keywords:
#culture & creativity
#local identity & heritage

Different types of maps and visualisations produced (geo-maps; connection maps; etc.)

Activity 3: Innovation Jam and design of the co-creation programme**Preparatory/
Enabling activity****26/05/2022-27/05/2022
(Innovation Jam)
June 2022-September 2022
(co-design)**Target groups:
Representatives from local grassroots initiatives and UniversitiesCollaborators:
members from T-Lab 4, 5, 6, 7.Keywords:
#learning, skilling, making
#creativity & talent

- 34** participants, mainly from Universities and grassroots organisations
- 1** co-design tool produced
- 3** design briefs created

| Stakeholders & Beneficiaries

Several **stakeholders and collaborators** have been activated during the period of reference in order to equip the pilot with the right expertise and resources needed to unlock the portfolio. All the activities have been developed through the active contribution of a number of T-Labs, which have been working in close collaboration with the Local Coalition in order to design, deliver and document the work carried out.

The policy workshop was facilitated by members of T-Lab 6 – Social Innovation and Social Inclusion. Furthermore, **experts from four EU cities** (i.e. Dortmund, Barcelona, Copenhagen, Gothenburg) were invited to present concrete cases of collaborative governance models for district management, with the expert facilitation of **ARUP**. For the Innovation Jam, six members of the T-Labs co-organized the activity, working remotely with the Local Coalition in the design of the methodology and tools, facilitating the Jam on site, and then ensuring its documentation and follow up. During the Jam, the Labs' members kickstarted the work by providing thematic examples and best practices that could inspire the design process during and after the Jam. Moreover, the Labs worked throughout the Jam in order to support the matchmaking between the participating Universities and grassroots organisations, in order to create meaningful synergies that could leverage individual expertise and experience.

Through the activities, the ZZ pilot managed to engage **different types of beneficiaries** (target groups). The main objective of the Collaborative Governance workshop was to influence the management of the municipality by letting them consider and reflect on alternative governance models. Therefore, the local coalition addressed mainly policy makers for this workshop. The Innovation Jam was instead addressed to University professors and staff, as well as to practitioners and managers of cultural and creative initiatives active on the island.

Photo credits:
Gure Txoko
Espacio Open
Piugaz

Contribution to impact at mission level - Main activities' results

In the paragraphs that follow, we provide an overview of the main results achieved through the activities described earlier, mainly extracted from an online survey addressed to the beneficiaries involved.

Knowledge & awareness on the redevelopment and possibilities for collaboration

The Innovation Jam (and previous early engagement activities) proved to be an important activity for spreading and increasing awareness and knowledge about the redevelopment of the island, but also around the grassroots initiatives that are active on site. The Jam was also a valuable opportunity to share and discuss some major urban challenges that Zorrotzaurre is currently facing, including in terms of environmental sustainability, inclusion, quality of life and wealth for its present and future inhabitants. The direct involvement of University staff in the Jam proved to be an important factor to further spread the visibility of the island and its future plans and risks, including through the near future involvement of students within the context of the meanwhile co-creation programme.

Similarly, the Collaborative Governance workshop demonstrated positive results in terms of enhancing the knowledge of the participants around concrete models of participatory governance for districts and neighbourhoods. Indeed, many participants were already familiar with the concept; however, the presentation of concrete cases and the discussion that followed proved to be a valuable opportunity for a shared reflection on replicability and transferability of these models.

Motivation to collaborate and engage in multi-actor alliances

The Innovation Jam was the first activity of the pilot to trigger motivation and anticipate concrete collaboration between grassroots initiatives and HEIs and thus represented a major milestone in the local strategy of temporary uses. The results of the survey demonstrated that the Jam contributed significantly to motivation and willingness to collaborate through the lens of urban challenges in ZZ. The survey also marked the contribution of the Jam to enhanced and enriched relational capital; the participants had the chance to meet new persons and organisations with whom they could work with in the future. Furthermore, since the motivation of the participants seems high, it is important to keep the momentum. The local coalition will try to materialise in the upcoming academic year the collaboration and strengthen the links between the grassroots initiatives and HEIs, so as to create longer term collaborations. In the near future, the local coalition will analyse and identify the type and level of involvement of the grassroots initiatives in each of the three tracks of the programme. The role of the universities is relatively clear, however the role of the grassroots initiatives will require more work of scoping. Similarly, the Collaborative Governance workshop proved to be an opportunity to steer and boost a reflection - amongst local policy and decision makers - on the type of governance model that would allow Zorrotzaurre to make the most of multi-stakeholder dialogue and collaboration, towards ZZ as a vibrant and innovative ecosystem of culture and creativity. The workshop was an occasion to explore pioneering examples of collaborative governance models for districts across European cities, which could inspire and provide meaningful inputs to the Municipality of Bilbao and the key stakeholders of the redevelopment.

| Contribution to impact at Pilot level

The section describes the pilot level changes and considerations gathered through the 'Critical Friend' interview. As anticipated, the interview is aimed at exploring if and how the activities undertaken during the period of reference are contributing towards long term outcomes and impacts of urban regeneration, particularly from the point of view of enhanced strategic, operational and relational dimensions (ref. Methodology section). In the following paragraph we report on the main strengths and weaknesses that emerged through the interview. A self-assessment scoreboard filled out by the Local Coalition is provided at the end of the section. It is important to highlight that the insights and reflections reported in this chapter do not only capture the voice and perceptions of the Local Coalition; they also include and integrate the results of the ongoing observation and support developed by the Transformation Agency over time, in its role of 'critical friend' of the pilot.

The evaluation of the progress of the ZZ pilot requires us to acknowledge the complex reality of the redevelopment, and its sudden acceleration in the recent past.

Due to ongoing and expected new evictions, the island is currently characterised by a mounting sense of uncertainty and fear that seems to be widespread across many of the grassroots initiatives that are active on site [24], which often makes it hard, if not counterproductive, to deal with the topic of temporary uses as a lever for positive urban transformation.

The regeneration plan for Zorrotzaurre is ambitious and will likely bring many benefits, including in terms of quality of housing, amenities, greening, educational and job opportunities, better access and connectivity, amongst others. Yet, this is a complex and long term redevelopment which will take years or even decades before such positive results will be fully unlocked; meanwhile, many social, cultural and economic actors in Zorrotzaurre **struggle with the 'everyday' and perceive the risk of short term disruption, including in terms of displacement, loss of identity and relational capital, feeling of isolation and powerlessness.**

Many of the grassroots initiatives engaged through T-Factor have more than 10 years of history in the island, often run and maintained through personal investment and efforts, and despite structural barriers. Many of them live and express the frustration of *'doing meaningful stuff which yet often remains invisible, as if it would become visible, it would bring about major questions around what to be prioritised in urban regeneration processes'* (extract from a meeting with local grassroots initiatives). Moreover, there is also a **sense of missed opportunity**, particularly when it comes to *'what Zorrotzaurre could have been or could still be if we are to give legs, impetus and support to what is already there'*. In many ways, Zorrotzaurre is exemplary of the **paradox of temporary uses, where the meanwhile is essentially the terrain of conflict between a landlord who wants to send you away, and a guest who does not want to leave.**

Furthermore, although the redevelopment has been phased and planned accordingly, the detailed roadmap is almost unknown to the grassroots, and the **lack of direct channels of communication with the Municipality - especially as one single voice that can represent all the initiatives - have been often mentioned as a barrier to uncertainty mitigation and trust creation.** More broadly, while ZZ in particular and Bilbao in general have been staging many pioneering temporary uses over the years, the Municipality does not have a specific regulation for these uses, which is

[24] It should be noted that this aspect of fear and uncertainty by the local grassroots has been emerging over time through various activities in T-Factor, including workshops, informal conversations, and coordination meetings. Indeed, it should be treated carefully, as it may not represent a diffused perception nor it could mean the same for different grassroots initiatives across the island.

also a barrier to access, maintenance and investment for many cultural and creative organisations, especially the small and most fragile ones. Overall, addressing the meanwhile in ZZ turned out to be a very sensitive topic, bringing about the risk of raising the social conflict rather than contributing to its mitigation - thus requiring the Local Coalition to be extremely careful in the type of narrative and arguments used so far, as well as agile and responsive against rapidly changing conditions on site.

Nevertheless, within this challenging landscape, there are several areas of benefits that the Local Coalition mentioned during the interview. In the first instance, T-Factor proved to be a valuable platform for bringing the grassroots initiatives together and engaging them in a shared dialogue and conversation about the main challenges perceived around the redevelopment, the meanwhile topic, and how this can be leveraged in a more active and constructive way. More in particular, the project is providing the local grassroots with the opportunity to explore rooms of collaboration with local Universities, enhancing professional connections but also raising the visibility of both physical spaces and activities across the island. At the same time, the project is supporting a crucial reflection and awareness-raising process amongst the grassroots, related to their capacity and willingness to cooperate more and act as one collective voice for the present and future of the island.

“T-Factor is helping create awareness among the community actors by providing a space for dialogue, to have daily relationships, and a conversation about the problems of the island. There was a need for dialogue and T-Factor is creating spaces where this can happen ”
(ZZ Local Coalition).

The general knowledge on the redevelopment seems to have been positively affected as well, especially on the side of the Universities actively contributing to the co-creation programme. The direct involvement of the Transformation Labs also appears as an important driver and incentive to local collaboration and constructive dialogue, bringing about fresh views

and perspectives on the island that - along the run - have helped overcome moments of blockages and conflicting discussions, especially internally to the Local Coalition.

Furthermore, the participatory approach adopted throughout the activities has helped identify key needs, challenges, and priorities of diverse local actors and turn them into areas of shared action and exploration through meanwhile placemaking. As a result, a meanwhile co-creation programme has been collaboratively designed and is now under implementation, addressing three urban challenges: i. Circular Economy; ii. Climate Resilience; & iii. Sociality and Well-being. This programme, which is the core meanwhile use experimented in T-Factor, is meant to be the actual testbed for novel civic curricula that can better link theory and practice on the ground, thus making the case for longer term alliances between Universities and grassroots organisations in address to shared challenges and opportunities of urban transformation. Although the programme is in early stages, there are several potential benefits that this experimentation could unlock, including in terms of bringing young students closer to the island and expanding opportunities for imagining and prototyping the future of spaces and their functions according to values and qualities of inclusion, sustainability and quality of life for all.

From a strategic and operational perspective, there seems to be an increasing alignment within the Local Coalition, which is largely perceived as a positive effect of the project. Although the ongoing work and collaboration has encountered several moments of blockages and conflicting views, the Local Coalition has been often able to get to shared decisions and joint proposals for the steps to be taken over time. Despite the Local Coalition being ‘small’, it is somehow representative of (some) of the different interests and agendas at play in Zorrotzaurre, and is thus exemplary of the type of conflicts and discussions that are mostly at stake.

Overall, the pilot also appears in a promising stage when it comes to capacity building and knowledge sharing. Both within and beyond the Local Coalition, there have been significant flows of knowledge and capacity building opportunities generated over time, both within the

ongoing work of coordination and strategic reflection undertaken by the Local Coalition with the Agency and the T-Labs. Currently, the pilot is receiving direct support from four Transformation Labs, accounting for an overall team of +15 people with expertise ranging nature-based solutions, climate adaptation and mitigation, circular and collaborative economy, arts and culture-led spatial practices, digital manufacturing, amongst others. More in detail, the collaborating T-Labs are T-Lab 4 'Urban design for sociality and well-being'; T-Lab 5 'Circular and Collaborative Economy'; T-Lab 6 'Social Innovation and Social Inclusion' and T-Lab 7 'Climate change and Regenerative cities'.

Lastly, we shall mention the ongoing effort of the pilot when it comes to **influencing local policy-making and the redevelopment itself**, an aspect that stands as a key precondition for Mission 2 and 3 on Collaborative Governance and Enabling Regulations, and more broadly for the overall pilot's legacy and sustainability. Although this aspect is and remains challenging - also pushing the Local Coalition to eventually reconsider the initial ambitions and meaning of the set Missions, the Workshop on Collaborative Governance represented an important milestone. Not only did it create the opportunity to convene pioneering examples of collaborative governance models for districts across European cities; it also provided T-Factor members (including members of the Local Coalition and T-Labs) **with the first space of dialogue about ZZ with the Municipality and the top management of the redevelopment**. It also turned out to be an opportunity for multi-department exchange about the future of ZZ. Yet, **this remains the weakest aspect of the pilot**, and will indeed require more effort and investment in the near future, not least in terms of novel ways of engagement and 'arguments building' vis-à-vis decision makers.

The Local Coalition is aware that fears of displacement and risks of disruption of the existing activities on the island may turn out to be a weak argument in a redevelopment that will likely create much more jobs, cultural and creative enterprises, amongst other benefits. The strategy

should go instead towards **making the case for a more plural, diverse and lively cultural regeneration** where high profile actors can coexist and collaborate hand in hand with smaller and community-led organisations, unlocking novel schools of thoughts and approaches to the creation of cultural and creative urban ecosystems. As a key next step which already started at the time of writing this report, the pilot will develop a study on the social, cultural and economic value generated by the existing cultural and creative initiatives in Zorrotzaurre, as a way to provide the Municipality and other regeneration stakeholders with evidence and arguments that can help make the redevelopment more inclusive and sustainable towards the long run.

Towards the next period, the Local Coalition has finally pinpointed the need of **strengthening the involvement of the grassroots initiatives**, including towards reinforced engagement and involvement in the co-creation programme. Creating partnerships, collaborations, and networks among the grassroots, HEIs and the local community with a focus on building trust and transparency should be the way forward according to the Local Coalition, which could eventually help in unleashing a concrete legacy in the form of a resilient community of practice.

“In the coming months, T-Factor should focus on building trust and transparency among the local actors and increasing collaborations and supporting the fragility of the grassroots ecosystem and to understand what kind of legacy T Factor could leave” (Local Coalition).

	Dimensions	1	2	3	4
STRATEGIC	Positioning & Reputation	The portfolio poorly contributes to enhancing the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is not properly valorised.	The portfolio partially contributes to the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is considered but not a driver in the cultural and social evolution of the area	The portfolio brings a great visibility to the area and raises awareness about its heritage	The portfolio has provided the area with a new identity and its heritage is appreciated by diverse audiences.
	Attractiveness	The portfolio is raising limited interest and struggles to attract diverse audiences and target groups.	The portfolio raises the interest of target groups and engages with an unvaried audience on a local level.	The portfolio is compelling for all target groups and attracts a diverse audience both locally and from the surroundings	The portfolio is compelling and raises the interest of new groups and audiences both locally and from the surroundings
	Relevance & Opportunity	The portfolio addresses in a limited way local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are neither investigated nor pursued.	The portfolio addresses some local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are identified	The portfolio inclusively responds to pressing local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Expands opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets	The portfolio is adjusted to address new emerging challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. creates a number of new opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets.
OPERATIONAL	Planning & Delivery Capacities	The portfolio has limited available resources and the retrieval of missing resources is yet to be defined.	The portfolio has some available resources and activities that could retrieve resources are under definition.	The portfolio is financially sustainable and activities/fundraising initiatives to retrieve them are in progress .	The portfolio is financially sustainable and has retrieved most fundings.
	Resilience, Flexibility & Adaptability	The portfolio has not identified emerging needs and opportunities that could have influenced the masterplan	The portfolio has identified some emerging needs and opportunities but strong 'evidence' is missing	Emerging needs and opportunities have been identified and masterplan adjustments are under definition	Emerging needs and opportunities have been fully defined and the masterplan has been adapted accordingly
	Interoperability & Connectivity	The pilot is not aware of other initiatives in the area and has not identified relevant policies and plans that could contribute to the meanwhile strategy	The portfolio is aligned with some initiatives in the area or policies and plans relevant to the meanwhile use strategy have been analysed.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are almost established. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy supported by policy programmes.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are concrete. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy is contributing and supported by policy programmes.
RELATIONAL	Impact time & Depth (Too early to assess)	The portfolio results are requiring more time than expected and not all results and impacts will be achieved	The portfolio results are timely and most results and impacts are expected to be achieved.	The portfolio results have been achieved earlier than expected allowing to add additional uses for different groups.	The portfolio is involving and aligning around local innovation missions with a plethora of diverse stakeholders.
	Agency & Legitimacy	The portfolio does not contribute to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors to involve to build multi-sectoral coalitions have not been identified	The portfolio contributes in a limited way to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors have been identified but must define how to involve them in multi-sectoral coalitions	The portfolio contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established	The portfolio strongly contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An inclusive array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established
	Legacy, Sustainability & Scalability	The portfolio does not have a clear legacy.	The portfolio creates certain conditions for long term legacy but remains context-specific (not transferable).	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become more sustainable in the long-term. E.g. Scalability is being investigated	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become fully scalable or transferrable.

| PART 2
CONTRIBUTION
TO IMPACT AT
TRANSNATIONAL
LEVEL

| 2.1. Introduction

In order to set the ground for evaluation at transnational level, we shall recall the fundamental role of **systems thinking** in which T-Factor is rooted. The project recognises that cities are complex systems by design, where urban regeneration and transformations typically occur through dynamics that are fundamentally interconnected and interdependent. Indeed, deep and long-term urban transformations cannot be sparked through single and siloed temporary uses; rather, they require a holistic and systemic approach to meanwhile intervention where temporary uses are designed and run as a **portfolio of strategic experiments**; driven by **time-bound, specific missions** framed as **call to actions to collective and collaborative discovery** in placemaking; aligned with the local development vision yet relevant to international agendas (i.e., SDGs). So conceived, we understand temporary uses mainly in their potential to support **strategic learning, risk awareness & management, and better decision-making** along the run of urban regeneration processes, where participatory engagement and co-creation throughout the meanwhile are not nice to have, but rather key requirements to test, anticipate, and accelerate more complex and longer term urban transformations. At the project's transnational level, the ambition is thus to spread relevant learning and knowledge in ways that can inspire, influence and keep momentum on urban regeneration driven by values and qualities of democracy, inclusion and wealth for all within planetary boundaries.

More in detail, there are two main areas of impact considered for the transnational level:

1. Contribution of T-Factor to the 'practice' of meanwhile uses - understood as how the project is supporting **visibility** of these practices, **dissemination of existing and co-creation of new knowledge**, and **capacity building in their design and management**, with the overall objective of spreading temporary uses as a viable, strategic approach to urban regeneration.
2. Contribution of T-Factor to the 'politics' of inclusive and sustainable urban regeneration and 'policies' of meanwhile uses - understood as

how the project is contributing to international and EU agendas on sustainable urban development, as well as how it is eventually influencing and triggering policy innovations for meanwhile uses, mainly at the local levels.

2.2. Contribution to the 'practice' of meanwhile uses

Meanwhile uses are a relatively emerging and fragmented practice across the European landscape of urban regeneration. Even in those cities and territories where meanwhile uses have a sound curriculum, their typical characteristics of bottom-up emergence and rapid and agile delivery make them a quite rich and continuously evolving domain of practices and possibilities. Contributing to visibility, knowledge creation, and capacity building are thus crucial aspects for these practices to become the *new normal* in the way we equip cities for major contemporary challenges. There is a yet untapped opportunity to test and observe the **viability and versatility of meanwhile uses in addressing both contextual and global challenges of urban development**, and this positions T-Factor as a valuable contributor to novel understandings of, and possibilities for, meanwhile uses.

Over the period considered, all the three aspects mentioned above - visibility, knowledge and capacity building - have been explicitly addressed, with activities and results presented in the paragraphs that follow.

2.2.1. Visibility of meanwhile uses

In the period considered, effort has been made to keep on showcasing and disseminating T-Factor in particular, and meanwhile uses in general. While a full and comprehensive reporting of all outreach, dissemination and exploitation activities can be found in **D8.5 Outreach Report v2.0** (delivered contextually to the present report), for the sake of 'visibility' within the transnational evaluation we can mention the participation of,

T-Factor to **14 external events** (including online and in presence), accounting for **approx. 700 participants** in total. The typology of these events is rich, including publics from academia, businesses, civil society and the public sector. Indeed, these numbers do not say much around visibility and eventually enhanced awareness of meanwhile uses; however, we can also say that in many cases invitations came from persons attending previous events, who were stimulated and wanted to know more by inviting T-Factor's members to their own events.

The number of events **directly organised by T-Factor** at both central and pilots' levels is much higher and so is the outreach, both direct and indirect. Spanningly, we can count more than **50 events** including online webinars, festivals, training sessions, workshops, walkscapes, policy-level events and more, although given the participatory process of T-Factor, it is hard to ascribe them to siloed categories as they were often responding to multiple goals where visibility of meanwhile practices stood transversally. Nonetheless, we could state that T-Factor and temporary uses were exposed to a huge diversity of audiences and at different scales - local, municipal, regional, EU. To this, we shall also mention the appearance on the project in **+30 mentions** between press, radio and television, including within well known newspapers such as *El Pais*, *El Correo*, *Il Sole 24 Ore*, *Wyborcza*, *Kauno Diena*, *Journal de Noticias*, *Repubblica*, and others. Continuous storytelling has also been made through the main project's social media such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter. At present, the global reach through the different T-Factor communication channels is above **8,9K people**.

Furthermore, during the period the project kept on disseminating the **Advanced Cases Portfolio (D2.1)**. The Italian version was disseminated throughout the national network of ANCI which gathers together and represents more than **8,000 Municipalities across Italy**, and led to the organisation of a specific policy event in June 2022, which is however reported later as it was specifically aimed at policy innovations for meanwhile uses. Similarly, the Portfolio was also translated in French and disseminated throughout the network of *La Friche*.

A mention shall be made of the **Temporary Uses Map** created by T-Factor [25]. The work on the map was initiated in early 2021 under the

lead of Politecnico di Milano, with the ultimate aim of producing an openly available tool for dynamic mapping and systematisation of meanwhile practices and related institutional actions [26] across European cities. Although this work also has the objective of contributing to better knowledge of the state of play of temporary uses, it is particularly important for making meanwhile practises more visible. **Approx. 100 entries** are currently harvested in the map including concrete cases of temporary uses, institutional actions and relevant actors. The map is dynamic and can be nurtured at any time via external inputs, thus representing an important tool that can contribute to mapping and enhanced visibility.

Summarising, it is hard to provide reliable evidence on enhanced visibility and general awareness of meanwhile uses, and harder is to eventually attribute this effect to T-Factor. What we can say is that since the beginning of the project, this topic **seems to be more present in the general debate on urban regeneration and sustainable and inclusive urban development**, not least in terms of presence in national, regional and local media.

Regarding the European level, the **DUT Partnership** [27] recently mentioned the reuse of vacant, underused and transient spaces as possibilities towards 15 minutes cities' experimentations, while an early 2022 call for proposals within the **New European Bauhaus** funded a specific project on temporary uses and inclusive public spaces led by **Universitat Oberta de Catalunya**, partner of T-Factor [28].

Furthermore, as we will see later in the section related to policy innovations, there is increasing interest from local authorities in exploring temporary uses as novel instruments of urban planning. In June 2022, within a T-Factor event for local policy makers, the **Tuscan Regional Councillor for Infrastructure, Mobility and Territorial Governance** made an explicit **call to action to all Tuscan municipalities towards the full adoption of meanwhile uses in urban planning and development**. The Tuscany Region is also partnering on an INTERREG

[26] With this term, we refer in particular to enabling conditions for temporary uses, including policies and regulations, governance arrangements and funding mechanisms, mainly at Municipal and Regional levels.

[27] See: <https://dutpartnership.eu/>

[28] See: <https://www.t-factor.eu/uoc-asd-public-inclusive-parks/>

[25] Available at: <https://www.t-factor.eu/temporary-use-map/>

project explicitly addressing policies and regulations for temporary uses, which was elaborated and presented thanks to the direct push of T-Factor. Nonetheless, **at the EU level this topic still seems largely untapped**, which may be a unique opportunity for T-Factor to push for more explicit and dedicated policies and programmes supporting international cooperation in this field.

2.2.2. Knowledge and capacity building for meanwhile uses

Dissemination of existing knowledge, co-creation of new knowledge, and support to capacity building for meanwhile practices are central and transversal objectives of the project. Although it is hard to separate and categorise activities done over time in these areas and results achieved at different scales (especially when considering that all the pilots put knowledge co-creation and capacity building at the very centre of their local meanwhile strategies), in the following paragraphs we attempt to report on two main areas of work: i) **support to pilots and their local stakeholders in designing, delivery and critically reflecting on meanwhile strategies**; ii) **international collaborations** unlocked especially through the Transformation Labs.

i) Capacity building for the design and delivery of meanwhile strategies

Over the period, T-Factor has continuously supported the pilots throughout the design and delivery of portfolios of temporary uses. Along the run, the project has invested considerable effort in designing and running a **supporting infrastructure for knowledge and practice co-creation and exchange** - for, among and beyond the T-Factor's pilots. The Transformation Agency and the T-Labs have been the key engines of such infrastructure, providing an operational framework, developing tools and methods, facilitating and/or running activities at pilots' sites, and supporting continuous documentation and learning capture of the local meanwhile journeys.

From the outset, the project has been working to create a **wide set of tools and methods** that could support the pilots throughout their

meanwhile journey, from in depth immersion into the local contexts under regeneration, passing through early engagement for bottom-up identification and scoping of key challenges and opportunities for meanwhile intervention, continuing with co-design of temporary use portfolios, up to rapid prototyping, testing, and learning capture. The **Transformation Agency** has steered and curated the whole process, leveraging the expertise of its design partners [29] to elaborate on both new and existing tools, transferring them to the Local Coalitions, and supporting their application. Besides, the **T-Labs** have sided the whole process [30], 'plugging in' from time to time with thematic tools and methods relevant to the specific pilots' missions - for example around topics such as participatory mapping of biodiversity, guidelines for inclusive digital placemaking, methods and models for collaborative governance of spaces, amongst others.

T-Factor Workshops in Amsterdam and Bilbao

[29] More in detail, the members of the Transformation Agency are: LAMA, ANCI Toscana, University of the Arts London, Politecnico di Milano and Aalborg University. For more information, see: <https://www.t-factor.eu/how-we-work/>

[30] The seven Transformation Labs of T-Factor are coordinated by Waag, which has been working continuously in sync with the Agency. See: <https://www.t-factor.eu/how-we-work/>

All the tools and methods have been carefully documented especially within the **T-Factor Digital Toolbox** [31] which is meant to be one of the main products and legacy of T-Factor. At the time of writing this report, the Toolbox hosts more than **20 tools already tested by the pilots**, as well as a variety of suggestions for further readings and resources, all organised according to the main steps of the T-Factor’s meanwhile methodology for easy navigation and retrieval of resources.

Similarly, effort has been devoted to the curation and capture of the activities organised by the pilots (including in collaboration with the T-Labs), these also documented within the **‘Toolbox in Action’** where each pilot can be navigated along its temporary use path. Although this section is the main ‘work in progress’ space of the project, at the time of writing this report it hosts more than **40 ‘stories’** or - in T-Factor’s terminology - **key content production moments** [32], for the large majority produced through various geometries of collaboration among the pilots, the Agency, the T-Labs and, of course, stakeholders and communities on site.

Although at present the Toolbox hasn’t yet been launched at scope and scale, it is meant to become a key reference point for both T-Factor’s partners and, more importantly, for external audiences, as it is conceived as an easy-to-use and accessible source of knowledge and practices on temporary uses. Moreover, although demanding in effort, the process behind the Toolbox’s development is proving to be key in **‘enforcing’ careful, constant documentation** across the pilot sites and the T-Labs, as well as continuous reflection on the relevance and innovativeness of content produced over time.

Furthermore, a number of training and capacity building sessions were organised during the period to support the pilots and local stakeholders in advancing the design and delivery of meanwhile portfolios. For example, we shall mention the **Transformation Camp** in Florence (March 2022), the webinar on **Fundraising strategies for Cultural and Creativity-led placemaking** (June 2022), and the **Gathering in Marseille** (September 2022) which combined an exploration of La Friche (one of the T-Factor’s Advanced Cases) and training sessions on governance and business models for temporary uses. More details of these activities are provided as boxes in the following pages.

[31] Available at: <https://hub.t-factor.eu/>

[32] With the term ‘stories’, we refer to the actual implementation of a specific temporary use or activity, which in turn typically generates narratives of what happened, who was involved, how, and the main learning. Many activities also created, and will keep on creating, specific tools and methods that are captured in the Toolbox in order to allow replication, re-use and transferability./

Figure 25: Screenshot of the Exploring and Inquiring page of the Toolbox

Figure 26: Screenshot of the Toolbox in Action main page

TRANSFORMATION CAMP

Florence, 16-17 March, 2022

Two-day workshop organised at Manifattura Tabacchi Florence, one of the advanced cases of T-Factor. The Camp was conceived as an intensive, laboratorial session aimed at accelerating the detailed definition of the pilots' Portfolios, including the precise support to be delivered by each T-Lab or combination of T-Labs to the pilots. The Camp was designed and hosted in close collaboration between LAMA, Waag and Polytechnic of Milan in their own roles of Transformation Agency and T-Labs coordinators and members (respectively), and was addressed to all T-Factor's partners, with emphasis on the pilots' Local Coalitions and their key local stakeholders who, for the occasion, were invited to attend and participate actively. During the Camp, the pilots had the chance to explore and test a number of design tools as part of the design process, and also benefited from continuous support and guidance from both the Agency and T-Labs' members. The Camp was the first 'in presence' gathering of the project, and thus represented a key moment for all partners in terms of creating closer relationships, collaborations and trust. The Camp also led to the elaboration of two deliverables, i.e., D4.4. Design driven city making tools and D5.4 Activity Plans 2.0. D4.4 contains a detailed list of tools and methodologies for prototyping and testing (also documented within the Digital Toolbox), while D5.4 captures the results of the work done in Florence and iterated in the following months.

60 participants

8 working rounds

1 guided tour

**4 design canvases
elaborated**

**Prototyping guidelines
produced**

2 Follow-up deliverables

47 participants

1 guided tour

enhanced understanding of possibilities for governance and business modelling for temporary uses

Fundraising for Cultural and Creativity-led placemaking

Webinar, 28 June, 2022

In June 2022, LAMA and ANCI organised the webinar 'Fundraising strategies for culture and creativity-led placemaking'. The invited speaker was Dr. Andrea Caracciolo di Feroletto, senior lecturer of the School of Fundraising in Rome and member of the Certification Committee of EFA, the European Fundraising Association. Through the webinar, T-Factor sought to create opportunities to share knowledge, tools and case studies useful to retrieve additional funding for temporary uses within the pilots, although the event was also open to external audiences. In total, the webinar involved 23 participants, largely from T-Factor. The ex-post survey demonstrated a good level of appreciation and perceived relevance, as well as perception of increased knowledge on fundraising options and tools potentially applicable to the pilots. The weighted average score increased from 4,2 towards a score of 7 out of 10 (i.e. a score of 1 relates to very low knowledge and a score of 10 relates to an elevated knowledge). Furthermore, the participants reported that the speaker provided a comprehensive overview of the topic, including by presenting concrete examples and success stories. The webinar was also reported as accessible in style and language.

23 participants

+8 case studies explored

enhanced understanding of possibilities for fundraising

T-Factor gathering at La Friche, Marseille

14/15 September, 2022

In September 2022, the T-Factor consortium gathered in Marseille for a deep exploration of Friche La Belle de Mai, one of the T-Factor's Advanced Cases. The gathering combined a guided tour, presentations and training sessions dedicated to collaborative governance and business models of temporary uses. The respondents of the survey stated that the guided tour was inspiring for several reasons. First, the participants were stimulated by the story of the site and its model of participatory governance and approach to meanwhile as a 'permanent' way to weaving people in places. La Friche has been perceived as an outstanding example of how to 'make places' together with a variety of publics and in response to a diversity of needs. The respondents also identified additional factors that made La Friche worth visiting, such as the support provided by local administrations to arts and creativity-led urban regeneration, the type of capital deployment, and the way spaces are used to host a large number of organisations, big and small, working along the full arch of arts, heritage, culture and creativity. Furthermore, the respondents indicated that the presentations and workshops enhanced knowledge on collaborative governance models for meanwhile spaces. The presentation was clear and engaging, useful in providing categories to interpret different governance models and addressed the questions of the consortium members in a structured way. Practical sessions required the pilots to work out generic models and make them applicable to their context, which helped reflect on the level of ambition in terms of participation and power shifts through collaborative governance. When it comes to the session on business models, this also proved to be beneficial in terms of better awareness and knowledge. The participants indicated that the business models' framework adopted was effective and that the group discussion enabled them to go deeper into this aspect. However, the respondents also highlighted that both aspects would have required all key stakeholders to sit at the same table, such as landowners, developers, and tenants.

Lastly, one important stream of capacity-building consisted of **ongoing reflection and self-evaluation as part of the critical friend process** implemented by the Agency. Since June 2021, each pilot has been followed by a dedicated member of the Agency in charge of supporting the ongoing delivery of the portfolio, particularly through regular feedback and critical inputs. Although each agency member and pilot had autonomy in organising their own working flow, on average the various working groups opted for bi-weekly (online) meetings and field visits over time. Approximately, **70% of the Agency effort in this period has been devoted to direct support to pilots**, while the rest has mainly consisted of internal touch points among the Agency members, and production of deliverables. Agency support also included a round of critical friend interviews with each Local Coalition; although these interviews were mainly instrumental for the evaluation at pilot level, the insights were also key to better understand and assess the overall contribution of the project to capacity building. The Labs have undergone a similar process, with regular touch moments coordinated by Waag (**+15 organised during the period**) and a more structured focus group implemented in September 2022 for mid term evaluation.

Results emerging from the critical friend process are largely qualitative. The Local Coalitions reported general positive effects of the methods and tools adopted. Although often told as **an overall complex and demanding process**, there are several areas of benefits perceived. In the first instance, the Local Coalitions generally reported **increased awareness of and sensitivity to, the complexity in which they operate**, as well as **more capacity to deal with it**. Similarly, the process and the methods have often been reported as beneficial in their **emphasis on participation and engagement with a plurality of voices and perspectives**. One outstanding aspect is the **emergent, agile and flexible nature of the process**, which almost all pilots perceive as a unique feature of T-Factor and a key contributor to **mindsets and skills for iterative and agile design and placemaking**.

However, this same process was also reported as **difficult to be fully embraced and managed**, especially vis-à-vis the requirements of the T-Factor's funding and the relatively tight and rigid schedule in production of deliverables and reporting. Claims were made about **the extent to which flexibility can be fully accommodated** - for example by changing

or re-adapting planned temporary uses or the way financial resources can be spent, in a situation where as a Consortium there is a fundamental requirement to be consistent and reliable with the Grant Agreement with the European Commission and the types of indicators originally envisaged. Despite openness and continuous support by the Commission's officers, this remains a structural problem that T-Factor may share with similar R&I projects, as even when changes can be made, typically the long time of approval and bureaucratic procedures have effects all along the chain of project management and delivery, including preventing people and organisations by default from embarking in possibilities for re-planning and re-scoping. This aspect is particularly important in T-Factor, as it is largely perceived as **a major barrier to agile and flexible placemaking vis-à-vis rapidly accelerating change and systemic risks** that permeate cities and, by extension, urban regeneration.

A positive aspect also emerges around ambitions in participation and adoption of **meanwhile uses as ways to respond to vulnerabilities**. Increasingly over time, and also thanks to the push of the European Commission, the topic of how meanwhile uses can help address specific needs from vulnerable categories has been getting higher within both the project and pilots' agenda. All pilots and Labs have been pushed heavily to address this aspect, which in turn has increasingly permeated discussions and debates across the various project's bodies and streams of work. Pilots such as MIND in Milan went back to their planned portfolio in order to include a focus on **NEETs**; a discussion is currently underway within the Local Coalition in Lisbon and the collaborating T-Labs, aimed at understanding how might the pilot be able to address the exacerbating problem of **evictions** in Segundo Torrao neighbourhood at Trafaria; London is heavily focussed on bringing and demonstrating benefits to **local residents and deprived communities** in and around Euston; Bilbao is mainly working to support **grassroots and community-based organisations** in Zorrotzaurre (mostly small and fragile) in having a real say and legitimacy throughout the redevelopment; both Amsterdam and Kaunas are putting special focus on **children, adolescents and young people's** health and wellbeing through greening and wild nature.

It is early to say whether this increasing focus on vulnerabilities can translate into better capacities and more effective interventions.

Moreover, all the Local Coalitions recognise that these are major issues that single temporary uses can barely support, especially with the relatively limited funding they have within T-Factor. However, it appears as a positive effect of the overall project's push towards meaningful impact, and in some cases (especially MIND and London Euston) can also be demonstrated by increasing sensitivity and openness of the developers to support meanwhile uses in address to vulnerable groups.

Lastly, one critical point emerges around perceived capacity and legitimacy in influencing broader plans of regeneration and power dynamics at higher level. Although this does not apply to all pilots nor in the same way (a fewer of them reporting quite the opposite perceptions, yet often due to good relationships and collaborations preceding T-Factor), claims were made about the need for the project to provide more support and capacity building on this aspect, especially considering that the actual work on site requires heavy operational effort which in turn may leave less time to strategic thinking. Indeed, this is a critical aspect that needs to be addressed more in general, and more deliberately if T-Factor aims to create the proper conditions for impact and meaningful legacy.

i) Co-creation of new knowledge and capacity building through International collaboration (Pilots-T-Labs collaboration)

The Transformation Labs are the core engine of T-Factor for unlocking new knowledge and capacity on meanwhile uses through international collaborations. Over the period, there have been massive flows of collaboration among the pilots and T-Labs, where the input and expertise of the latter have often been key in enriching and expanding scope and ambitions of temporary uses and experiments in the meanwhile.

Generally, in 2022 all pilots have been collaborating with **two thematic Labs on average**, with the exception of Bilbao which has been supported by four Labs (for more detail on this, the reader can refer to the specific pilot chapters). Spanningly, there have been **+15 travels** made by the Labs towards the pilot sites, and approximately **20** are the activities run

or co-organised by the Labs, including design and prototyping workshops, lectures, research sprints, field interviews, elaboration of guidelines, and more. The breadth of topics faced and content produced and planned to be produced is quite diverse, spanning temporary uses for **greening and biodiversity**, guidelines and principles for **digital placemaking**, thematic toolkits, podcasts and other types of storytelling and storysharing outputs, amongst many others.

KNOWLEDGE & CAPACITY BUILDING THROUGHOUT DESIGNING & DELIVERING MEANWHILE USES / HIGHLIGHTS

Increased awareness of and sensitivity to **complexity**

Enhanced capacity to navigate and deal with **complexity**

Strong focus on **participatory engagement**

Awareness and commitment to address **vulnerabilities** more explicitly and deliberately

Agile, flexible and iterative placemaking process as more capable of embracing rapid change and systemic risk

Complex and demanding process that require high expertise and effort to be fully run

Rigidity of timing, tight scheduling and spending barriers which often contrast with the emergent and rapidly evolving nature of temporary uses

High **operational effort** which may leave **less time for strategic thinking**

70% of Agency effort devoted to direct support to pilots

+20 Tools elaborated and tested

+40 Stories captured in the Toolbox

3 thematic training activities (intensive)

T-Labs have been exposed directly to the local stakeholders and communities engaged by the pilots, which in many cases opened up opportunities for **unplanned and new activities and collaborations**. For example, the field visit of T-Lab 2 in MIND Milan brought Lendlease (MIND's developer) to Bilbao for a follow-up visit, aimed at knowing more about Bilbao's ecosystem and clusters for R&I. Similarly, these international collaborations are currently creating a **number of spillover projects submitted mainly to EU calls for new funding**, most of them under evaluation.

In general, the evaluation of international collaboration by means of the T-Labs is proving to be highly beneficial. **New knowledge in placemaking possibilities; enhanced relational capital; better capacity to work and collaborate in international environments; better capacity to overcome blockages** as effect of fresh and more external perspectives brought locally; **improvement in lateral thinking** are all aspects that have been mentioned during critical friend interviews and T-Labs' focus groups. Based on the context and challenges of the pilots, the thematic collaborations with the T-Labs are acting as an important driver in shaping and executing the pilots' portfolios, and are contributing heavily to generation of valuable knowledge and insights for participatory placemaking in the meanwhile. The Labs are especially instrumental in **fostering a variety of roots and understandings of the meanwhile locally**, along topics such as arts and culture-led spatial practices, circular and collaborative economy, citizens-led smartness, climate adaptation and resilience, social innovation, and more.

One **critical point emerges instead around cross-pilots and cross-Labs collaborations**, as well as in terms of **timely sharing** of the work and ongoing achievements beyond T-Factor's partners and their most immediate tiers of stakeholders. As activities at pilots' sites intensify, there is an increasing need to create more occasions for confronting and learning from each other, as well as to make external publics benefit from what the project is doing, producing and learning.

This is an aspect that has recently started to be more addressed, particularly through more structured moments of peer learning and exchange that can also be opened to the general public.

KNOWLEDGE & CAPACITY BUILDING THROUGHOUT PILOTS-T-LABS COLLABORATION / HIGHLIGHTS

Enhanced and new knowledge in **placemaking possibilities and approaches**

Enhanced **relational capital**

Better capacity to **work and collaborate internationally**

Better capacity to **overcome blockages**

Improvement in **lateral thinking**

New **spillover projects** created and **unplanned activities and opportunities for international collaboration**

Need to improve **timely sharing of progress across pilots and T-Labs, as well as peer learning and exchange**

+15 regular touch points among T-Labs

+15 travels made for on site activities

+20 activities run collaboratively

+40 Stories captured in the Toolbox

2.3. | Contribution to 'politics' of urban regeneration and 'policies' for meanwhile uses

2.3.1. Contribution to politics of urban regeneration

With the term 'politics of urban regeneration' we refer to **visions, qualities, values and narratives** that surround and inform international and EU agendas and initiatives on sustainable urban development. In the following paragraphs we report on the project's contribution to the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations, as well as to recent policies and initiatives at EU level that give further context and scope of action to T-Factor. More in particular, we describe how the project is attempting to leverage on such agendas and initiatives to contribute to keep momentum on, and unleashing, novel approaches to urban regeneration driven by people and for people within planetary boundaries.

Sustainable Development Goals

The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [33] provide a global framework with specific objectives that address a complex, interlinked, and wide range of social, economic, and environmental issues. The SDGs outline 169 targets to be achieved by 2030, and stress the urgency of global action towards the set goals. Cities are crucial contexts where to address the SDGs and accelerate time to achievement, and urban regeneration is increasingly the playing field where to advance radical transformations in the way we can produce, consume, live and overall thrive inclusively and in respect to planetary boundaries.

Designing SDGs-driven meanwhile uses may bring about important contributions in addressing contemporary challenges such as climate breakdown, unaffordable costs of living, and rising inequalities. Indeed, these are complex and systemic challenges that cannot be tackled in isolation, nor through the logic of single and siloed projects. The often small and contingent nature of temporary uses may make them apparently unsuited for the scale and scope of actions needed.

Yet, within T-Factor their relevance to the SDGs is essentially understood in the possibility to narrow down grand challenges into the everyday of local communities and urban spaces: it means **interrogating what deprivation, unaffordability, exclusion, natural depletion or other major issues mean and look like for those who are actually experiencing them in the hyper-local**, and exploring what can be done in the meanwhile for alleviating the effects while anticipating mitigation and prevention options toward the long run. Moreover, if **gentrification** is the relatively hidden threat to many urban regeneration across Europe - including for the redevelopments targeted by T-Factor, temporary uses offer the chance to deliberately inquire into this complex and often ambiguous phenomenon, most importantly through a critical reflection along reactivation and requalification of spaces, rising in property values, and dynamics/risks of displacement of the existing social, cultural and economic fabric.

As we already commented in the Advanced Cases Portfolio (D2.1), temporary uses may bring with them an **intrinsic risk of being gentrification propellers**, especially when funded and driven by private interests. Yet, they may also offer the opportunity to explore and trigger **alternative forms and architectures of urban regeneration, particularly along the key conditions - regulations, policies, governance, funding - that can unlock bottom-up access to space, co-investment, co-maintenance and co-production of (shared) urban assets**. Whether it is a community garden, a number of green shelters put along a street, a story trail, a digital placemaking tool or an experimental civic curriculum [x], all these experiments necessarily touch upon the key conditions mentioned above, and can all be small and time-bound tests for broader and more ambitious innovations at larger scales - neighbourhood, district, whole city. Therefore, it is especially this prototyping and exploration characteristic of both placemaking possibilities and their enabling conditions that makes temporary uses particularly relevant to, and worth exploring as means toward the end of the SDGs.

[33] See: <https://sdgs.un.org/>

[34] These are all concrete examples of temporary uses and activities under development in T-Factor.

Within this context, from the outset of the design process the project worked to embrace and consider the SDGs within the local pilots. At present, the pilots are pursuing **19 thematic missions** (3 on average per pilot) which in turn are relevant to **11 SDGs**, as shown in Figure 27. **SDG 11 and 17 are central and apply to all pilots and the project as a whole**, as they reflect the core goals of T-Factor of contributing to sustainable cities and communities, and strengthening international partnerships for this goal. Within SDG 11 in particular, there are a number of targets that are at stake, including:

- Target 11.3: By 2030, enhance inclusive and sustainable urbanisation and capacity for participatory, integrated, and sustainable human settlement planning and management in all countries.
- Target 11.4: Strengthen efforts to protect and safeguard the world's cultural and natural heritage.
- Target 11.7: By 2030, provide universal access to safe, inclusive, and accessible, green and public spaces, in particular for women and children, older persons, and persons with disabilities.

Almost all pilots' missions revolve around capacity building for participatory and sustainable urban development; protection and preservation of local identity and heritage; and access to safe, inclusive and quality public spaces especially for the most vulnerable groups. There are several experiments of temporary uses and activities currently undergoing which can demonstrate concrete ways for addressing these targets locally, for example through collaborative greening involving NEETs (Not in Education, Employment and Training) and communities affected by redevelopments' disruptions; bottom-up harvesting and showcasing of local memories; capacity building

Figure 27: Relation pilots' missions - SDGs, own elaboration

programmes for children and young people on urban biodiversity, amongst many others.

Although it is too early to provide reliable evidence and success stories, there are emerging signs that **these crucial topics are getting higher both within the T-Factor's agenda and within local development agendas at pilot sites**. For example, both Milan and London's Local Coalitions reported **increasing openness and sensitivity of the developers** to leverage T-Factor in address to public spaces' accessibility and affordability, although attributing this effect to the project only may be highly questionable. More broadly, all the pilots have increasingly interrogated the ambition of their portfolios towards major challenges of sustainable urban development, and many of them went through situations of **re-scoping or re-adapting** so as to better or more explicitly address such challenges through temporary uses. Furthermore, almost all pilots are trying to address some of the **enabling conditions for temporary uses**, not only by exploring them at the small scale of a given temporary uses, but also working on **proposals and proofs of concept for Municipalities** and other relevant stakeholders. At completion of the project, it is expected that all these local actions and their outputs can form a **resonated, full T-Factor portfolio** that can show practical and holistic strategies of meanwhile intervention rooted in, and contributing to, the SDGs.

Moreover, as mentioned earlier, at the overall project level there is effort in place to document all the activities and temporary uses developed over time, so as to make them publicly available on the Toolbox. Within the latter, all the contents and stories can be filtered per various categories, including by pilots' missions which are linked to the six impact themes of the T-Factor's Theory of Change, in turn relevant to a number of SDGs as shown in **Figure X**. This is designed on purpose in order to help users retrieve content and possible inspirations for journeys or missions of temporary uses rooted in the SDGs. It is a sort of 'meta' contribution of T-Factor to the SDGs, particularly through tools and methods that can inspire others to take on similar actions and with similar objectives of sustainable and inclusive urban development.

Figure 29: Screenshot of the archive section in the Toolbox

Figure 28: Impact themes and relevant SDGs of the T-Factor's Theory of Change

CONTRIBUTION TO SDGS / HIGHLIGHTS

+19 thematic missions relevant to 11 SDGs

Target 11.3 / Target 11.4 / Target 11.7 particularly at play among pilots

SDG 11 and 17 apply at project level

Meanwhile experiments undergoing which can demonstrate concrete ways for addressing SDGs targets locally

Toolbox designed to inspire SDGs-relevant temporary uses

EU policies and initiatives

Inclusion, environmental sustainability and (social) innovation are the three building blocks of T-Factor from the outset. A number of recent EU policies and initiatives have been increasingly a point of reference for the project, especially within the process of clustering and collaborating with external projects. More in detail, the [European Green Deal](#), the [New European Bauhaus](#), the [Leipzig Charter](#) and the [EU Mission on Climate Neutral and Smart cities by 2030](#) are the main policies and initiatives of relevance for T-Factor.

A number of activities were organised during the period to start creating better connections with these initiatives. First, we shall recall the collaboration with the 'sister projects' [CENTRINNO](#) and [Hub-IN](#) initiated

in 2020. This collaboration is particularly important to support cross-project discussion and exchange on approaches, tools and methods to transformative urban regeneration, touching upon aspects such as the role of heritage and future of historic urban centres, governance and investment models, approaches and tools to systemic impact assessment. The cluster represents **26 European cities** and is committed to contributing to new regeneration approaches for urban areas in the transition to resilient, inclusive, sustainable, and vibrant cities across Europe. Regularly, the sister projects organise joint activities for knowledge sharing and internal coordination meetings to share learning and identify early opportunities for synergies.

The collaboration was kickstarted with the production of a joint **Manifesto and Action Plan** [35] aimed at synthesising the innovation aspirations and perspectives of the three projects. The Manifesto came from co-production and contribution across many of the partners of the three projects, and was disseminated within the related consortia, as well as at any joint event organised over time. It was followed by an online webinar in March 2022 called '[Regenerating Cities For the Post-Pandemic](#)', which gathered together EU level representatives across different policy areas (culture and heritage, research & innovation, urban agenda, social entrepreneurship), speakers from **seven Horizon projects** and **74 participants** in a discussion on how to measure impact in urban regeneration and transition pathways. The event was also a moment for the European Research Executive Agency to present how these approaches could be relevant to the EU Urban Agenda, EU Mission for Climate neutral and Smart Cities by 2030, the EU Green Deal, and the New European Bauhaus. Importantly, the Manifesto precedes a more comprehensive and articulated set of joint policy recommendations which will be delivered by the end of the project, as core output of the collaboration and learning gathered, exchanged and contrasted among the sister projects.

[35] See: <https://www.google.com/url?q=https://www.t-factor.eu/towards-innovative-inclusive-and-creative-hubs-in-european-cities/&sa=D&source=docs&ust=1669373971596566&usg=AOvVawOdXgirPubl8BcDqEBns33>

Regenerating Cities for the Post-pandemic: what counts for transformative impact

Webinar, 2 March 2022

In the aftermath of the Covid-19 pandemic and the context of climate breakdown in which we live, urban regeneration requires new and bold approaches to the way we reboot our cities and we think through and for transformative impact. This webinar, which gathered together policy experts from the European Commission and OECD as well as practitioners from different EU projects, discussed key challenges and opportunities for sustainable and inclusive urban transformations, and further showcased different approaches to impact measurement in this field.

+70 participants

Policy officers at EC and OECD, representing urban matters, culture, social entrepreneurship, R&I

7 Horizon projects exploring their approaches to impact (T-Factor, Centrinno, Hub-IN, Reflow, Varcities, OpenHeritage, CLIC)

Two events were also organised in June 2022 as side events of the New European Bauhaus Festival, namely the webinar "[Business Models for tomorrow's heritage](#)" and the three-days festival [Many Possible Cities](#) in Florence entailing workshops and discussions on the core themes of the NEB, with speakers from cities such as **New York, Barcelona, London, Bordeaux, Marseille, Amsterdam**, as well as from T-Factor's partners such as **Waag, University of the Arts London, LAND and La Friche**. This event was particularly effective in terms of outreach,

involving **+600 citizens, +40 experts** and receiving great exposure in local media and press. One important milestone was also the participation of the sister projects to the [World Urban Forum](#) in Katowice in July 2022; T-Factor along with the sister projects contributed to the session titled "**Just, Productive, Creative and Climate Neutral cities**" [36], discussing research and innovation approaches towards sustainable urban transformation.

While we can say that these different events may have helped build interest and momentum around T-Factor and the sister projects, more effort is indeed needed when it comes to depicting more direct contributions to relevant EU strategies and initiatives. For T-Factor in particular, more direct connections with the [Net Zero Cities](#) project are worth exploring in the near future, especially considering that some cities partnering or contributing to the debate within T-Factor - including **Florence, Prato, Milan, Lodz, Dortmund** - have been selected as part of the **100 climate neutral cities**. The opportunity in this case is that of specifically exploring the role that meanwhile use might play in supporting bottom-up just transitions, complementing macro level interventions for adaptation and resilience especially through the lens of civic engagement toward behavioural change.

When it comes to how the pilots are locally embracing and contributing to these policies and initiatives, we have already reported on this both within the pilots' chapters and in some passages above. Generally, there are three key overarching themes and policy priorities addressed across the pilots currently emerging the most:

Inclusive engagement - understood both through the process of designing temporary uses in address to a diversity of publics and communities' needs, and as actual uses and activities that provide concrete benefits to them.

Protection, preservation and enhancement of local identities and heritage - particularly through arts, culture and creativity-led spatial practices that help create a sense of identity, sense of place and belonging.

Greening and wildlife conservation and promotion - particularly through the intersection of greening and wild urban nature with health, wellbeing, active citizenship and individual and collective empowerment and capacity building.

[36] See: <https://www.t-factor.eu/just-productive-creative-and-climate-neutral-cities-world-urban-forum/>

As temporary use strategies around these themes are currently under full implementation, little can be said on their actual contribution to the policies considered. However, at project's completion, it is expected that concrete and tested experiments can help show a possible way forward to the local implementation of the said policies and strategies, inspiring and influencing more institutional support for their spread and scaling.

CONTRIBUTION TO EU Policies and initiatives / HIGHLIGHTS

Sistering with CENTRINNO and Hub-IN with a joint Manifesto and Action Plan

3 international events co-organised with the sister projects

Many Possible Cities as side event of the NEB

Pilots' focus on inclusive engagement, arts and heritage, and greening as key areas where to demonstrate the benefits of meanwhile uses

2.3.2. Contribution to policies for meanwhile uses

Influencing and boosting municipal policies, regulatory and governance frameworks for meanwhile uses across European cities is a critical factor for these practices to spread at scale and scope. Since the beginning, T-Factor worked in address to this challenging and ambitious objective. Back in 2021, the Advanced Cases Portfolio highlighted a number of challenges and criticalities around institutional support for these practices.

In 2022, this topic started to be addressed more explicitly, including through a number of research sprints and dedicated events such as:

- The research sprint delivered by TU Dortmund University as part of its support to Bilbao within T-Lab 6 [37]. This research investigated different cases of collaborative governance models for district management across European cities, and was followed up by a **dedicated event in Bilbao** in March 2022, which gathered together decision-makers and experts from the cities of Bilbao, Barcelona, Dortmund, Copenhagen, Gothenburg, Florence, Prato and the Tuscany Region.
- The online workshop '**Enabling Regulation for temporary uses**' organised in May 2022 under the lead of TU Dortmund University and the City of Dortmund, which brought together several cases and examples of institutional, enabling actions for temporary uses.
- The production of the T-Factor Manifesto. As a follow up of the enabling regulation event, a Manifesto has been drafted as a call to action to Municipalities across Europe to endorse meanwhile uses, through a number of specific recommendations and success stories provided as examples and inspirations. At the time of writing this report, the Manifesto is under finalisation. It is intended to be an intermediary step toward the production of a full package of policy recommendations by the end of the project, in the form of a White Paper.
- The event '**Policies for city making**' organised by ANCI Toscana and LAMA within **Many Possible Cities Festival** in June 2022, which saw the participation of +100 policy and decision makers across the Tuscany Region, and which discussed the state of play of temporary uses' policies and regulations through the experience of the Tuscany Region, Municipalities of Florence, Prato, Reggio Emilia and Bologna. The event was closed by the Tuscan Regional Councillor for Infrastructure, Mobility and Territorial Governance, who made an explicit call to action to all Tuscan municipalities towards the full adoption of meanwhile uses in urban planning and development.
- The submission of the project '**IMPETUS**' to the INTERREG programme in early summer 2022, developed by ANCI Toscana and

[37] See: <https://www.t-factor.eu/collaborative-governance-models-for-district-management/>

- LAMA on top of the conversations established with the Tuscany Region. If funded, this project will represent a major opportunity to complement T-Factor with a specific stream of work dedicated to policies and regulations for temporary uses. New municipalities such as Lille, Riga, Jerez de la Frontera and Regions in Western Europe are directly involved in the project, thus allowing also to expand the current cohort of cities involved or in conversation with T-Factor.

Over the period, T-Factor has been relatively successful in initiating a dialogue and triggering institutional interest around meanwhile uses. The number of policy-makers actively approached over time and/or involved in the discussion on possible institutional actions for temporary uses is **+40 for individual policy and decision makers** at local and regional levels mainly, while **10 are the Municipalities** across Europe so far engaged mainly through T-Factor events. Amongst them, the **Tuscany Region, the Municipality of Florence and Prato** are the ones where, at the central project's level, collaboration and conversations are more regular and goal-oriented. This is also due to a precise strategy of ANCI Toscana, as T-Factor's lead, to demonstrate the role of temporary or meanwhile uses across medium and small municipalities across the Tuscany Region, which could eventually unlock positive spillover effects in terms of influencing and showing a possible way forward to these practices across other territories and cities in Europe. However, at final

'I believe that meanwhile uses can be well beyond a tool to fill empty spaces and vacancies in cities. Against the complexity of the challenges we face in cities, meanwhile uses can bring about a novel vision of citymaking that can generate positive effects all along citizen engagement, quality of life, better planning, institutional innovation and more' (Valerio Barberis, Councillor for urban planning and environment, Municipality of Prato)

'We should start considering meanwhile uses as a way for planning and developing territories across the whole of the Region. It is a unique opportunity we have especially with the upcoming resources of the National Plan for Recovery and Resilience, and as a Region we should consider how to support these practices at scale' (Stefano Baccelli, Councillor for Infrastructure, Mobility and Territorial Governance, Tuscany Region)

Images of the 'Policies for city-making event', Photo credits: Besnik Mehmeti

Enabling Regulation for Temporary Use

5 May, 2022

Online workshop delivered in May 2022, organised by TU Dortmund University and the City of Dortmund as part of their support activities within T-Lab 6 Social Innovation and Inclusion. The purpose of the workshop was to showcase and discuss concrete cases of enabling actions for temporary uses at the local level (across policy, regulation, governance and funding, mainly), so as to help spread knowledge and provide inspiration for possible actions to be developed within T-Factor and beyond. The workshop brought together a rich panel of speakers, including:

- **Stephanie Haury**, German Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development (BBSR).
- **Dr. Robin Chang**, RWTH Aachen University.
- **Oliver Hasemann**, ZwischenZeitZentral Temporary Use Agency (ZZZ).
- **Jörg Jessen**, FreiRaumStation Agency for Temporary Use.
- **Stefan Sturm**, Gladbach and Westend in Mönchengladbach.
- **Lucie Renou**, Samoa Agency.
- **Emma Tytgadt**, City of Ghent.
- **Chiara Maresi**, City of Bologna.
- **Maxime Zaït**, Communa ASBL - Belgium.

The event was particularly important in the process of T-Factor towards policy recommendations for temporary uses. A T-Factor Manifesto was initiated after the workshop as an intermediate step towards a full package of recommendations by the end of the project. At the time of writing this report, the Manifesto is under finalisation and highlights six main areas of concrete action, including by offering practical examples and inspirations as emerged during the workshop.

release of the Manifesto, T-Factor may count on a more specific tool to reach out and spread the need of institutional actions across European cities.

Also in this case, it is too early to say whether the project is actually influencing and triggering change on policy innovations for meanwhile uses. Moreover, the **attribution factor remains a challenge**. However, the interest of some of the Municipalities involved so far; the breadth of the discussion undertaken during the events mentioned above and through follow up meetings; some political statements registered; and not least the INTERREG project submitted with the Tuscany Region and involving new Municipalities, may let assume that the project is in a **good position to spark positive effects on policy-making**.

We remain aware that the most ambitious scenario is a one where T-Factor's recommendations and learning start to be considered within local policies and strategies for urban planning and development, and some preparatory actions are initiated, for example via feasibility studies, dedicated working groups, small scale experiments and dedicated calls for funding. When it comes to regulation, this is instead a **much more complex and longer term challenge**, given the extreme diversity in which cities regulate access to space, change in uses and land development and management, as well as the relatively restricted margin of manoeuvre that EU institutions, the Commission in particular, have on this matter to enforce new rules and legislation locally.

CONTRIBUTION TO POLICY INNOVATION FOR MEANWHILE USES / HIGHLIGHTS

+40 local decision and policy makers actively engaged

10 Municipalities involved mainly through events

Manifesto with policy recommendations at municipal level under finalisation

INTERREG project submitted to explore specific policies and regulations for temporary uses.

CONCLUSIONS

| CONCLUSIONS

T-Factor is a complex and multi-layered innovation project focussed on urban regeneration and on the role that meanwhile uses in urban regeneration can play in **bringing forward impact and unlocking meaningful change at different levels and scales of intervention**. Starting from the *micro (or mission) level* of single meanwhile spaces and activities that are leveraged to create short to medium term opportunities and benefits for a variety of publics; followed by the *meso (or pilot) level* of the whole orchestration of meanwhile uses and their potential to deeply influence the trajectories of masterplans and regeneration processes; and finally to the *macro (or transnational) level* where systematisation of knowledge, knowledge exchange, and transnational collaboration can be key in supporting and advancing novel understandings, ways and tools for inclusive and sustainable urban regeneration.

The following points highlight the main learning and overall challenges encountered in the period considered for mid-term evaluation.

Understandings of the meanwhile

The topic of meanwhile and meanwhile uses in urban regeneration is far from being univocally understood as a possible lever for positive urban transformations and transitions to more inclusive, sustainable and vibrant cities. Especially where meanwhile practices already have history and curriculum, they may be surrounded by ambiguous understandings and contradictory feelings that, by extension, may apply to urban regeneration. Claims and concerns may be raised whether meanwhile uses are **another way to listen to needs or create expectations which will likely remain unheard**, adding to consultation fatigue where participatory engagement can be perceived as a way to extract bottom-up information with no payback. Or, as in the case of Zorrotzaurre's grassroots initiatives, 'meanwhile uses' is basically an unwanted label and a narrative that just hides and switches the attention from the fundamental threat to their stability and future in the area. If we are to advance meanwhile uses as the opportunity for participatory placemaking and inclusive urban regeneration, we should always

question how different people and communities understand and perceive this term and practice, and the extent to which these understandings encounter or contrast with each other, as well as with the vision of those who are actually driving the meanwhile strategy. And even when these perspectives land on the same orbit, the complexity and diversity of the interests at play require a very careful, aware and critical approach. **We should always ask ourselves *who is participating, why, how, with what perspectives and expectations***. Approaching meanwhile uses as ways to listen to and engage with as many voices as possible is thus key if we are to set the proper conditions for participatory and inclusive cities, even if this means risking continuous situations of lock-ins.

Meanwhile uses and urban challenges

Whether meanwhile uses can meaningfully address and contribute to solve pressing urban challenges is yet to be fully demonstrated. The often small and contingent nature of temporary uses may make them apparently unsuited for the scale and scope of actions needed. Yet, a potential contribution of meanwhile practices is essentially in the possibility to narrow down grand challenges into the everyday life of people and urban spaces. It means interrogating what climate breakdown, deprivation or lack of access ***mean and look like for those who are actually experiencing these issues, and exploring what can be done in the meanwhile for alleviating the effects while anticipating opportunities for mitigation and prevention in the long run***. Where a pilot managed to engage with a plurality of voices, we can observe more diversified portfolios aimed to test a number of different yet connected paths to co-benefits through meanwhile intervention, as well as a higher degree of willingness and perceived legitimacy to action towards urban challenges. Moreover, concrete experiments across the pilots such as 'messy corners', civic curricula, green shelters, digital placemaking tools and others necessarily require to interrogate the key conditions - ***across access to space, maintenance, governance, funding*** - that eventually allow learning and benefits to be scaled up. This in turn iterates **the need for meanwhile uses to go beyond interventions on physical spaces only**.

One point emerges especially when it comes to how meanwhile uses can help make cities greener and sensitive to biodiversity protection and preservation - a point that almost all the pilots are addressing, yet through different foci. Nature is typically slow and thinks in terms of seasons. Although we may all sense the fundamental role and value of nature vis-à-vis human life, whether this can turn into more awareness, motivation and willingness to (bottom-up) action is well beyond obvious. As we have seen especially in the Amsterdam pilot, the temporality of meanwhile uses may stand as a barrier to wide engagement with greening and eco-practices, because people might not immediately perceive the benefits of these practices through single events or in the short time. Moreover, if we are to really design cities *for and with* nature, we must begin to listen to and include voices other than those of humans, and **ask ourselves what the right to the city would look like if a tree, a bird, a frog could have their say**. If this is a long term challenge that requires us to embrace novel ways of governing urban assets - not to say to bring back the value and wisdom of indigenous cultures which we have denied or considered inferior for centuries in history, at least in the meanwhile we can begin to ask new questions and begin to spark novel understandings of rights to the cities that contemplate a variety of inhabitants, including non human.

Meanwhile uses and local agendas and interests

That meanwhile practices can effectively align and create synergies among different agendas and interests is one of the key assumptions of T-Factor, and yet an aspect that at the time of writing this report is yet to be demonstrated, especially through reliable evidence. Among the pilots, only Euston and to some extent MIND and Kaunas show some emerging, positive signs on this aspect, mostly witnessed by the continuous interest and participation of the developers to the project's ongoing evolution, increasing openness to explore and support temporary uses especially in address to vulnerable groups, and - in the case of Euston and Kaunas - with new, joint projects elaborated on top of T-Factor for additional funding. Nonetheless, even when these agendas align, there might be the risk that meanwhile uses serve the interests and decisions of those who are driving the redevelopments, instead of being a way to put them under question. Therefore, there is continuous, fundamental work to be done in terms of negotiating

interests and motivations. However, when the Local Coalitions were able to get the full support and commitment of the key regeneration stakeholders, this had a variety of spillover benefits throughout the meanwhile strategy, not least by overcoming blockages in access to spaces or identifying new opportunities for intervention early in time. One positive aspect can instead be said for all the Local Coalitions '*from within*', especially those who are participated by many partners and organisations locally. Generally, the process had positive effects on their capacity to work together; indeed, there was no shortage of discussions and conflicting views over time, and a lot of unplanned effort was needed to manage and overcome internal blockages. However, most of the Local Coalition were increasingly able to negotiate and find common ground, mostly as effect of ongoing dialogue and confrontation.

Meanwhile uses, placemaking processes and capacity building

The approach to meanwhile uses as an iterative, agile and emergent process largely stands as the unique feature of T-Factor. Although challenging vis-à-vis the typical linear thinking and culture of achievements in which we all tend to move and act, this process is proving beneficial when it comes to unlocking novel capacities and possibilities for meanwhile intervention and urban regeneration. It is also an approach most worthy of further implementation and exploration in response to rapid change and systemic risk, **but also against the typically different timings through which meanwhile uses, the broader regeneration path and in turn urban development and transformations happen and unfold** - if we want these layers to interact and influence each other towards spillover benefits. Moreover, meanwhile uses allow us to explore a diversity of topics within the local development context, and to build capacity around them (amongst diverse stakeholders) Promising examples demonstrate f how we can trigger bottom-up action towards greening and biodiversity, preservation and protection of local identities and heritage, upskilling and reskilling in emerging fields such as the circular and collaborative economy.

Meanwhile uses and urban spaces

The large majority of the pilots have concentrated their efforts and experiments on public and open air and green spaces. While this is

valuable in terms of how meanwhile practices can help unlock new functions, qualities and values of public spaces in cities, still this is a weak point when it comes to **demonstrating their versatility in leveraging a variety of spaces, including buildings**. There were reasons why most of the pilots had to opt for the said choice, including problems in access and availability of spaces during construction periods. In Aleksotas and Trafaria, for example, the Local Coalitions leveraged alternative spaces nearby the area under redevelopment as a way to overcome this issue. Similarly, Amsterdam, Milan and London pilots were mainly harnessing outdoor spaces, not only as a choice but also as a necessity. In general, this difficulty in accessing indoor spaces might also entail a certain resistance of developers and regeneration stakeholders in allowing access to buildings, including in terms of risking effects of attachments which may in turn makes it more difficult to sell or locate spaces at a later stage. Somehow, this is a core issue of meanwhile uses when they start to cross private interests and future private spaces, and across the pilots it proved to be possible only when there was a direct support from developers and regeneration stakeholders. All in all, **(bottom-up) access to space for meanwhile intervention largely stands as a highly challenging aspect in the period considered**, possibly reflecting a major issue and broader trend across European cities that we often tend to ascribe to 'gentrification' and general dynamics of displacement and replacement, but that in essence might signify a shortage in democratic access to city-making - or at least a shortage in democratic access to the capacity and resources required to implement meanwhile uses.

Meanwhile uses and operational capacity

Designing and delivering meanwhile strategies is a complex and demanding effort that requires proper capacities and a high degree of adaptation and flexibility to evolving conditions on site. Across the pilots, there was usually considerable time and effort spent on planning, delivering and following up. There were often multiple activities that followed each other in a relatively short timespan, which was necessary to keep engagement and momentum high, but also required a lot of planning. Typically, temporary use strategies require **articulated teams**, including not only design and management expertise, but also competencies and skills in facility management, communication, and more. Overall, the operational aspect has proven to be particularly

demanding, and in some cases created negative effects in terms of leaving time and space for more strategic and long term thinking.

Meanwhile uses and funding

Funding and spending are crucial aspects in the large majority of the pilots. In many cases, the financial resources provided through T-Factor were not sufficient to cover the scope and scale of the activities, especially in terms of covering capital costs or costs other than personnel and light equipment. However, some pilots such as MIND, Aleksotas and Euston were particularly successful in retrieving additional finances, especially when they deliberately designed and addressed meanwhile uses as ways to embrace local strategies and initiatives of sustainable urban development through multi-stakeholder collaboration. This may mean that when meanwhile strategies are conceived as 'platforms' for convening and hosting already existing initiatives and efforts, they could have more chances to pool resources and make better use of existing capacities and assets, tangible and intangible. One critical point emerges instead about **the need to make spending flexible, agile and less bureaucratic, hand in hand with the key nature and characteristics of temporary uses as practices by emergence and by design**. The way money can be spent or rapidly reallocated to different budget's headings is key if we want to remain open to possibilities and discoveries along the path. It would be also important that financial resources can be spent on hard materials and infrastructure, especially when access to buildings and indoor spaces is hard. Pilots such as MIND, Amsterdam and Zorrotzaurre were and keep on looking for ways to raise external funding to make this possible, as the T-Factor funding poses limitations on this.

'Additionality' of meanwhile uses

Meanwhile uses typically occur within broader and complex processes where many factors are simultaneously at play and influence each other. Proving what their added value is in urban regeneration is hard in general, and **hardly doable with attribution mechanisms and approaches**. Moreover, thinking in terms of outputs and outcomes only risks returning a heavily limited picture of what is really happening on the ground, especially when contrasting and projecting the results toward the long run of urban regeneration. What we have learned in this

reporting period is that the most interesting and valuable insights usually emerge from peer discussion and critical reflection, and through stories and anecdotes captured on site. While a lot of effort has been put on evaluating and assessing single activities, the return in terms of learning and understanding the pilots' evolution was somehow limited and often worked better through discussions and loosely organised moments of collective reflections. While we remain aware that some measured evidence is needed to contextualise and demonstrate the benefits of meanwhile uses and T-Factor as a whole, toward the next period we shall increase time and depth dedicated to ongoing reflection, particularly by putting the spotlight on 'soft' dynamics emerging all along the path and processes of running temporary uses locally, and contrasting and confronting them across the pilots and beyond.

/ANNEX 1

**CRITICAL
FRIEND
INTERVIEW**

DIMENSIONS	Guiding Questions
OVERVIEW	What have been the main achievements of the period? What worked well/what worked less well? What were your expectations, and what has been the reality?
STRATEGIC (The contribution of the Portfolio to value creation around the redevelopment)	
POSITIONING & REPUTATION	Is the visibility and reputation of the regeneration enhanced? Are local identity, heritage & values valorised and positive cultural and social evolution promoted? Which activities implemented brought visibility to the area? How? Which factors do you think contributed to the visibility or identity of the area & for whom?
ATTRACTIVENESS	Does the portfolio attract new target groups over time and raise interest from different publics? Are there elements missing that would enhance greater attractiveness? What would be needed to integrate them in the existing strategy?
RELEVANCE & OPPORTUNITY	Does the portfolio respond to pressing local challenges? Does it address needs and priorities of different people and groups, enhancing diversity and inclusivity? Does it create opportunities for aligning stakeholders agendas and pooling assets on shared objectives? Does it have the potential to create new partnerships and investments?
OPERATIONAL (the contribution of the Portfolio to effectiveness & efficiency of the regeneration process)	
PLANNING & DELIVERY CAPACITIES	Do you have the right resources (financial, human, technical) to run the portfolio? Are there activities generating or attracting additional resources? Which combination of innovative skills & knowledge is harnessed? Which other expertise and inputs might be needed to increase impact? Is the portfolio experimenting with new ways of planning, designing and delivering urban regeneration? Is it contributing to a new urban regeneration culture amongst developers and key stakeholders?
RESILIENCE, FLEXIBILITY & ADAPTABILITY	Has the portfolio allowed you to take more informed and evidence-based decisions? Has it transformed masterplans' assumptions over time in response to emerging needs and opportunities? Is it improving risk and conflict management and mitigation?
INTEROPERABILITY & CONNECTIVITY	Is the portfolio aligned with the other initiatives in the area? Are there newly identified or developed policies, programmes, schemes, initiatives or financial incentives contributing to the meanwhile strategy or that the strategy can contribute to? What might be needed to increase the synergy and dialogue between these initiatives? What might be needed to improve the synergy between temporary uses?
RELATIONAL (the contribution of the Portfolio to accelerating and anticipating time to impact towards the long term)	
IMPACT TIME & DEPTH	Is the portfolio accelerating time to results and achievement of goals of the wider regeneration initiative? Is it adding on results not originally envisaged? To what extent are the different actors involved aligned around local innovation missions?
AGENCY & LEGITIMACY	Is the portfolio contributing to empowerment, agency and legitimacy? Does it uncover novel ways of collaboration and collective decision-making?
LEGACY, SUSTAINABILITY & SCALABILITY	Is the portfolio leaving a concrete and tangible legacy? Is it evolving from the initial vision? Does the portfolio create conditions for a long term legacy? Does it allow you to sustain and boost positive results in the long term? Is it scalable and transferable to other contexts?

/ANNEX 2

**SELF-
ASSESSMENT
SCOREBOARD**

	Dimensions	1	2	3	4
STRATEGIC	Positioning & Reputation	The portfolio poorly contributes to enhancing the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is not properly valorised.	The portfolio partially contributes to the visibility and reputation of the area. E.g. Local heritage is considered but not a driver in the cultural and social evolution of the area	The portfolio brings a great visibility to the area and raises awareness about its heritage	The portfolio has provided the area with a new identity and its heritage is appreciated by diverse audiences.
	Attractiveness	The portfolio is raising limited interest and struggles to attract diverse audiences and target groups.	The portfolio raises the interest of target groups and engages with an unvaried audience on a local level.	The portfolio is compelling for all target groups and attracts a diverse audience both locally and from the surroundings	The portfolio is compelling and raises the interest of new groups and audiences both locally and from the surroundings
	Relevance & Opportunity	The portfolio addresses in a limited way local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are neither investigated nor pursued.	The portfolio addresses some local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Opportunities for leveraging on pooled assets are identified	The portfolio inclusively responds to pressing local challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. Expands opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets	The portfolio is adjusted to address new emerging challenges, needs and priorities. E.g. creates a number of new opportunities of leveraging on pooled assets.
OPERATIONAL	Planning & Delivery Capacities	The portfolio has limited resources and the retrieval of missing resources is yet to be defined.	The portfolio has some available resources and activities that could retrieve resources are under definition.	The portfolio is financially sustainable and activities/fundraising initiatives to retrieve them are in progress .	The portfolio is financially sustainable and has retrieved most fundings.
	Resilience, Flexibility & Adaptability	The portfolio has not identified emerging needs and opportunities that could have influenced the masterplan	The portfolio has identified some emerging needs and opportunities but strong 'evidence' is missing	Emerging needs and opportunities have been identified and masterplan adjustments are under definition	Emerging needs and opportunities have been fully defined and the masterplan has been adapted accordingly
	Interoperability & Connectivity	The pilot is not aware of other initiatives in the area and has not identified relevant policies and plans that could contribute to the meanwhile strategy	The portfolio is aligned with some initiatives in the area or policies and plans relevant to the meanwhile use strategy have been analysed.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are almost established. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy supported by policy programmes.	The mission is aligned with city plans and synergies with other initiatives are concrete. E.g. The meanwhile use strategy is contributing and supported by policy programmes.
RELATIONAL	Impact time & Depth (Too early to assess)	The portfolio results are requiring more time than expected and not all results and impacts will be achieved	The portfolio results are timely and most results and impacts are expected to be achieved.	The portfolio results have been achieved earlier than expected allowing to add additional uses for different groups.	The portfolio is involving and aligning around local innovation missions with a plethora of diverse stakeholders.
	Agency & Legitimacy	The portfolio does not contribute to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors to involve to build multi-sectoral coalitions have not been identified	The portfolio contributes in a limited way to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. Actors have been identified but must define how to involve them in multi-sectoral coalitions	The portfolio contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established	The portfolio strongly contributes to empowerment, agency and legitimacy. E.g. An inclusive array of actors has been involved and multi-sectoral coalitions have already been established
	Legacy, Sustainability & Scalability	The portfolio does not have a clear legacy.	The portfolio creates certain conditions for long term legacy but remains context-specific (not transferable).	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become more sustainable in the long-term. E.g. Scalability is being investigated	The portfolio legacy is clear and has evolved to become fully scalable or transferrable.

/ANNEX 3

ACTIVITY CARDS

To access the full list of pilots' activity cards:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1yocU2rmg8Z8YIKg-XX5r9Fg0oAejlziX>

t-factor.eu

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